

Archaeological Data Recoveries at
Sites HU-6 and HU-7
Río Antón Ruíz Flood Control Project
Municipio de Humacao, Puerto Rico

New South Associates
6150 East Ponce de Leon Avenue
Stone Mountain, Georgia 30083

ARCHAEOLOGICAL DATA RECOVERIES
AT SITES HU-6 AND HU-7,
RIO ANTON RUIZ FLOOD CONTROL PROJECT,
MUNICIPIO DE HUMACAO, PUERTO RICO

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Jacksonville District
400 West Bay Street
Jacksonville, FL 32202-4407

Report prepared by:

New South Associates
6150 East Ponce de Leon Avenue
Stone Mountain, GA 30083

Peter E. Siegel, Ph.D. – Principal Investigator and Author

with a contribution by

John E. Foss, Ph.D., Soil Scientist

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ABSTRACT

New South Associates conducted two Phase III archaeological data recoveries in conjunction with a flood control project located in the Municipio de Humacao, Puerto Rico. The data recoveries addressed the prehistoric deposits in Sites HU-6 and HU-7. This work was performed on behalf of the U. S. Army Corps of Engineers, Jacksonville District. Both sites are located in the Playas and Alluvial Plains physiographic region along the east-central coast and between the Río Antón Ruíz and Boca Prieta.

Backhoe trenches were excavated across each of the sites, which were examined and described by a soil scientist for information on the depositional and soil formation histories. One-by-one-meter excavation units were widely spaced across the areas of potential effect to investigate spatial variability in the artifact deposits. The historic overburden in selected areas of each site was machine-stripped, followed by shovel-scraping to search for cultural features.

Based on artifact densities (high, moderate, and low/sterile), three groups of excavation units were defined in Site HU-6. In total, 1,380 artifacts, predominantly prehistoric pottery, were recovered from 19 1-x-1-m excavation units. The major portion of the assemblage is contained within Stratum 2 (Bw- and BC-horizons), buried beneath approximately 40 cm of historic alluvium. The few temporally sensitive artifacts in the collection indicate a Monserrate/Santa Elena occupation. No features were identified in the site.

Initially, Site HU-7 was examined with 10 1-x-1-m excavation units. In doing so, a relatively dense well-preserved deposit of prehistoric pottery was located in the north-central portion of the site within the area of potential effect. Additional units were excavated in this portion of the site, resulting in 45 1-x-1-m units for Site HU-7. The depositional history for Site HU-7 was the same documented for Site HU-6, with the major portion of the deposit buried beneath approximately 50 cm of historic alluvium. In total, 2,990 sherds were recovered from the site. Contrary to Site HU-6, many of the sherds in Site HU-7 were large, and, in some cases could be re-fitted to form large portions of vessels. Twenty-three distinct vessels were identified across five vessel classes. Based on chronologically sensitive ceramics, Site HU-7 was occupied during the transition between the Monserrate and Santa Elena periods (ca. AD 900-1000). The densely occupied portion of the site corresponds in size to small or medium ethnographically documented Amazonian households.

Sites HU-6 and HU-7 represent small household-based settlements occupied for approximately 10-20 years during the transition between Periods IIIa and IIIb. The presence of other contemporaneous sites in the area, in similar settings, suggests that a well-developed adaptation centered around the extraction and use of coastal estuarine resources. These small household-based settlements were undoubtedly linked to larger networks of settlements, locally and regionally, across the post-Saladoid political, social, and economic landscape. Social and economic relations revolving around tribute may have been established by Period IIIa, associated with the earliest evidence for institutionalized social inequality on Puerto Rico. Small household-based camps dating to the post-Saladoid occupations on the island must be viewed as potential resource-extraction places in the primary production of tribute. This observation can only be

substantiated with complete and systematic settlement data for a polity. The social, political, and economic context must be considered when attempting to understand the function of any site dating to the post-Saladoid occupations of Puerto Rico.

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Fieldwork was ably conducted by Alvin Banguilan, Carlos Laboy, David Laboy Sanchez, Tasha Mannino, Anna Maria Ricah Josefa Borrás Marquez, Sean Norris, and Matthew Tankersley. Ms. Theresa M. Hamby performed a superb job as Field Director. Ms. Christy Bagwell supervised the processing of artifacts and data entry. Mr. Tony Greiner produced the report graphics. Dr. J. W. Joseph served as Project Manager and provided constructive input in the field strategy, analysis, and report synthesis.

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I. INTRODUCTION

PURPOSE AND GOALS OF THE INVESTIGATION

New South Associates (NSA) performed two Phase III archaeological data recoveries in conjunction with a flood control project located in the Municipio de Humacao, Puerto Rico. The data recoveries addressed the prehistoric deposits in Sites HU-6 and HU-7. This work was performed on behalf of the U. S. Army Corps of Engineers, Jacksonville District.

Phase III archaeological data recovery investigations were necessary to meet the requirements of a "no adverse effect" determination for the flood control project. This work was performed in compliance with various legislative and regulatory guidelines. Relevant laws and guidelines include the National Historic Preservation Act of 1966 (Public Law 89-665); the Advisory Council's Guidelines set forth in 36CFR800 for the Protection of Historical and Cultural Properties; the National Environmental Policy Act of 1969 (Public Law 91-190); Archeology and Historic Preservation: Secretary of the Interior's Standards and Guidelines (National Park Service 1983); Ley 112 para la protección de los recursos culturales de carácter arqueológico (Instituto de Cultura Puertorriqueña [ICP] 1988); *Reglamento para la radicación y evaluación arqueológica de proyectos de construcción y desarrollo* published by el Consejo para la Protección del Patrimonio Arqueológico Terrestre de Puerto Rico (ICP 1992); and *Guía para hacer investigaciones arqueológicas, fases I, II, III* and *Guía para preparar informes arqueológicos, fases I, II, III*, both published by the Oficina Estatal de Preservación Histórica (1993a, 1993b).

PROJECT HISTORY AND BACKGROUND

Phase II evaluations were conducted on Sites HU-6 and HU-7 by Panamerican Consultants (Cinquino et al 1995). In total, 81 shovel tests and three 1x1-m test units were excavated in Site HU-6, resulting in the recovery of 700 prehistoric potsherds, 70 rock fragments, 51 fragments of fire-cracked rock, 39 faunal fragments, 59 historic artifacts, and 10 miscellaneous artifacts (Cinquino et al. 1995:30, Table 1). The prehistoric pottery was interpreted to be primarily of the Santa Elena complex, followed by Cuevas (Cinquino et al. 1995:65-66). Prehistoric deposits were documented to a depth of 90 cm (Cinquino et al. 1995:70).

Site HU-7 was tested with 32 shovel test units. Prehistoric artifacts were recovered from the upper 60-70 cm of soil (Cinquino et al. 1995:34, 40). No chronological determination was made for Site HU-7. Cinquino et al. (1995:70-71) recommended that Site HU-6 is eligible and Site HU-7 is potentially eligible for listing in the National Register of Historic Places.

II. ENVIRONMENTAL AND PREHISTORIC CULTURAL CONTEXT

ENVIRONMENTAL SETTING

Puerto Rico is the smallest and most easterly of the Greater Antilles (Figure 1). It is 3,421 square miles in area and is included in the Greater Antilles Geologic Province. Puerto Rico is surrounded by the Atlantic Ocean to the north, Mona Passage to the west, the Caribbean Sea to the south, and Vieques Sound to the east (Figure 2). Approximately 75 percent of the island is characterized by rugged steeply sloped mountains. These mountains form the Cordillera Central, the Sierra de Luquillo, and the Sierra de Cayey. Much of the island's periphery consists of a coastal plain that averages approximately 5 km in width. Although the climate of Puerto Rico in general may be classified as humid sub-tropic, considerable variation exists within the island, from the mountains to the coast and from the island's northern shore to its more arid southwestern coastal plain.

Average annual temperatures in Puerto Rico range from 68° F in the highlands to 78° F in coastal areas (Beinroth 1969:7; Fassig 1911). Annual rainfall varies from 230 in. in the Luquillo Tropical Rain Forest (northeast coast) to 35 in. along the dry coast of the southwest (Beinroth 1969:7; Fassig 1909). The east coast area, centered by Humacao, is within the direct path of the easterly trade winds. Winds and rains associated with tropical storms and hurricanes impact the area (Boccheciamp 1977:97-99). Average annual rainfall for the Río Antón Ruíz area is approximately 86-88 inches (Boccheciamp 1977:Table 10; Fassig 1909:Table 1).

Puerto Rico is divided into seven physiographic regions: Mountain Uplands, St. John Peneplain, Caguana Peneplain, Foothill Zone, Interior Lowlands, Belted North Coastal Zone, and Playas and Alluvial Plains (Beinroth 1969; Mitchell 1954). Sites HU-6 and HU-7 are located within a portion of the Playas and Alluvial Plains physiographic region (Beinroth 1969:Fig. 1). Although most sections of this region are situated along the north and south coasts of the island, sizable pockets of playas and alluvial plains are found on the east and west coasts. In general, the playas and alluvial plains are flat and mostly sandy and located along the mouths of larger streams. The playas and alluvial plains date to the Holocene and Pleistocene ages (Beinroth 1969:11, Fig. 2). According to the Holdridge classification of ecological life zones, the Río Antón Ruíz project area is situated within the subtropical moist forest that constitutes approximately 60 percent of the entire island (Ewel and Whitmore 1973:72, Table 2).

The coastline along the southeastern portion of Puerto Rico consists of large rocky headlands and broad alluviated valleys (Kaye's [1959:Figure 6] Type B coastal landform; Morelock 1978:15-16). Long arcuate beaches of siliceous sand front the alluvial valleys. This section of coastline is considerably less indented than the north and south coasts (Kaye 1959:51, Figure 6). The broad alluvial plain of the Río Antón Ruíz shoreline is seen in Figures 3-7.

A number of large streams traverse the southeastern headlands and alluvial plains, originating in the Tertiary and Cretaceous hills of the St. John and Caguana

Figure 1
Map of the Caribbean Basin

Figure 2
Map of Puerto Rico Showing the Locations of Sites HU-6 and HU-7

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Figure 6
Aerial Photograph of Punta Santiago (Autoridad de Carreteras y Transportación, Oficina de Fotogrametría, 1936)

Figure 7
Playa and Alluvial Plain Fronting Sites HU-6 and HU-7, View to the Northeast (February 8, 2000)

Peneplains. High-energy water flows occur in the lower courses of coastal estuaries, resulting from high precipitation in the interior and oceanic swells pounding the coast. This combination of river flow and tidal motion results in high nutrient levels that foster the growth of mangrove stands in estuarine settings.

Five types of mangrove forests have been identified in Puerto Rico, which are based on topography and patterns of water circulation: fringe, riverine, overwash, basin, and dwarf forests (Lugo and Snedaker 1974; Martínez et al. 1979). Mangrove forests, in general, were important sources of natural resources for both prehistoric and historic occupants of the island. Large fragments of carbonized mangrove recovered from prehistoric sites on Puerto Rico indicate that this was an important fuel wood in antiquity (Newsom 1993). Several species of land crabs inhabit mangroves. These animals are considered a delicacy today in Puerto Rico, and judging from the abundance of crab exoskeletons in Saladoid middens, they were an important food source in the past.

Prior to Spanish contact, mangroves covered approximately 30,000 acres of land in Puerto Rico (Wadsworth 1959:59), although in 1969 Wadsworth revised this estimate to 60,193 acres (Martínez et al. 1979:14). During Spanish occupations of the island, mangrove trees were extensively harvested for charcoal and for wood in shipbuilding, construction, and posts (Wadsworth 1950:40-41, 1959:59-60). By 1974, approximately 15,800 acres of mangrove forests were remaining.

As of 1979, the largest remaining stand of riverine mangrove forest on Puerto Rico was located along the Río Antón Ruíz, covering an approximate area of 731 acres (Martínez et al. 1979:36-38) (Figure 8). The alluvial plain located south of Punta Lima, in the area fronting the Río Antón Ruíz, is subjected to relatively high-energy wave levels. In this area, mangroves occur as basins or riverine stands, and receive high inputs of freshwater runoff (Martínez et al. 1979:36).

Canopy heights of the Río Antón Ruíz mangroves range from 18 m to 22 m. Documented taxa of mangroves in this stand include bloodwood (*Pterocarpus* sp.), red (*Rhizophora mangle*), and white (*Laguncularia racemosa*) (Martínez et al. 1979:37, Profile 5). Sites HU-6 and HU-7 currently are located in an upland area adjacent to the mangrove forest (Martínez et al. 1979:Figure 8). However, prior to extensive destruction of mangroves during the historic period these sites were most likely situated within the mangrove forest.

Two major and four minor watersheds, with a total drainage area of 91 mi.², are situated in the east-central (Humacao-Naguabo) portion of Puerto Rico. The Río Humacao and Río Blanco are the largest streams in the area, each with drainage areas of 29 mi.². These are followed by the Río Antón Ruíz with a total drainage area of 11 mi.². Out of the six basins, the Río Antón Ruíz occupies the most alluvial land (10 mi.²) and least upland area (1 mi.²). The Río Blanco to the north drains the Sierra de Luquillo mountain range. To the south, the Río Humacao drains the Sierra de Cayey Mountains. Situated between these two ranges, the Río Antón Ruíz drains almost entirely alluvial coastal lowlands (Graves 1989).

Figure 8
Near Mouth of Río Antón Ruíz, Flanked by Mangrove Forest, View to the North-northwest (February 8, 2000)

Geologically, the project area is classified as Holocene and possibly Pleistocene beach deposits. These consist of unconsolidated fine- to coarse-grained sand and pebble deposits of quartz and feldspar grains and plutonic and volcanic fragments. The beach deposits grade into and, in small areas, are overlain by alluvial and swamp deposits. The mangrove stand lining the banks of the Río Antón Ruíz is described as Holocene swamp deposits, consisting of black to dark brown organic-rich soil and muck in a poorly drained alluvial plain (M'Gonigle 1979).

The soils of both Sites HU-6 and HU-7 are classified as Aguadilla loamy sand, 0 to 2 percent slopes (Boccheciamp 1977:7, Sheet 31). Aguadilla soils in general are coastal, excessively drained, and rapidly permeable. They formed in sands of mixed origin. The project area is included in the Coloso-Toa-Bajura soils association, which are characterized as "deep, moderately well drained to poorly drained, nearly level soils on flood plains" (Boccheciamp 1977:General Soil Map).

PREHISTORIC CONTEXT

Taxonomic Terminology. This overview follows the system established by Rouse (Cruxent and Rouse 1958-1959; Rouse 1964, 1965, 1972, 1986, 1989; Rouse and Allaire 1978) and modified by Vescelius (1980). This is a hierarchical scheme, whereby a specific cultural manifestation may be ordered into increasingly larger (or more general) levels of classificatory units (Vescelius 1980:38).

The most specific level of assignment is the "complex" (*style* is a synonym) (Rouse and Cruxent 1963:16-17). A complex is relatively narrow in time and space and refers to a local group. Defining the spatial (and sometimes temporal) limits of a complex is often a source of considerable debate among researchers. The complex is defined as the set of material cultural items, or assemblages, which distinguishes it from another complex. At the most general level of analysis is a "series." (Peruvianists use the term *horizon* [Bennett and Bird 1960:107], while followers of Lathrap [1970] use *tradition* [e. g., Myers 1973].) A series consists of a number of related styles that span a relatively large amount of time and space. Willey and Phillips (1958:33-34) point out that most horizons (in Peru) "have a 'slope' depending on the amount of time required for the spread of the elements used as horizon markers." Cruxent and Rouse (1958-1959) coined the term "series" in their study of Caribbean systematics (Rouse and Cruxent 1963:23-26). They noted that ceramic style distributions are not horizontal in this region and in fact are irregular. Intermediate between the style and series is the "subseries" (referred to as a *pattern* by Vescelius [1980:39]). As the term implies, a subseries consists of a subset of related styles that are narrower in time or space, or both, than the total set of styles defining the series.

The series name is denoted by an "oid" ending, such as Saladoid, Ostionoid, etc. The subseries name is recognized by the "an" ending, and modifies the series (e. g., Cedrosan Saladoid). Styles (or complexes) are named after the type site where the style was first recognized. Thus, the Hacienda Grande style, recognized by the distinctive complex of painted, incised, and modeled pottery and carved and polished stone items was defined based upon the excavations at the Hacienda Grande site in Puerto Rico (Rouse and Alegría 1990).

As emphasized by Vescelius (1980), this classification scheme is inherently flexible so that finer or coarser grain categories may be discussed. Thus, he argued that a complex may be subdivided into “facies” that represent specific activities (with the associated set[s] of artifacts) conducted by members of a local group (Vescelius 1980:39-40).

Rouse offered an alternative terminology based on “peoples” and “cultures.” He argued that:

Peoples are alternatively called cultural groups in order to distinguish them from ethnic and social groups. The three are defined differently: peoples by their cultures, ethnic groups by the cultural, linguistic, and/or racial traits through which their members identified themselves, and social groups by their personnel, organization, and functions . . .

Each people has an overall set of artifacts, customs, and beliefs, which we call its culture, focus, or phase, and which we contrast with its language. Each social group, on the contrary, has a more limited range of cultural and linguistic traits, depending upon its composition and functions. The group’s cultural traits are collectively known as its subculture (Rouse 1989:384, emphasis in original).

Vescelius’s complexes, patterns, and series are equivalent to Rouse’s cultures (defined by their ceramic styles), subseries, and series. Both Vescelius’s (1980) and Rouse’s (1989) schemes are hierarchical, thus allowing researchers “to express the degree of difference between individual cultures” (Rouse 1991:684). In the present study, the terms “ceramic style” and “ceramic complex” are used interchangeably (Rouse 1989:385). When referring to the entire assemblage of a complex, and not simply ceramics, the term “cultural complex” is employed. “Cultural complex” refers variously to the material culture deposited by a local group and to the local group itself. Therefore, the Hacienda Grande cultural complex is defined both as: (a) the material residues of the Hacienda Grande people, and (b) the local group who manufactured and deposited these material residues.

Caribbean and Puerto Rican Prehistory. Caribbean prehistory typically is divided into two major temporal blocks: pre-ceramic age and ceramic age. Each of these temporal blocks is associated with a suite of distinctive adaptive strategies. Archaeologists use these cultural-historical constructs as a framework for discussing changes in sociocultural integration. The cultural history provides an important framework within which archaeological research may proceed. It is important to note, however, that researchers disagree over many of the specifics concerning adaptations, cultural change, the duration of periods, and continuities/discontinuities of particular lifeways. Therefore, the outline presented here is viewed as a broad model, specific details of which may change with ongoing research.

A large literature exists regarding Holocene lifeways and adaptations in the Caribbean (e.g., Rouse 1986, 1992; Sanoja and Vargas 1983; Siegel 1989a; Keegan 1992; Veloz Maggiolo 1976; Wilson 1997). The purpose of this section is to review relevant research conducted in the vicinity of the Río Antón Ruíz project area. In addition

standard sources on Puerto Rican prehistory, a number of compliance and survey and planning studies were consulted (Daubon Vidal 1988; Figueroa Lugo 1986, 1990; Gonzalez Colón 1995; Meléndez Maíz 1999; Ramos 1984; Ramos Vélez and Meléndez Maíz 1991; Rodríguez López 1990, 1991; Rodríguez Morales 1987; Schlafer 1993; Shelton and Robinson 1999; Walker 1984).

Adaptations and lifeways of prehistoric groups are intimately connected to features of the landscape (Jochim 1976). Resources, travel, and habitation are important factors considered by groups when distributing themselves across the landscape. In addition, social considerations are evaluated by people and groups in decision making. This combination of social and physical requirements results in a cultural landscape that is unique in time and space.

The earliest human occupations for the Caribbean fall into the Archaic period, which is subdivided into two sub-periods: Early Archaic (ca. 5000 BC to 2000 BC) and Late Archaic (ca. 2000 BC to 500 BC). The initial peopling of the Caribbean islands, ca. 5000 to 4000 BC, was by nomadic bands of hunters-collectors-foragers who dispersed into the northern Caribbean (Cuba, Hispaniola) from the Yucatán Peninsula of Central America and into the southern Caribbean (Trinidad, Tobago) from the Orinoco Valley of South America (Harris 1973, Moore 1991; Rouse and Allaire 1978; Veloz Maggiolo and Ortega 1973; Veloz Maggiolo and Vega 1982; Wilson et al. 1998). These groups occupied rock shelters and open-air camps, depending on local topographic conditions. Implements were fabricated from shell and high-quality cherts available on some of the islands. Subsistence was based on the hunting, collecting, and foraging for small land mammals, shellfish, and crabs. Evidence for Early Archaic occupations in the West Indies is limited to Cuba, Haiti, Dominican Republic, and Trinidad (Dacal Moure and Rivero de la Calle 1996; Harris 1973; Moore 1991; Veloz Maggiolo 1972; Veloz Maggiolo et al. 1979).

By 2000 BC, Archaic groups had expanded through much of the West Indies, including Puerto Rico, the Virgin Islands, and portions of the Lesser Antilles (Armstrong 1980; Bullen and Sleight 1963; Davis 1974, 1982; Goodwin 1978; Lundberg 1989; Pantel 1988; Rouse 1952a, 1952b; Rouse and Alegría 1990). These groups were more specialized to coastal resources and occupied coastal settings more frequently than Early Archaic folks. Some Late Archaic groups were more sedentary and occupied larger settlements than Early Archaic people. In addition to hunting, gathering, collecting, fishing, and foraging for available plants and animals, there is recent evidence that Late Archaic peoples were systematically burning and clearing portions of the landscape, probably for small-scale horticulture (Siegel et al. 1999). In addition to the use of chipped-stone implements, Late Archaic peoples incorporated ground stone and shell tools into their tool-kits, potentially reflecting an emphasis on the processing and consumption of wild and cultivated grains and fruits.

Playa Blanca is the closest site to the Río Antón Ruíz with a reported Archaic deposit (Rouse 1952b:550-551). The site is located adjacent to a coastal mangrove swamp, approximately 10 km to the northeast of the Río Antón Ruíz. The site was described as a "shell heap." Artifacts collected from the site include one potsherd "near the surface . . . a stone chip, four blunted clam shells, three shell nodes, four plain shell tips, seven fractured shell tips, and two pieces of coral" (Rouse 1952b:551).

The Saladoid peoples who dispersed into the West Indies from northeastern South America approximately 2,500 years ago were horticulturists, who relied extensively on fishing and the collecting of marine and terrestrial faunal resources (DeFrance 1989; DeFrance et al 1996; Keegan 1985; Newsom 1993; Siegel 1991a, 1991b; Watters and Rouse 1989; Wing 1989). They produced thin-walled elaborately painted, incised, and modeled ceramic vessels and figurines; fine groundstone celts, adzes, beads, and amulets; carved and ground shell, bone, and coral objects; in addition to many everyday items fabricated from stone, bone, shell, clay, coral, wood, cloth, and feathers. Similarities in material culture across sites and through time provide the basis for assigning the groups to a single series of Saladoid cultures, named after the Saladero type site excavated by Rouse and Cruxent (1963). It is widely believed that the Saladoid peoples displaced pre-existing Archaic groups who were already occupying the Caribbean archipelago. However, the extent and nature of interactions between the ceramic and preceramic-age groups in the Caribbean are poorly understood (Siegel 1989b). Chanlatte Baik (1995) argues that Archaic and Saladoid groups co-existed and interacted, eventually resulting in the late prehistoric/Contact-period Taínos.

Evidence from site distributions and typologies, burials, and internal settlement structure indicates that Saladoid groups were relatively egalitarian in social organization (Rodríguez 1990; Siegel 1989b, 1992; Versteeg 1989). Grave goods associated with excavated burials are not elaborate (Chanlatte Baik 1979, 1983; Rodríguez 1991; Siegel 1992). Human bone chemistries do not reveal differential access to better-quality foods by some individuals (van Klinken 1991). Sizes and locations of Saladoid settlements do not reflect asymmetrical relations of power (Siegel 1996:Figure 3).

There are material cultural elements associated with late prehistoric/Contact-period Taíno rituals that appear also in Saladoid contexts. These are most clearly represented by three-pointed objects variously carved from stone, bone, shell, and coral, and which are a subset of the larger class of religious items called *zemis* (Fewkes 1891, 1907; McGinnis 1997; Rouse 1992; Walker 1993). Saladoid-period three-pointers were small and elegant in their simplicity. In contrast, three-pointers manufactured by the Taínos ranged from large and ponderously baroque in symbolism and imagery to small and undecorated. Three-pointers produced by groups chronologically intermediate between Saladoid and the Taínos were stylistically diverse, but the general trend from small to large and simple to complex is apparent (Walker 1993:43-45). Other materializations of Taíno rituals that appear in earlier time periods include snuff-spouts, probably for inhaling *cohoba*; elbow stones; and stone collars (Alegría 1986; Rouse 1986, 1992; Rouse and Alegría 1990; Walker 1993), although the three-pointer is the only artifact class to unequivocally link ceremonialism of the earliest Saladoid cultural complex with rituals documented by the conquistadores (Walker 1993). Finally, specific ceremonial components of Saladoid, Ostionoid, and Taíno villages were functionally the same, even as they changed in form (Siegel 1996). Artifactual and architectural elements suggest that ritual and cosmology, subsumed by the religious sphere of society, were part of an enduring tradition throughout the ceramic-age of the Greater Antilles and possibly the Virgin Islands (Morse 1989, 1990, 1991, 1992; Rouse 1992; Siegel 1989b, 1996, 1997, 1999; Walker 1993).

On Puerto Rico the Saladoid series is represented by the Hacienda Grande (early Saladoid, ca. 200 BC to AD 400) and Cuevas (late Saladoid, ca. AD 400 to 600) cultural

complexes. The Hacienda Grande style of pottery includes the most elaborately decorated and technically sophisticated vessels produced in prehistoric Puerto Rico (Rouse and Alegría 1990). It is comparable in form, surface decoration, and technology to the ceramic styles found on Grenada and associated islands (Pearls style; Bullen 1964; Bullen and Bullen 1972), Martinique and St. Lucia (Vivé style; Haag 1964), Guadeloupe (Morel I style; Clerc 1968), Antigua (Indian Creek style; Rouse 1974; Rouse and Morse 1999), and the Virgin Islands (Prosperity style; Morse 1989; Righter and Lundberg 1991).

Rouse has provided a detailed characterization of the Hacienda Grande ceramic style (Rouse and Alegría 1990:39-50). Many of the vessels produced by the Hacienda Grande artisans are extremely thin, often less than 5 mm thick, and tempered with fine sand (Rouse and Alegría 1990:39-41). In profile, the pots are S-shaped, often having one or more sharply angled corner points, referred to variously as keels or carinas. Bases are typically flat or slightly concave. Frequently, too, Hacienda Grande style pots come with annular or pedestal bases.

Vessel rims range from direct to concave on deep, shallow, and restricted pots. Lips typically are squared but it is not unusual to find rounded lips as well. Thin externally directed lip flanges are a distinctive feature of many Hacienda Grande pots. Bottles and jars are also characteristic of the Hacienda Grande style.

Secondary shape features are abundant and diverse. Handles range from open and D-shaped to flat tabular lugs appended to the sides of vessels or lip flanges. The open D-shaped handles frequently are surmounted by a protuberant button. The lug, or tabular, handles are often perforated with a small hole, but usually are solid. Tabular handles may be a continuation, but at an angle, of a rim. Frequently, tabular handles are built onto rim lip flanges.

In addition to the protuberant, or knob, buttons there are appliqué and dome-shaped buttons. Appliqué buttons appear singly and on the side of a vessel. These buttons typically are perforated transversely, possibly for suspending a pot with a cord (Rainey 1940:52; Rouse and Alegría 1990:42). Dome-shaped buttons usually are found on the upper surfaces of flanges, but also may be seen on complex effigies.

Effigies, as secondary shape features on Hacienda Grande vessels, are diverse ranging from elegantly simple to complex. They may depict real animals from the Saladoid landscape (including the South American homeland) or fantastic creatures that most likely were derived from the world of myth or trance, or both.

Carinas are corner points, or keels, on the sides of vessels. Technically, a carina is the junction of two planes forming an angle (Rice 1987:218). Carinas typically occur at junctions between lower and upper bodies and between necks and shoulders. The point of contact between a flat base and the lower body of a vessel is called an end point. According to Rouse, Hacienda Grande-style vessels are more angular in cross-section than pots from later styles in eastern Puerto Rico, which may have softer and more-graceful profiles (Rouse and Alegría 1990:41).

Flanges are predominantly oriented to the exterior, but occasionally a vessel will have a flange directed to the interior. Interior flanges are never as wide or elaborate as

outwardly oriented flanges. Exterior lip flanges are most frequently found emanating directly from the vessel rim. Often, however, flanges are built onto tabular handles or vice versa. Technically, a tabular handle is a form of flange that is interrupted rather than a continuous strip of clay defining the vessel perimeter. Flanges occasionally are placed below the rim on the body of a pot. These are termed sub-labial flanges (after Lathrap 1970:85).

The surface treatment of Hacienda Grande-style vessels visually is one of the most striking aspects of this pottery complex. The interplay of numerous surface decorative modes with a variety of vessel forms and secondary shape features result in an exuberance of visual messages, which undoubtedly had social and iconographic significance.

Surface decoration consists of various combinations of incising, painting, and smoothing or burnishing. One of the most distinctive features of the Hacienda Grande decorative modes is the style of white and red painting applied to many vessels. The typical method of painting was to coat the entire surface of a vessel, or a large section of it, with a slip. Usually the slip is red, but occasionally black, white, or orange was used. Over the red slip, designs in white were painted. There is a staggering variety to the kinds of designs painted. Most common, however, are curvilinear and rectilinear geometric patterns. The Hacienda Grande artisans employed sophisticated methods of pattern production, frequently alternating between positive and negative images (Rainey 1940:45; Roe 1989; Rouse 1952a:338-339; Rouse and Alegría 1990:44).

In addition to geometric designs, painting was used to highlight secondary shape features of a vessel. Handles, buttons, spouts, and effigies are often the sites of elaborately painted decorations. Incision is another mode of surface decoration. It may be used to outline areas to be decorated with paint or more incisions, or both. Alternatively, incision may take the place of painted lines. Delicately incised lines frequently are filled in with paint.

One distinctive style of incising, referred to as zoned-incised and crosshatching (zic for short), is a hallmark of the Hacienda Grande complex. It has been suggested that zic-decorated vessels were produced by peoples who colonized the West Indies prior to the Saladoid migrants (Chanlatte Baik 1979, 1983). Chanlatte refers to this as the Huecoid series, named after the La Hueca assemblage excavated on Vieques Island. Rouse (1989, 1992; Rouse and Morse 1999) concludes on the contrary, that while the La Hueca style is distinct from Hacienda Grande, Prosperity, or Indian Creek, it is still part of the Saladoid series. I too would include the La Hueca "style" within the Saladoid series. Further, I would not identify it as a distinct style, but include the La Hueca pottery as another ware produced by the relevant early ceramic-age groups (i.e., Hacienda Grande, Prosperity, Indian Creek, etc.) (Siegel 1991a:82-83, 1998:181, 2000:419). The Punta Candeleró site, located approximately 12 km south of Sites HU-6 and HU-7, contains a large assemblage of "La Hueca" style artifacts (Rodríguez López 1991).

Current understanding of the Cuevas complex places it from AD 400 to 600. This is based, however, on very few C-14 dates (Rouse et al. 1985:Table 4). Based on additional dates it has been suggested that Cuevas should be expanded by

approximately 100 years, or AD 400 - 700 (Siegel 1991c:Note 3, 1992:114). Oliver (1992:202-203) came to the same conclusion based on his work on Culebra. Stylistically, Cuevas pottery represents a developmental decline from the Hacienda Grande complex. The quality of execution in surface decoration exhibits a noticeable decline compared to the previous period and modeling and incision drop out of the ceramic repertoire. White-and-red painting is still maintained, however, "the complex curvilinear designs . . . give way to crude parallel lines before disappearing completely" (Rouse and Allaire 1978:472).

Morphologically, the distinctive angularity of Hacienda Grande pots is replaced during the Cuevas period with vessels displaying softer, more rounded profiles. In this context, corner points or carinas are rounded, rather than sharp, lip flanges disappear, and internal thickening of vessel rims are rounded. In addition, other secondary shape features are less elaborately rendered (compared to Hacienda Grande), decline in frequency of use, or simply disappear.

In general, ceramic vessels diagnostic of the Cuevas complex appear graceful in profile with soft corner points. The use of secondary shape features is limited to handles and diminutive buttons. Surface decoration consists of crudely applied white designs over red slip or buff. More frequently, vessels are unpainted but may be well-smoothed and polished.

In addition to simplification of ceramic design and construction techniques, concomitantly there is a simplification in the lapidary and shell carving arts by the Cuevas period. Shell and stone beads are still produced but details of engraving, incising, and general ornamentation are emphasized less in the Cuevas period compared to Hacienda Grande. Punta Candellero, mentioned earlier in connection with La Hueca, contains a large Cuevas component (Rodríguez López 1991). Site HU-1, located on Cayo Santiago, produced a handful of Cuevas-style sherds (Rouse 1952b:551-552) (Table 1).

On eastern Puerto Rico and some of the islands to the east (to Antigua), there were local developments out of the Cedrosan Saladoid cultural substrate. These local groups are collectively referred to as the Elenan Ostionoid subseries (Rouse 1992). On western Puerto Rico and most of the Greater Antilles, post-Saladoid cultures are part of the Ostionan Ostionoid subseries (AD 600-1200). On Puerto Rico, the Ostionoid series, in general, is characterized initially by a simplified repertoire of ceramic decorative and technological modes compared to the preceding Saladoid series. Ostionoid ceramic traits include polishing, applied and modeled designs, geometric line-and-dot incision, red painting over entire vessel surfaces, raised loop handles, flat bases, and thin rims.

Monserrate is the initial Elenan Ostionoid ceramic style (AD 600-900), although some researchers include it with the Saladoid series, referring to it as an epi-Saladoid style (Roe et al. 1990; Vescelius and Walker 1983:25). Originally, Rouse referred to this style as Tibes (Rouse 1982:Figure 1), but renamed it Monserrate (Rouse and Alegría 1990:53), after the name used by Vescelius (Carbone 1980:32). In his review of the Monserrate ceramic style, Roe reiterated Rouse's concept of clinal change in modal popularity: "The ceramics of Monserrate provide a perfect illustration of the continua of

modes throughout the sequence. In a sense, this makes cutting that sequence at any particular point in time a little arbitrary" (Roe et al. 1990:345). Nevertheless, there are characteristics of the pottery that permit cultural assignments to be made.

Rouse characterizes the Monserrate style as consisting of semi-globular bowls with thick vessel walls and rarely painted (Rouse and Alegría 1990:53). The only secondary shape features are loop handles. Rim flanges and transversely perforated buttons are noticeably absent (Roe et al. 1990:346). Continuing the progression of vessel profile "softening," Monserrate-style pots lose distinct corner points or carinas. Rounded internally thickened rims continue and become more pronounced with the Monserrate style and vessels begin to take on ovoid plan view shapes (Roe et al. 1990:346). Surface decoration consists of splotches of red or rose-colored paint applied to a buff background and of black smudging to create negative design patterns. Incision is rare. Usually vessels are unpainted and unincised. A few sherds of this complex were recovered from Site HU-1 (Table 1).

On eastern Puerto Rico, the Santa Elena period dates from AD 900 to 1200. The trend that began during the Cuevas period, with the gradual loss of paint, culminates with the Santa Elena complex. Ceramic vessels are now nearly always unpainted. Open handles disappear "leaving only vestigial ridges on the vessel wall" (Rouse 1982:50). On the other hand, incision, which dropped out of the ceramic repertoire with the Cuevas style, reappears with Santa Elena. The type of incising, however, is very different from the Hacienda Grande mode. Santa Elena incision is relatively thick and deep. It is frequently associated with vestigial handles, and in many cases the thick vertical incision helps define the handle.

By Santa Elena times, vessel wall profiles are smooth curves, rather than angular. In plan view, vessels are circular to navicular in form. Diversity of vessel forms is considerably lower compared to the previous periods. Adorno effigies are used frequently by the Santa Elena potters, but they differ considerably from Saladoid effigies. Santa Elena effigies are unpainted and relatively crude. Incised lines and punctations are used frequently in their construction. The Punta Santiago site, located less than one mile to the south of Site HU-7, contains a large Santa Elena occupation, as does Site HU-1 (Table 1). An "Elenoid" component was reported for Site N-5, located along the lower Río Blanco, approximately one mile to the north of Site HU-6 (Table 1).

The Esperanza period ranges from AD 1200 to 1500. Thick incision on ceramic vessels, described for the Santa Elena style, continues in modified form during the Esperanza period. The characteristic mode of Esperanza-style incision consists of "pairs of parallel lines, either semicircular or straight and inclined alternately in opposite directions" (Rouse 1952a:354). This manner of decoration typically appears as a series of chevron designs on the upper body of restricted bowls (Rouse 1952a:Plate 7, B and 7, J). Esperanza occupations are reported for the Punta Santiago site and Site HU-1 (Table 1).

Recently, researchers have proposed broad interactions within the Caribbean during the late ceramic age. This corresponds to the late prehistoric/protohistoric time period, or Chican Ostionoid in Puerto Rico and the Virgin Islands. The late prehistoric ball court located on St. Croix was undoubtedly connected in some way to the Taíno chiefdoms on Puerto Rico. It is certainly the case that the ethnohistorically documented

Table 1. Documented Archaeological Sites in the Vicinity of Sites HU-6 and HU-7.

Site	Setting	Cultural Association	Reference
N-4	Playa on Punta Lima	Surface deposit with shell and pottery. Petroglyphs.	ICP ^a
N-5	Alluvial plain	Deposits with shell, lithics, and Elenoid pottery.	ICP
N-6	Alluvial plain	Surface scatter of nineteenth-century artifacts.	ICP
HU-1	Low area between two hills on Cayo Santiago	Medium-sized shell heap, approximately 50 m in diameter and 75 cm deep. Cuevas (28 sherds), Ostiones [Monserrate] (11 sherds), Santa Elena (587 sherds), and Esperanza (63 sherds) pottery.	Rouse 1952b:551-552
Punta Santiago	Coastal plain	Large site, approximately 6.1 ac. in area. Santa Elena, Esperanza, and Capá pottery. Santa Elena component predominates.	Meléndez Maíz 1989; Ramos Veléz and Meléndez Maíz 1991

^{NOTE} Information reported here is taken verbatim from site forms, compliance reports, or publications.

^a Instituto de Cultura Puertorriqueña.

chiefdoms on Hispaniola and Puerto Rico were based upon carefully controlled movements of tribute. Wilson argued that "the ball game was a venue for interaction and competition between villages and larger polities and apparently had social and political ramifications" (Wilson 1990:24). If the Classic Taíno chiefdoms were fueled by domination and expansionism (an "ideology of domination" [Moscoso 1981]) then perhaps the St Croix ball court, and what it represents, is a product of this process. If so, the spatially expansive character of the Puerto Rican chiefdoms must have been moving east; Hispaniola was already spoken for. Perhaps the Chican influences are related to a kind of Taíno imperialism (see also Allaire 1992; Lundberg et al. 1992; Morse 1992).

III. FIELD METHODS

SITE HU-6

Archaeological fieldwork for Site HU-6 was formalized in the Scope of Work, which was approved by the PR SHPO (Appendix I). Specific aspects of the fieldwork included:

- Re-locate Phase II units, to the extent possible.
- Excavate four backhoe trenches, each approximately 20 m long, 1 m wide, and 1 m deep. Each backhoe trench will be examined by a soil scientist.
- Hand excavate 15 1-x-1-m test units.
- Machine-remove the plowzone and shovel-scrape a 20 x 20-m size area searching for cultural features.

Certain aspects of the proposal were revised as fieldwork proceeded. Namely, 19 1-x-1-m test units were excavated and approximately 445 square meters of overburden were mechanically removed. Areas of mechanical excavation were distributed across three blocks.

SITE HU-7

Proposed fieldwork for Site HU-7 was similar in kind to that listed above for Site HU-6. It differed in degree or intensity of investigation:

- Re-locate Phase II units, to the extent possible.
- Excavate two backhoe trenches, each approximately 20 m long, 1 m wide, and 1 m deep. Each backhoe trench will be examined by a soil scientist.
- Hand excavate 10 1-x-1-m test units.
- Machine-remove the plowzone and shovel-scrape a 10 x 15-m size area searching for cultural features.

Four backhoe trenches and 45 1-x-1-m test units were excavated. Overburden was mechanically removed from an area of approximately 422 square meters.

Field Recording Techniques

Initially, all test units were excavated in 10-cm levels within natural layers. As information was obtained about the depositional history, especially with input from the soil scientist, this strategy was modified appropriately. Namely, it was learned that approximately the upper 50-60 cm of soil in the area consisted of historic alluvium. This

information, combined with the paucity of prehistoric artifacts in the historic overburden, resulted in the decision to abandon 10-cm arbitrary levels in this upper deposit.

All hand-excavated sediments were sifted through 1/4-inch hardware cloth to ensure the uniform recovery of artifacts. Unit levels were also hand troweled and soils in the screens were troweled to aid in the identification of artifacts smaller than 1/4 inch. Standardized forms were used to record depth measurements, soil textures and Munsell colors, artifact contents, and general observations. At least one wall of each test unit was drawn and photographed. Photographs were taken to document the project area and fieldwork in progress.

IV. RESULTS

SITE HU-6

Site HU-6 is located along the south bank of the Río Antón Ruíz (Figure 3). Cinquino et al. (1995:30) indicated that 81 shovel tests and three 1-x-1-m units were excavated in this site during the Phase II evaluation. They state that "over 50 shovel tests were positive" (Cinquino et al. 1995:30). In their map of the site, 64 shovel tests are depicted, 41 of which are positive. The positive shovel tests are concentrated to the southern portion of the area tested (Cinquino et al. 1995:Figure 6).

Using the Phase II results as a general guide, the Phase III excavation units were judgmentally distributed across the portion of the site within the right-of-way to characterize the spatial and density distributions of artifacts. Results of these excavations were used to guide the follow-up stripping.

The data recovery fieldwork was conducted in four stages:

Stage 1. Stage 1 consisted of establishing a grid and correlating the engineering base map to the project area (Figures 9 and 10). To this end, swaths of forest were cleared using heavy equipment, creating lines of sight and areas for placing trenches and excavation units (Figure 11). The grid datum (N0E0) was placed in a large cleared area, approximately 32 m from the north shoulder of Highway 3. One of Panamerican's shovel test pin flags was located, labeled as T6E#2. On the current grid, Panamerican Shovel Test T6E#2 corresponds to N125E37.

Stage 2. After establishing the grid, two 1-x-1-m units and, in consultation with the soil scientist, five backhoe trenches were excavated in selected areas (Figures 10 and 12).

Stage 3. After reviewing the trench profiles, an additional 17 1-x-1-m excavation units were distributed across the site area.

Stage 4. On completion of the excavation units, three block areas were selected for machine removal of the plowzone and historic alluvium. These areas totaled approximately 450 m².

Stratigraphy

Dr. John Foss, the project soil scientist, described eight backhoe trench and excavation unit profiles across the site area (Appendix II). In general, soils in the site consist of sand or loamy sand with little soil development. Recognizable soil horizons include an A/A_p, weakly developed B_w, and a transitional BC. One or more C-horizons were documented, all comprised of calcareous sands in the lower depths. Depending on the location of a test unit or trench, the water table was encountered from 50 to 100 cm below ground surface (Figures 13 and 14).

A portion of the Trench 1 profile is depicted in Figure 15. This profile is typical of the stratigraphy across the site. The upper 30 cm consists of a dark brown (10YR 3/3)

Figure 9
Site HU-6 Grid Plotted on Engineering Base Map

Figure 10 Locations of Excavation Units, Backhoe Trenches, Mechanically Stripped Areas, and Distinctive Artifacts in Site HU-6

Figure 11
Clearing a Swath of Vegetation Across Site HU-6 (January 10, 2000)

Figure 12
Backhoe Trench 2 in Site HU-6 Examined by Dr. John E. Foss (January 12, 2000)

Figure 13
North Wall of EU 16 (Site HU-6)

Figure 14
Mechanically Stripped Block 1 in Site HU-6,
Showing the Water Table at Approximately 60 cm.

Figure 15
Portion of Backhoe Trench 1 Stratigraphic Profile (Site HU-6)

loamy sand Ap horizon. This is underlain by a weakly developed Bw-horizon, characterized by brown (10YR 4/3) to dark grayish brown (10YR 4/2) loamy sand with some iron coatings on sand grains, approximately 17 cm thick. A transitional BC-horizon, approximately 20 cm thick, underlies the Bw-horizon. The BC-horizon consists of brown (10YR 5/3) to grayish brown (10YR 5/2) sand, with many medium-size and distinct yellowish brown (10YR 5/8) mottles. The trench bottomed out in three horizons of unweathered parent material: Cg1, Cg2, and Cg3. The Cg1 (25 cm thick) consists of grayish brown (10YR 5/2) to brown (10YR 5/3) sand with many medium-size and distinct yellowish brown (10YR 5/8) mottles. The Cg2-horizon (30 cm thick) has the same color and mottle characteristics as the Cg1; texturally, it consists of calcareous sand. The trench terminated at 1.5 m in gray (2.5Y 5/1) to dark gray (5Y 4/1) calcareous sand (Cg3 horizon).

Square Excavation Units

Nineteen 1-x-1-m units were excavated in Site HU-6 (Figures 9 and 10). These units were broadly dispersed across the site to investigate spatial variability in the artifact deposits. Three groups of excavation units were defined on the basis of artifact density: high, moderate, and low/sterile.

Eight units were low in artifact density to culturally sterile: EUs 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10-13, and 16. These were followed by five moderately dense units: EUs 3, 6, 8, 14, and 18. Artifact densities were highest in EUs 15, 17, and 19. Based on artifact densities, the central portion of the project area was the most intensively occupied. The three highest and two of the moderately dense units are located in this central area (Figures 9 and 10).

Figure 16 depicts the stratigraphic weight distributions of pottery by excavation unit. Stratigraphically, the densest portion of the deposit is situated from approximately 25 cm to 50 cm below ground surface (Figure 16). This dense portion of the deposit corresponds generally to the Bw- and BC-soil horizons. The majority of artifacts recovered from the site consists of prehistoric pottery.

For analytical purposes, the artifact assemblage was divided into three stratigraphic units: plowzone (Ap-horizon), Bw/BC-horizon, and the C/Cg-horizon. The vertical distributions of pottery were viewed against the pedological descriptions of the trenches to establish these units. The stratigraphic units served to structure the analysis of spatial and vertical patterning in the artifact distributions. The analytical units are depicted on Figure 16 as Strata 1, 2, and 3.

In total, 1,380 artifacts, weighing 5.25 k (11.61 lbs.), were recovered from Site HU-6 (Table 2, Appendix III). Of these, 820 artifacts (59.42% of total) were prehistoric pottery fragments. Shell fragments accounted for 463 pieces (33.55% of total) of the assemblage. The remainder of the assemblage consisted of coral (55 fragments, 3.98% of total) and charcoal (41 fragments [8.5 g], 2.97% of total). By weight, 88.48 percent of the assemblage consisted of pottery (4.64 k [10.25 lbs.]), followed by shell (6.40%, .33 k [.74 lbs.]), coral (2.51%, .13 k [.29 lbs.]), and charcoal (.16%, 8.5 g [.29 oz.]). The shell and coral fragments are very small and most likely constitute natural inclusions in the sandy beach deposits. The Holocene and Pleistocene beach deposits located in this portion of

Stratigraphic weight distributions of prehistoric pottery by excavation unit in Site HU-6. Excavation Units 7 and 9 were culturally sterile. Figure 16

Table 2. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Site HU-6.

Stratum	Pottery		Hammerstone		Shatter		Shell		Coral		Charcoal		Total	
	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)
1	198	788.7	1	125.9	2	2.2	160	147.6	37	86.2	9	<1	407	1,150.6
2	519	3,275.8					36	96.2	7	14.9	32	8.5	594	3,395.4
3	103	584.1					267	92.5	11	31.1			381	707.7
Total	820	4,648.6	1	125.9	2	2.2	463	336.3	55	132.2	41	8.5	1,380	5,253.7

the coast, south of Ensenada Honda, contain considerable quantities of shell and coral fragments (M'Gonigle 1979). It was decided to retain a sample of these ecofacts to document the sedimentary context of the site deposits. Worked shell or coral artifacts were not recovered from the site, although one of the pieces of coral appears to have used as an abrading implement (Figure 17a).

The ceramic assemblage was divided into rim types, bases, and body sherds (Tables 3 and 4). Body sherds represent 90.94 percent by count (743 sherds) and 86.91 percent by weight (4,014.5 g) of the assemblage. Of the rim sherds, 9 are fragments of concave vessels, 5 of shallow and convex vessels, 12 of restricted vessels, 13 of deep and convex vessels, and 31 of unidentifiable vessel types (Table 3).

The major portion of the ceramic assemblage is contained within Stratum 2 (Bw- and BC-horizons): 63.52 percent (by count) or 70.19 percent (by weight) of all pottery. Of the Stratum 2 pottery, 90.36 percent by count ($n=469$) or 86.11 percent by weight (2,821 g) are comprised of body sherds.

Stem-and-leaf statistics were generated using total artifact weights per stratum and excavation unit (Table 5). Excavation units were ranked into high, moderate, and low artifact density ranges for each stratum (Table 6). In general, units were rather consistent across strata in terms of artifact densities. EU 8 is the only unit that diverged more than one level of artifact density across the three strata (Stratum 1=high, Stratum 2=moderate, Stratum 3=low). This anomaly is explained by the presence of a possible hammerstone (125.9 g) in Level 1 of the unit. The possible hammerstone (Figure 17b) was associated with two pieces of chert shatter (Figure 17c), one of which was covered by cortex over two-thirds of the dorsal surface. Subtracting the possible hammerstone from the assemblage would bring EU 8, Stratum 1 down to the moderate artifact density level.

The general consistency in relative artifact densities across strata in the various sections of the site, combined with pedological development forming Bw- and BC-horizons, suggests a relatively stable surface at some time in the past, during which the archaeological deposit was formed. Further, if several distinct cultural occupations were present then we would expect greater divergence in artifact densities from stratum to stratum or level to level than what is apparent in Table 6. The loose sandy structure of the site sediments undoubtedly results in considerable translocation of artifacts from their original depositional context. Burrowing organisms, such as crabs, roots, and rodents, are notorious for moving artifacts, up and down, through site sediments. Thus, many of the artifacts collected from the A- and C-horizons probably have been translocated from the Bw- and BC-horizons.

The range of vessel types represented in the Site HU-6 ceramic assemblage is rather low. In total, 70 rim sherds were recovered, 31 of which were too small to identify vessel type (Table 3). Of the remaining rim sherds, deep and convex vessels were the most prevalent (by count and weight), followed by restricted rims, concave rims, and shallow and convex rims. In the HU-6 assemblage, most of the shallow and convex vessels have external lip flanges appended to the rims (Figures 18-20), similar to some vessel profiles illustrated by Rouse for the Ostiones style (Rouse 1952a:Figure 2, I,

Table 3. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Pottery Recovered from Site HU-6.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Deep and Convex Rims		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)
1	1	9.9			6	36.2	1	20.2	11	41.5	19	107.8
2	5	57.8	5	56.2	6	63.6	10	138.4	20	48.9	46	364.9
3	3	24.5					2	17.5			5	42.0
Total	9	92.5	5	56.2	12	99.8	13	176.1	31	90.4	70	514.7

Table 4. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases and Body Sherds Recovered from Site HU-6.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds and Bases		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1			176	651.4	176	651.4	195	759.2
2	4	89.9	469	2,821.0	473	2,910.9	519	3,275.8
3			98	542.1	98	542.1	103	584.1
Total	4	89.9	743	4,014.5	747	4,104.4	817	4,619.1

Table 5. Stem-and-Leaf Statistics for Total Artifact Weights (g) by Excavation Unit and Stratum in Site HU-6

Stratum	Minimum	Maximum	Median	Lower Hinge	Upper Hinge
1	0.0	265.0	40.9	18.7	76.4
2	0.0	1,095.0	44.3	7.15	149.5
3	0.0	156.4	5.0	0.0	56.9

Table 6. Site HU-6 Excavation Units Ranked by Artifact Densities Per Stratum based on Stem-and-Leaf Statistics.

Excavation Unit	Stratum 1			Stratum 2			Stratum 3		
	High	Moderate	Low	High	Moderate	Low	High	Moderate	Low
1	X				X		X		
2	X				X			X	
3	X			X				X	
4		X			X				X
5		X			X			X	
6		X			X				X
7			X			X			X
8	X				X				X
9			X			X			X
10		X				X		X	
11		X				X			X
12			X		X				X
13			X		X				X
14		X				X			X
15		X		X			X		
16			X		X			X	
17	X			X			X		
18		X		X			X		
19		X		X			X		
Total	5	9	5	5	9	5	5	5	9

Figure 17. Exterior Photograph and Profile of Shallow and Convex Rim with External Lip Flange, Backhoe Trench 4 (Site HU-6)

Figure 18

Exterior Photograph and Profile of Shallow and Convex Rim with
External Lip Flange, Backhoe Trench 4 (Site HU-6)

Approximately 30 cm

Figure 19
Interior Photograph and Profile of Shallow and Convex Rim with
External Lip Flange, EU 17, Level 4 (Site HU-6)

Figure 20
Exterior Photograph and Profile of Shallow and Convex Rim with
External Lip Flange, EU 19, Level 3 (Site HU-6)

Figure 21
Interior Photograph and Profile of Restricted Rim with
Internal Thickening, EU 13, Level 3 (Site HU-6)

Internally Thickened Rim

Figure 22
Fragment of a Vertically Incised Handle
EU 4, Level 1 (Site HU-6)

M). The majority of the restricted rims are direct with rounded lips. One of the restricted vessels has rounded internal thickening of the rim (Figure 21), very similar to that depicted by Rouse for the Santa Elena style (Rouse 1952a:Figure 2, Q). Two fragments of vestigial handles with thick vertical incisions are present, both collected from Stratum 1 in EU 4 (Figure 9). This type of handle is distinctive of the Santa Elena style (Figure 22). EU 4 also produced an unslipped body sherd with portions of the interior painted red; this form of surface treatment is characteristic of the Monserrate style.

These limited data minimally indicate a Santa Elena occupation and perhaps an earlier Monserrate (called Ostiones in Rouse's [1952a] publication) occupation. Based on the locations of chronologically distinctive sherds, the Santa Elena occupation is broadly dispersed across the portion of the site located within the APE; there may be a small Monserrate occupation limited to the northern and eastern edges of the excavated portion of the site (EUs 4 and 14). Site HU-6 clearly extends outside of the APE, to the north and south of the right-of-way (Figure 9). The Río Antón Ruíz is located approximately 30 m to the north of the APE.

Machine Stripping of Block Areas

Three block areas were selected for machine removal of historic alluvium to search for cultural features (Figures 10 and 14). The trackhoe operator was directed to carefully remove a few inches of soil at a swipe for a large area, after which the archaeologists shovel-scraped and examined the soil for any evidence of features. Each block was systematically stripped in this manner, to a depth of approximately 60 cm (well into the B-horizon).

Block locations were selected in relation to a combination of high, moderate, and low artifact density excavation units. No features were identified. Foss noted that "the upper 50 to 80 cm of sands have been leached of their carbonates during the weathering process" (Appendix II). Such leaching will frequently remove organic residues that are used to identify postmolds and pit features. However, pit features that contain artifacts should still be identifiable by intact concentrations of artifacts; none of these were documented.

SITE HU-7

Site HU-7 is located approximately 460 m (1,509 ft.) to the south of Site HU-6. Cinquino et al. (1995:34) indicate that 32 shovel tests were excavated in this area for the Phase II evaluation, 21 of which produced artifacts. Their map of Site HU-7 shows 34 shovel tests, 20 of which were positive (Cinquino et al. 1995:Figure 7). No 1-x-1-m units were excavated in the Phase II evaluation.

Fieldwork for the data recovery was designed to characterize the spatial and density distributions of artifacts within the right-of-way, followed by more extensive hand excavations and mechanical stripping in particularly productive sections of the site.

Six stages of fieldwork were conducted for the data recovery.

Figure 23
Site HU-7 Grid Plotted on Engineering Base Map

Figure 24
Locations of Excavation Units, Backhoe Trenches, and Mechanically Stripped Area in Site HU-7

Stage 1. The project area was cleared of trees and a grid was established, which was referenced to the engineering base map (Figure 23).

Stage 2. In consultation with the soil scientist, four backhoe trenches were excavated across the Site HU-7 project area (Figure 24).

Stage 3. After reviewing the backhoe trenches with the soil scientist, locations for 10 1-x-1-m test units were marked.

Stage 4. On completion of the initial 10 units, additional 1-x-1-m units were excavated in particularly productive portions of the site and a series of shovel tests was excavated to assess the northwestern boundary of the site.

Stage 5. Historic alluvium was removed by machine from a section of the site approximately 420 m² in area (Figure 25).

Stage 6. Following preliminary analysis of the artifacts, and in consultation with the USACE, a follow-up round of fieldwork was conducted to address an intensively occupied portion of the site.

Stratigraphy

With some exceptions, the soils in Site HU-7 are the same as those described for Site HU-6. Four backhoe trenches were excavated across this portion of the project area, all of which were described by Foss (Appendix II). Backhoe Trench 1, excavated in the southeastern section of the site, revealed a particularly poorly drained area, intersecting the water table at 52 cm. Preserved wood was collected from this trench at 130 cm, although no evidence of a buried A horizon was observed. Preserved wood was also collected from Backhoe Trench 4 at approximately 130 cm. The Trench 4 wood was retrieved from a buried A-horizon (2Ab), consisting of mottled very dark gray (10YR 3/1) calcareous sand. A buried A-horizon (2Ab), associated with a considerable amount of pottery, was identified at 63 to 70 cm in Backhoe Trench 3B. The Trench 3B buried A-horizon consisted of very friable mottled brown (10YR 4/3) loamy sand. Based on stratigraphy and soil characteristics, the buried A-horizons documented in Trenches 3B and 4 represent separate surfaces and different periods of time (Appendix II).

A portion of the Trench 3B profile is depicted in Figure 25. The Ap-horizon, approximately 7 cm thick, consists of dark brown (10YR 3/3) to brown (10YR 4/3) very friable loamy sand. This is underlain by a 15-cm thick BA-horizon, characterized by yellowish brown (10YR 5/4) to dark yellowish brown (10YR 4/4) loose sand with few medium-sized distinct yellowish brown (10YR 5/8) mottles. The BA-horizon is underlain by the Bw-horizon, approximately 40 cm thick. This is a layer of yellowish brown (10YR 5/4) to dark yellowish brown (10YR 4/4) loose loamy sand with many medium-sized distinct mottles. The buried A-horizon (2Ab-horizon) is positioned from 63 to 70 cm and consists of brown (10YR 4/3) very friable loamy sand with many fine distinct yellowish brown (10YR 5/8) mottles. This is underlain by the 2C1-horizon (70-90 cm), which consists of brown (10YR 5/3) to yellowish brown (10YR 5/4) very friable loamy sand with many medium-sized distinct yellowish brown (10YR 5/8) mottles. The trench terminated at 103 cm in the 2C2g-horizon, characterized by gray (2.5Y 5/1) loose

calcareous sand with common medium-sized distinct dark yellowish brown (10YR 4/4) mottles.

Square Excavation Units

The project scope of work specified the excavation of ten 1-x-1-m test units across Site HU-7 (Appendix I). These ten units were widely spaced across the area of potential effect to evaluate the spatial and density distribution of artifacts (Figures 23 and 24).

Shallow poorly drained soils were documented in the southern portion of the APE, a finding congruent with Foss's observations of Backhoe Trench 1. Excavation Units 5, 6, and 9, located in the southern portion of the APE, were culturally sterile. A small amount of prehistoric pottery was recovered from units excavated in the central portion of the APE, just to the north of the sterile southern excavation units. Excavation Units 7 and 8 yielded 4 and 9 sherds, respectively. Likewise, Excavation Units 4 and 10, placed in the west-central and western portion of the APE, were relatively unproductive (4 and 0 artifacts, respectively).

Units excavated in the vicinity of Backhoe Trench 3A and 3B produced relatively many artifacts (EU 1 [126 sherds] and EU 2 [18 sherds]). EU 3, placed near Backhoe Trench 4, produced 46 sherds. At this stage, the field portion of the original scope of work was completed; 10 1-x-1-m units had been excavated across the site area as defined by the Phase II evaluation (Cinquino et al. 1995). However, the units excavated in the north-central section of the site revealed a denser artifact deposit than was expected.

There was still time remaining in the field schedule, so, in consultation with the USACE, it was decided to continue excavating units, concentrating in the north-central portion of the site (Figures 23 and 24). Eleven additional 1-x-1-m units were excavated during the remainder of the originally scheduled field season. A small block was excavated in connection with EU 1. Further, EUs 15 and 16 were excavated to evaluate the spatial extent of the deposit (Figure 24). EU 15 produced approximately 225 potsherds, in an area originally thought to be near the edge or outside of the site. A series of shovel tests was excavated on a 10-m interval to the north of EU 15 (Figures 25 and 26). Shovel Test A5, located approximately 60 m north of EU 15, produced two sherds. The remaining shovel tests were sterile. EU 16, located at the extreme north end of the project area, produced 27 sherds.

On completion of 21 1-x-1-m excavation units the historic alluvium was mechanically removed from a large block area (approximately 420 m²) just south of the dense artifact deposit. If the dense artifact deposit represented a refuse midden, the expectation was that house remains or other related features would be located in an adjacent low-artifact-density area. Units excavated in and around the block area confirmed that this section of the site was very low in artifact density. As in Site HU-6, soil was removed a few inches at a time, while the field archaeologists shovel-scraped searching for soil anomalies/features. No features were identified in this area. Again, the sandy sediments are heavily leached and any organic material that may have been

Figure 25

Portion of Backhoe Trench 3B Stratigraphic Profile (Site HU-7)

Figure 26
Wooded Area to the North of EU 15 (Site HU-7), Where a Line of Seven Shovel Tests was Excavated (February 10, 2000)

Figure 27
Southwest Portion of Group 3b Block Excavation Area (Site HU-7, March 23, 2000)

Figure 28
Group 7 Block Excavation Area (Site HU-7, March 29, 2000)

present from the prehistoric occupations has disappeared. Fieldwork was completed at this point and artifacts were shipped back to the New South Associates laboratory for processing.

Following initial processing of artifacts and in consultation with the USACE it was agreed that additional fieldwork was necessary for the north-central section of the project area, where the dense artifact deposit was identified. A supplement to the original scope of work was prepared, which included the excavation of 20 additional 1-x-1-m units (Appendix I). Twenty-four 1-x-1-m excavation units were completed during the second round of fieldwork. These units were distributed across four small blocks traversing the north-central portion of the site (Figure 24).

In total, 45 1-x-1-m units were excavated in Site HU-7 during the Phase III investigation (Figures 27 and 28). For analytical purposes these units are grouped by site section and/or content. Seven groups of units were defined. Soil horizons combined with artifact densities were used to define stratigraphic units for each group. Foss observed that in general the soil horizons documented in Site HU-7 are the same as those identified in Site HU-6. Both sites are situated on the same alluvial landform (Figure 3).

All of the groups of units are located in the northern half of the Phase III project area. Units excavated in the southern portion of the project area were culturally sterile and will not be addressed further (EUs 5, 6, and 9). Group 1 consists of two units, EUs 7 and 8, both located in the central portion of the project area. Very few artifacts were recovered from these units (Figure 29). In the north-central section of the site, Group 2 consisted of EUs 3 and 12. In this area, the Bw-horizon is associated with a distinct spike in the frequency of artifacts, from approximately 35 to 55 cm (Figure 29).

A buried A-horizon was identified in Backhoe Trench 3B at approximately 63 cm, which "may represent . . . a few hundred years of stability before additional sediment covered the surface" and "indicates that occupation of the site occurred shortly after this brief period of stability" (Foss: Appendix II). Units excavated in the vicinity of Trench 3B generally display the greatest frequency of artifacts in the Bw-horizon, immediately overlying the buried A-horizon (Stratum 2 of Groups 3a, 3b, and 4; Figures 30-32). EU 15 (Group 5) displayed a similar artifact frequency spike as the Group 2 units, at approximately 35-55 cm (Figure 29). The Group 7 units produced many artifacts within an approximate 20-cm band, from 55-75 cm, corresponding to the BC-horizon (Figure 33).

A deeply buried 2Ab-horizon, containing several large pieces of preserved wood, was identified in Backhoe Trench 4, at approximately 125-130 cm. A sample of the preserved wood produced a radiocarbon date of 890+/-70 BP (cal AD 1005-1275, 2 sigmas; Beta-141675). The two-sigma calibrated date range corresponds to the currently accepted dating of the Santa Elena period (AD 900-1200). This buried A-horizon is positioned well within the current water table and approximately 40-50 cm below the artifact-bearing horizons of nearby excavation units. Given the identification of a stable surface at approximately 125-130 cm, which includes large fragments of preserved wood, we consider the radiocarbon date to be a reliable indicator of the age of the buried surface.

The east coast of Puerto Rico is situated directly in the path of large storms and hurricanes that arrive from the east. Based on historical and recent records available for Puerto Rico there were 20 large storms or hurricanes in the eighteenth century, 26 during the nineteenth century, and 31 during the twentieth century (Miner Solá 2000:28-90). Prior to the eighteenth century, historical documentation is less reliable (Miner Solá 2000:25-28). If we assume, on average, that 25 large storms or hurricanes per century cross much or all of Puerto Rico then approximately 225 of these violent events have affected the island since AD 1100. The majority of these storms enter the island from the east, battering in particular the Humacao region (Miner Solá 2000:45, 49, 52, 57, 68). The deeply buried 2Ab-horizon, located about 50 cm below the sealed Monserrate/Santa Elena archaeological deposit, dates to approximately AD 1100 (see below for a discussion of the ceramic chronology). It is conceivable, and indeed likely, that shortly after burial of the wood, one or more storm events deposited a considerable amount of sand prior to further soil development and human occupation of the site. Preserved wood was also collected at 130 cm from Backhoe Trench 1, although no evidence of a buried A horizon was observed in this trench.

Tables 7-27 present the frequency and weight distributions of the artifacts recovered from Site HU-7 by site section (group). Pottery represents the major portion of the overall assemblage. The stratigraphic distribution graphs depict weights of pottery by unit and group. Groups 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7 produced the most pottery by count and weight across the site. As in Site HU-6, most of the deposit is concentrated to Stratum 2.

Figure 34 depicts the spatial weight distributions of artifacts recovered from the north-central portion of the site. Groups 3a, 3b, and 7 produced considerably more artifacts than elsewhere in the site, suggesting distinct disposal or occupational areas. Relative sherd sizes may be examined for information on disposal and traffic areas within a settlement. Large fragments of pottery concentrated to a section of a site may reflect a primary disposal area. Such disposal areas may take the form of pit features or concentrated midden heaps. On the other hand, small pottery fragments may represent artifacts that were not removed in the waste disposal process during cleaning activities. These lost artifacts quickly become buried, especially in sandy matrices (Baker 1978; Brose 1970:46-49; DeBoer and Lathrap 1979:129; McPherron 1967:254-255; Stahl and Zeidler 1990). Further, they are more likely to become increasingly comminuted as a result of daily foot traffic, compared to artifacts that were deposited in recognized disposal areas. Of course, there will be a certain amount of mixing of large and small artifacts all over a site. It is unlikely that village occupants performed meticulous size-sorting exercises when disposing of their trash. Nonetheless, examining relative artifact sizes across a site provides insight into how space was partitioned within a village.

Figure 29

Stratigraphic weight distributions of prehistoric pottery for Groups 1, 2, 5, and 6 excavation units in Site HU-7

Figure 30

Stratigraphic weight distributions of prehistoric pottery for Group 3a excavation units in Site HU-7.

Figure 31
Stratigraphic weight distributions of prehistoric pottery for Group 3b excavation units in Site HU-7

Figure 32
Stratigraphic weight distributions of prehistoric pottery for Group 4 excavation units in Site HU-7

Figure 33
Stratigraphic weight distributions of prehistoric pottery for Group 7 excavation units in Site HU-7

Table 7. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Group 1 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Pottery		Shell		Coral		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	11	76.2	20	17.5	9	104.0	40	197.7
2	1	23.4	40	23.1	6	30.4	47	76.9
3	1	4.6	28	31.4			29	36.0
Total	13	104.2	88	72.0	15	134.4	116	310.6

Table 8. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Rimsherds Recovered from Group 1 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Deep and Convex Rims		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)
1					1	8.7					1	8.7
2												
3												
Total					1	8.7					1	8.7

Table 9. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases and Body Sherds Recovered from Group 1 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds and Bases		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1			10	67.5	10	67.5	11	76.2
2			1	23.4	1	23.4	1	23.4
3			1	4.6	1	4.6	1	4.6
Total			12	95.5	12	95.5	13	104.2

Table 10. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Group 2 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Pottery		Shell		Coral		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	34	273.4					34	273.4
2	51	858.8					51	858.8
3	10	250.4	35	26.5	18	33.0	63	309.9
Total	95	1,382.6	35	26.5	18	33.0	148	1,442.1

Table 11. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Rimsherds and Griddle Fragments Recovered from Group 2 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Griddle Fragments		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)
1	1	4.5					1	20.5	1	15.4	3	40.4
2	1	36.4							1	16.1	2	52.5
3												
Total	2	40.9					1	20.5	2	31.5	5	72.4

Table 12. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases, Body Sherds, and Griddle Fragments Recovered from Group 2 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds, Bases, and Griddle Fragments		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	1	32.0	30	201.0	31	233.0	34	273.4
2	1	167.6	48	638.7	49	806.3	51	858.8
3	1	66.0	9	184.4	10	250.4	10	250.4
Total	3	265.6	87	1,024.1	90	1,289.7	95	1,382.6

Table 13. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Group 3 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Pottery		Bone		Shell		Coral		Charcoal		Total	
	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)	Count	Weight (g)
1	107	761.6	4	<1.0	1	.5			2	.5	114	762.6
2	786	11,359.5			3	1.5					789	11,361.0
3	30	423.4			2	.3	3	6.3			35	430.0
Total	923	12,544.5	4	<1.0	6	2.3	3	6.3	2	.5	938	12,553.6

Table 14. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Pottery Recovered from Group 3 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Deep and Convex Rims		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	1	9.2			5	62.6			1	1.8	7	73.6
2	24	483.6	3	173.9	29	1,347.0	26	994.2	15	62.8	97	3,061.5
3	1	71.3			1	11.0	1	5.2	2	8.0	5	95.5
Total	26	564.1	3	173.9	35	1,420.6	27	999.4	18	72.6	109	3,230.6

Table 15. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases and Body Sherds Recovered from Group 3 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds and Bases		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	2	44.7	98	643.3	100	688.0	107	761.6
2	26	1,816.0	663	6,482.0	689	8,298.0	786	11,359.5
3	3	164.6	23	163.3	26	327.9	30	423.4
Total	31	2,025.3	784	7,288.6	815	9,313.9	923	12,544.5

Table 16. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Group 4 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Pottery		Shell		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	118	816.0			118	816.0
2	197	1,787.3			197	1,787.0
3	18	153.0	3	1.7	21	154.7
Total	333	2,756.3	3	1.7	336	2,758.0

Table 17. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Rimsherds Recovered from Group 4 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Deep and Convex Rims		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	2	34.5			4	25.3	1	63.9	2	4.6	9	128.3
2	2	93.3			3	75.7	7	110.2	1	<1.0	13	279.6
3												
Total	4	127.8			7	101.0	8	174.1	3	5.0	22	407.9

Table 18. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases and Body Sherds Recovered from Group 4 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds and Bases		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1			109	687.7	109	687.7	118	816.0
2	4	150.1	180	1,358.0	184	1,508.1	197	1,787.3
3	2	48.7	16	104.3	18	153.0	18	153.0
Total	6	198.8	305	2,150.0	311	2,348.8	333	2,756.3

Table 19. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Group 5 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Pottery		Shell		Coral		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	142	773.6					142	773.6
2	229	1,583.5	105	40.2			334	1,623.0
3	44	280.9	56	69.4	1	.6	101	350.9
Total	415	2,638.0	161	109.6	1	.6	577	2,747.5

Table 20. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Pottery Recovered from Group 5 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Deep and Convex Rims		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1			1	6.7	2	83.2	4	45.3	2	6.8	9	142.0
2					4	69.2	6	94.1	1	17.4	11	180.7
3					1	21.7					1	21.7
Total			1	6.7	7	174.1	10	139.4	3	24.2	21	344.4

Table 21. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases and Body Sherds Recovered from Group 5 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds and Bases		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1			133	631.6	133	631.6	142	773.6
2	6	205.8	212	1,197.0	218	1,402.8	229	1,583.5
3	1	19.3	42	239.9	43	259.2	44	280.9
Total	7	225.1	387	2,068.5	394	2,293.6	415	2,638.0

Table 22. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Group 6 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Pottery		Bone		Coral		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	12	26.0	1	18.7	2	13.1	15	57.8
2	15	75.2			5	34.6	20	109.8
3	4	25.9					4	25.9
Total	31	127.1	1	18.7	7	47.7	39	193.5

Table 23. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Rimsherds Recovered from Group 6 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Deep and Convex Rims		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1												
2	1	5.4					1	13.2			2	18.6
3												
Total	1	5.4					1	13.2			2	18.6

Table 24. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases and Body Sherds Recovered from Group 6 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds and Bases		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1					12	26.0	12	26.0
2			13	56.6			15	75.2
3			4	25.9			4	25.9
Total			17	82.5	12	26.0	31	127.1

Table 25. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Artifacts Recovered from Group 7 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Pottery		Shell		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	175	1,095.7			175	1,095.7
2	975	11,462.0			975	11,462.0
3	30	247.6	1	2.0	31	249.6
Total	1,180	12,805.3	1	2.0	1,181	12,807.3

Table 26. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Pottery Recovered from Group 7 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Concave Rims		Shallow and Convex Rims		Restricted Rims		Deep and Convex Rims		Unidentifiable Rims		Total	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	2	23.2			7	80.0	2	18.8	7	38.8	18	160.8
2	25	727.1	2	16.0	28	904.2	15	338.2	10	122.0	80	2,107.5
3	2	49.7	1	8.7			1	34.4			4	92.8
Total	29	800.0	3	24.7	35	984.2	18	391.4	17	160.8	102	2,361.1

Table 27. Frequency and Weight Distributions of Ceramic Bases and Body Sherds Recovered from Group 7 Excavation Units, Site HU-7.

Stratum	Flat Bases		Body Sherds		Total Body Sherds and Bases		Total Pottery	
	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)	Count	Weight(g)
1	1	35.7	156	899.2	157	934.9	175	1,095.7
2	26	1,100.00	869	8,255.0	895	9,355.0	975	11,462.0
3			26	154.8	26	154.8	30	247.6
Total	27	1,135.7	1,051	9,309.0	1,078	10,444.7	1,180	12,805.3

Figure 34
Spatial Weight Distributions of Pottery Recovered
from the North-Central Portion of Site HU-7

The groups shown in Figure 34 were investigated in terms of sherd count/weight ratios. Large values reflect, on average, small sherds for a group. Likewise, small values indicate, on average, big sherds. Groups 3 and 7 produced the smallest ceramic count/weight ratios (.074 and .092, respectively), indicating the presence of more large sherds than elsewhere (Figure 34). These were followed by Groups 2, 4, and 5 (.103, .121, and .157, respectively). Based on these data, Groups 3 and 7 likely represent primary disposal areas. Alternatively, the areas could reflect quickly abandoned and never-returned-to houses or ancillary structures. The absence of organic remains and discernible soil features like postmolds, pits, and hearths is most likely a product of intense leaching in the sandy sediments. Groups 2, 4, and 5 represent areas that had been subjected to factors producing, on average, small sherds. The scenario that emerges from the overall spatial arrangement of the five groups and the associated sherd count/weight ratios is one of a residential compound, with one or, at most, two households, which includes a small plaza, areas of foot traffic, and a distinct disposal area(s).

Ethnographically documented household communities located in lowland South America provide insights into prehistoric settlement organization. Households have been observed to consist of either a single nuclear family residing in its own house or several related nuclear families that are spatially clustered, thus forming a "domestic compound" (Butt 1970; Meggers 1971; Mentore 1983-1984; Roe and Siegel 1982; Siegel 1990; Siegel and Roe 1986; Urbina 1983-1984:185; Yde 1965). In some groups, extended families reside in a single large communal house (e.g., Crocker 1985; Gregor 1977; Jackson 1983; Nimuendajú 1946; Seeger 1981; Wilbert 1981; Yde 1965). Households function as the adaptive units in the maintenance and reproduction of social and economic relations. Frequently, several related nuclear families cooperate in a number of activities, constituting a corporate group in terms of production and labor and social relations. Multi-household villages typically are divided into house compounds that consist of houses, work sheds, kitchens, storage racks, etc. House compounds are situated in relation to each other, around and within the context of an open plaza. Plazas are kept free of weeds and are continually swept clear of debris, in a centrifugal fashion, eventually resulting in a doughnut-shaped midden (DeBoer and Lathrap 1979:128). This midden is another feature of a compound, and is composed of the organic and inorganic refuse swept from the plaza.

In small one- or two-household villages, the plaza consists of the cleared open space, within which structures are located and activities are performed. In the Shipibo context (upper Amazon), the on-the-ground correlate of a household has been defined as "a cleared plaza which is kept meticulously free of vegetation and which includes a minimum of two structures, a house and a kitchen" (DeBoer and Lathrap 1979:128).

Archaeological investigations conducted in a recently abandoned single-family Shipibo house compound revealed four distinct artifact clusters corresponding to what archaeologists refer to as middens (Siegel and Roe 1986:Figure 5). These middens represent the cumulative refuse of activities performed in discrete locations within the house compound.

Although postmolds and other features were not recovered from Site HU-7, the contents, locations, and sizes of the intact midden deposits indicate a one- or two-

household compound. Compositionally, the middens represented by excavation Groups 3a, 3b, and 7 are very similar. Stylistically, pottery collected from the middens date to the transition between the Monserrate and Santa Elena complexes, suggesting that the deposits formed more or less simultaneously rather than serially, an observation supported by the stratigraphy.

Contrary to Site HU-6, many of the sherds in Site HU-7 were large, and, in some cases, sherds could be re-fitted to form large portions of vessels (Figures 35-67). In addition to plotting sherd frequencies, vessels were tabulated based on unique rims. Many of the rims could not be assigned to specific vessels even though vessel form could be determined.

In total, 2,990 sherds (32,358.0 g) were excavated (Appendix IV). Of these, 261 are rims. After all artifacts had been labeled and cross-mends glued together the assemblage was laid out on tables and unique vessel numbers assigned where possible. Twenty-three distinct vessels were identified across five classes of vessels (Table 28).

Vessel classes were defined on the basis of profile views: concave, shallow and convex, deep and convex, restricted, and navicular (boat-shaped). Restricted bowls dominate the vessel assemblage ($n=8$), followed by concave ($n=7$), deep and convex ($n=5$), navicular ($n=2$), and shallow and convex ($n=1$) (Figure 68). Vessel morphology relates to how the vessel was used and access to the contents. In some assemblages vessel morphology also relates to stylistic or decorative parameters. For instance, in Saladoid series pottery, compound vessel types with multiple carination points provide one or more fields for painted and/or incised design layouts. Post-Saladoid assemblages do not exhibit the same degree of complexity in vessel morphology (e.g., Roe 1989).

In his analysis of the Site PO-21 ceramic assemblage Espenshade (2000) identified 48 vessels spanning 10 vessel form classes. The site, located in the Cerrillos Valley on the south coast of Puerto Rico, was interpreted to be a small Early Ostionoid occupation. Combining experimental, ethnographic, and ethnohistoric data Espenshade concluded that one to six families could easily have produced the PO-21 assemblage over a 3.5 to 21 year span, assuming year-round occupation of the village (Espenshade 2000:18).

In some respects, Site HU-7 is similar to Site PO-21. Both are small Ostionoid occupations, although Site HU-7 is located on the coast and Site PO-21 is positioned in the foothill zone of southern Puerto Rico. According to Espenshade (2000), Site PO-21 represents a single short occupation during the Early Ostionoid (Monserrate) period.

Figure 35
Plan View of Deep and Convex Bowl with Vertically Incised Loop Handle
(Vessel 1, EU 18, Level 6, Site HU-7)

Figure 36
Profile of Vessel 1

Figure 37
Profile of Vessel 1

Figure 38
Oblique View of Vessel 1

Figure 39
Profile of Vessel 1

Figure 40
Detail of Vessel 1

Figure 41
Deep and Convex Vessel with Flat Dimpled Base
(Vessel 2, EU 40, Levels 5 and 6, Site HU-7)

Figure 42
Restricted Bowl with Soft Carina (Vessel 4, EU 45, Level 4, Site HU-7)

Figure 43
Deep and Convex Bowl with Internally Thickened Rim
(Vessel 5, EU 28, Levels 1 and 2, Site HU-7)

Figure 44
Concave Bowl (Vessel 7, EU 30, Level 5, Site HU-7)

Figure 45
Deep and Convex Bowl with Squared Rim and Sharp Carina
(Vessel 9, Backhoe Trench 3A/3B, Site HU-7)

Figure 46
Restricted Bowl (Vessel 10, EU 15, Level 2, Site HU-7)

Figure 47
Restricted Bowl (Vessel 11, EU 12, Level 8, Site HU-7)

Figure 48
Lip Coil of Restricted Bowl (Vessel 12, EU 15, Level 8, Site HU-7)

Figure 49

Concave Bowl (Vessel 13, EU 2, Levels 6 and 7, Site HU-7)

Figure 50
Restricted Bowl with Appliqué Vertical Strips on Upper Shoulder/Rim
(Vessel 14, EU14, Levels 6 and 7, Site HU-7)

Figure 51
Restricted Bowl with Appliqué Button on Upper Shoulder
(Vessel 15, EU 20, Level 6, Site HU-7)

Figure 52
Deep and Convex Bowl (Vessel 16, EU 14, Level 6, Site HU-7)

Figure 53
Restricted Bowl (Vessel 17, EU 44, Level 6, Site HU-7)

Figure 54
Navicular Bowl with Red Paint on Lip of Rim
(Vessel 18, EU 45, Level 4, Site HU-7)

Figure 55
Navicular Bowl (Vessel 19, EU 15, Level 5, Site HU-7)

Figure 56
Concave Bowl with Red Paint on Lip of Rim
(Vessel 20, EU 45, Level 4, Site HU-7)

Figure 57
Restricted Bowl (Vessel 22, EU 32, Level 6, Site HU-7)

Top View

Side View

Figure 58
Concave Bowl (Backhoe Trench 3A/3B, Site HU-7)

Figure 59
Concave Bowl (Backhoe Trench 3A/3B, Site HU-7)

Figure 60
Dimpled Base (EU 14, Level 8, Site HU-7)

Figure 61
Flat Base (EU 3, Level 4, Site HU-7)

Figure 62
Flat Base (EU 23, Level 1 and EU 37, Level 2, Site HU-7)

Figure 63
Flat Base (EU 30, Level 5, Site HU-7)

Figure 64
Flat Base (EU 44, Level 4 and EU 40, Level 7, Site HU-7)

Figure 65
Cross-mended Body Sherds (EU 32, Level 5, Site HU-7)

Figure 66
Cross-mended Body Sherds (EU 30, Level 4 and EU32, Level 5, Site HU-7)

Figure 67
Cross-mended Handle Fragments (EU 44, Level 1 and EU 45, Level 1, Site HU-7)

Interior View

Exterior View

Table 28. Identified Ceramic Vessels Recovered from Site HU-7.

Vessel No.	Provenience	Group No.	Vessel Class	Figure No.
1	EU 18, Level 6. Bag nos. 215, 216, 216.	3a	Deep and convex. Vessel size at orifice: 27.6 cm x approx. 33 cm. Weight: 1,795.3 g. Monserrate/Santa Elena style. Handle present at one end.	35-40
2	EU 40, Levels 5 and 6, EU 41, Level 6. Bag nos. 1091, 1099, 1100.	7	Deep and convex. Vessel diameter: 28 cm. Weight: 509.4 g.	41
3	Trench 3A. Bag 102.		Concave bowl with band of red paint on exterior upper shoulder/rim.	
4	EU 45, Level 4. Bag nos. 1112, 1113.	7	Small restricted bowl.	42
5	EU 28, Levels 1 and 2. Bag nos. 1004, 1005.	5	Deep and convex vessel with internally thickened rim.	43
6	EU 28, Level 2. Bag no. 1105.	5	Concave.	
7	EU 30, Level 5. Bag no. 1072.	7	Concave.	44
8	EU 35, Level 2. Bag no. 1059.	4	Concave.	
9	Trench 3A/3B. Bag no. 98.		Deep and convex with squared rim and sharp carina.	45
10	EU 15, Level 2. Bag no. 190.	5	Restricted bowl. Orifice diameter approx. 30 cm.	46
11	EU 12, Level 1. Bag no. 162.	2	Small restricted bowl. Orifice diameter approx. 14 cm.	47
12	EU 15, Level 8. Bag no. 196.	5	Restricted bowl with lip coil.	48
13	EU 2, Levels 6 and 7. Bag no. 117.	3a	Concave bowl with externally thickened rim. Diameter: 27 cm.	49
14	EU 14, Levels 6 and 7. Bag nos. 185 and 186.	3a	Restricted bowl with appliqué vertical strips on upper shoulder/rim; Sanla Elena. Diameter: 29 cm.	50
15	EU 20, Level 6. Bag no. 223.	6	Restricted bowl with sharp carina and appliqué button on upper shoulder.	51
16	EU 14, Level 6. Bag no. 185.	3a	Deep and convex pot with sharp carina.	52
17	EU 44, Level 6. Bag no. 1107.	3a	Restricted bowl with externally thickened rim and sharp carina.	53
18	EU 45, Level 4. Bag no. 1113.	3a	Boat-shaped vessel with red paint on lip of rim. Monserrate.	54
19	EU 15, Level 5. Bag 193.	5	Boat-shaped vessel. Monserrate.	55
20	EU 45, Level 4. Bag no. 1113.	3a	Concave bowl.	56
21	Trench 3a. Bag no. 102.		Concave bowl with band of red paint along upper body and rim.	
22	EU 32, Level 6. Bag no. 1080.	7	Restricted bowl.	57
23	EU 11, Level 6. Bag no. 158.	3a	Shallow and convex bowl with red paint along lip of rim.	

Figure 68
Household Vessel Assemblage from North-central Portion of Site HU-7

Site HU-7 contains a sizable Santa Elena occupation and a smaller Monserrate occupation. The Santa Elena and Monserrate occupations are both positioned within Stratum 2 in Site HU-7. Within this stratum there is no discernible cultural stratigraphy enabling the Santa Elena and Monserrate assemblages to be separated. At best, the Site HU-7 deposit represents a transitional occupation between the Monserrate and Santa Elena periods. Others have noted the clinal variation in decorative and morphological attributes of vessels between the Cuevas and Monserrate periods (e.g., Roe et al. 1990). In fact, Vescelius refers to Monserrate as an "epi-Saladoid" transitional phase or complex (Vescelius and Walker 1983:25; see also Roe et al. 1990:345). Without elaborating, Ramos Vélez and Meléndez Maíz (1991:37) state that "the late Saladoid Ceramics Style on eastern Puerto Rico (Monserrate) is hardly distinguishable from early Santa Elena Style."

Typical Santa Elena pottery displays less of a "continuum of modes" from the previous Monserrate style, compared to the Cuevas-Monserrate transition. On the other hand, there is no evidence on Puerto Rico or elsewhere for population displacement or other social upheaval between the Early and Middle Ostionoid periods. During any time of social or cultural transition we would expect some degree of material cultural continuity, expressed either in the production of specific objects (pots in this case) or in distinct components of an overall assemblage, or both. The co-occurrence of some Monserrate with more Santa Elena ceramics may reflect a period of social transition at approximately AD 900.

In the Site HU-7 ceramic assemblage there is evidence for continuity of some modes between Monserrate and Santa Elena. Figures 35-40, 69 and 70 depict open loop handles rising over the vessel rims (Monserrate style) combined with thick vertical incisions on the handles (Santa Elena style). Other elements of the assemblage include "typical" Monserrate (Figures 53-55 and 70-72) and Santa Elena (Figures 48 and 50) ceramics. Robinson et al. (1985:F24) suggested that "outside of specific centers of regional ceramic tradition where a single stylistic concept was maintained, a variety of styles was adopted and assimilated by peoples in outlying settlements. Thus the variety represented in a particular assemblage would actually be a single, localized, stylistic unit characterized by a mixture of specific stylistic traits." Oliver (1992:51) too observed that "local groups adapted traits from various styles differently, and may utilize a number of supposedly diagnostic attributes of different styles at a single point in time."

Open loop handles are commonly found in Ostionoid-period deposits. These handles are variously plain, burnished, or painted red. Some open loop handles appear with thick vertical incisions on the exteriors of the handles (e.g., Vacía Talega site [Robinson et al. 1985:Figure 26]; Site LO-9 [Hayward and Cinquino 1999:Figure 8]; Site YO-1 [Walker and Walker 1983:28, Plate 12]; Site HU-7 [this report: Figures 35-40, 68 and 69].) Robinson et al. (1985:F20-F21) offer a nuanced discussion tracking the "design concepts" of handles with vertical incisions on the exteriors. In doing so, they demonstrate the continuum of modes from the Monserrate to Santa Elena complexes in the context of the very distinctive feature of Ostionoid pottery: handles. Robinson et al. (1985) suggest that centers and peripheries of ceramic traditions were critical in

¹ Early developments in the institutionalization of social inequality were occurring at this time, as evidenced by the presumed gradual increase in the use of ball courts on the island (Siegel 1999).

Figure 69
Loop Handle with Thick Vertical Incisions on the Handle Exterior
(EU 13, Level 6, Site HU-7)

Figure 70
Loop Handle with Thick Vertical Incisions on the Handle Exterior
(Backhoe Trench 3B, Site HU-7)

Figure 71
Red-on-buff Painted Body Sherds (Backhoe Trench 3A/3B, Site HU-7)

Figure 72
Painted Interior Base Sherd (EU 12, Level 3, Site HU-7)

Figure 73
Painted Body Sherd (Backhoe Trench 3B, Site HU-7)

determining whether there was mixing of design elements or not. Alternatively, within the overall design traditions, with the attendant rules that structure the traditions, potters may combine elements or modes of decoration and vessel form, some of which may presage developments to come. Observe the sequence: plain, burnished, or painted open loop handle to open loop handle with vertical incisions to squashed vestigial handle with vertical incisions to vertical incisions along a short stretch of vessel rim/shoulder (Figure 74). A variant on vertical incisions along the vessel rim is a series of vertical parallel appliqué strips along the vessel rim (Figure 50). This example underscores the importance of considering continuity of modes in West Indian pottery and the difficulty sometimes in rigidly pigeon-holing individual specimens to a particular style or complex.

Within the area of potential effect, Site HU-7 is small, approximately 1,500 m² (16,181 sq. ft.), or .15 ha (.37 ac.). Based on the horizontal distribution of artifacts the site extends outside of the right-of-way to the north and northeast. Although the density of artifacts diminished at the northern edge of the right-of-way, it is conceivable that the site deposit becomes more dense outside of the right-of-way. Thus, the northern boundary of the site remains unknown.

The densest portion of the site within the right-of-way is limited to an approximate 900-m² area (9,687 sq. ft.) (Figure 34). Within the excavated portion of this area, 23 vessels were identified. In total, 37 m² (4.1% of 900 m²) were excavated within the dense section of the site. If our vessel recovery rate is representative of the assemblage within the 900 m² area then approximately 516 pots should be present. It is not appropriate, however, to simply extrapolate in this manner; within the dense portion of the site some areas were more productive than others. Amazonian house compounds contain distinct midden areas where broken pots, among other classes of refuse, are located. Plazas, footpaths, and house floors are kept relatively clear of refuse.

Interpolating between the excavation areas within the north-central portion of the site, the middens defined by Groups 3a, 3b, and 7 comprise approximately 295 m². This area constitutes approximately 32 percent of the dense portion of the site.² If we assume that most broken vessels will be deposited in the refuse middens then we can use the projected midden areas to estimate the number of pots present.

Based on our vessel recovery rate and the projected midden areas there are approximately 72 pots present in the dense portion of Site HU-7. The dense portion of the site corresponds approximately in size to small or medium ethnographically documented Amazonian house compounds (e.g., DeBoer and Lathrap 1979; Siegel 1990; Siegel and Roe 1986). Using Espenshade's (2000) projection method (9 vessels per household, use-life of 1 year per pot, assume year-round occupation) we derive an approximate 8-year occupational span for the HU-7 "household area."

² Based on ethnographic data, 32 percent of a total house compound area may be reasonable to use as a target figure for the amount of refuse midden space (e.g., DeBoer and Lathrap 1979:Figure 4.6).

Figure 74
Sequence in the Design and Surface Treatment of Handles from the Monserrate to Santa Elena Periods

V. DISCUSSION

Sites HU-6 and HU-7 are small Ostionoid-period villages positioned on the east-central coast of Puerto Rico, from which the large island of Vieques is visible (Figure 75). The sites are located on a stretch of low alluvial coastal plain between the Río Antón Ruíz and the Boca Prieta. This stretch of beach is part of a larger arcuately shaped coastal plain that is delimited by Punta Lima to the north and Punta Santiago to the south. Cayo Santiago is located approximately 1.7 km (1.05 mi.) from the shore fronting the two sites (Figure 76).

The sites are located within 500 m of each other. Both are small with moderately dense archaeological deposits that most likely resulted from small year-round household occupations. In his survey of ten selected coastal river mouths, Walker (1984:63-64) concluded that early ceramic-period sites (Saladoid to "early Elenoid") tend to be located "in coastal settings adjacent to or on Cataño loamy sand," in contrast to later sites ("late Elenoid and Chicoid Series"), which "tend to cluster inland." This general observation is similar to Rouse's conclusion, differing in the timing of the move to the interior: "in Period IIb [Cuevas], the Indians began to penetrate the mountainous interior, settling in the larger river valleys which were the most easily accessible" (Rouse 1952b:367).

Rouse observed long ago that the Vieques Sound Area represented a logical unit of analysis and locus of intense cultural activity, as were passage ways between islands in general (Rouse 1951, 1982:Figure 2). The Vieques Sound Area includes eastern Puerto Rico, Vieques, Culebra, and the Virgin Islands. The degree to which passage areas represent loci of intense cultural activity must be viewed against such factors as sociopolitical organization, trade and exchange, subsistence and settlement patterns, etc. Rouse certainly acknowledges this point in contrasting pre-Columbian vs. historic orientations to sea and land (Rouse 1982:48). Within the prehistoric era, too, passage areas were differentially emphasized through time (see also Rodríguez 1992:4).

In his review of site locations and chronology for eastern Puerto Rico, Rodríguez (1992) defined the Vieques Sound Area to include the eastern two-thirds of Puerto Rico. Following Rouse (1952b), Rodríguez (1992) observed that beginning in Period IIb, settlement locations began to expand into the interior of the island. During Period IIIb (AD 900-1200), according to Rodríguez (1992:13), population levels, site numbers, and occupied habitats increased dramatically. Compared to Period IIa (early Saladoid), and to a lesser extent Period IIb (late Saladoid), post-Saladoid site sizes decreased considerably (Siegel 1995). To what degree did population re-structure, change, or both, is an unresolved question. Current evidence is equivocal for population pressure or resource limitations at any time during the ceramic age. Curet's (1992) survey in the Maunabo Valley, located in southeastern Puerto Rico, indicates population levels well below the local carrying capacity. However, population density was increasing through the post-Saladoid occupations. In his survey of the Loíza Valley, located in northeastern Puerto Rico, Rodríguez (1990) documented dramatically increased numbers of sites and site types during post-Saladoid time, corresponding to the development of ball courts and Taí no chiefdoms. Sociopolitical changes certainly were occurring by Period IIIa

Figure 75
Mouth of the Boca Prieta. Vieques Island is Visible in the Distance (February 8, 2000)

Figure 76
View of Cayo Santiago from Playa Fronting Site HU-7 (February 8, 2000)

(AD 600-900), evidenced by the development of ball courts and ceremonial plazas along the south coast (Siegel 1999:Figure 5).

Sites HU-6 and HU-7 represent small household-based settlements occupied for, perhaps, approximately 10-20 years during the transition between Periods IIIa and IIIb. How do we account for a buried A-horizon in Site HU-7 that dates to cal AD 1005-1275, and which is located approximately 50 cm below a Monserrate/Santa Elena cultural deposit? Given (a) the Monserrate/Santa Elena occupation overlying the buried surface, (b) the good integrity of the buried surface, and (c) the radiocarbon age of the wood that dated the buried surface, we suggest that this A-horizon is positioned within the early portion of the two-sigma date range (ca. AD 1000). If this surface was buried quickly (see discussion above regarding hurricanes), after which the area was occupied by Indians who created the ceramic assemblage, then we would conclude that the transition between the Monserrate and Santa Elena complexes dates to about AD 1000. This pushes the currently accepted transition date (AD 900) up by 100 years. Previously, I had suggested that the Cuevas period should be expanded by 100 years, based on an extensive radiocarbon dating program at Maisabel: AD 400-700 (Siegel 1991c:Note 3). Likewise, perhaps the Monserrate age range should be revised to AD 700-1000. The problem, however, is that the currently accepted chronology is based on uncalibrated radiocarbon dates (Rouse 1982, 1992; Rouse et al. 1985). Until all of the documented radiocarbon dates used to establish the existing chronology have been calibrated, it is difficult to offer firm revisions.

One might suppose, too, that the cultural complexes under discussion, Monserrate and Santa Elena, represent extremely large ranges of time (300 years each), thus invalidating any effort to reconstruct a household occupation that contains samples of both styles. If sufficient charcoal for dating had been available from the HU-7 midden, no finer resolution would have been added to the issue of a "household" than what is currently available. Radiocarbon dates are probability statements for a specified range of time. Calibrated two-sigma date ranges typically represent two hundred to three hundred years of time, an interval not very useful for discussing households or cultural/stylistic transitions.

What we do have in Site HU-7 is a small sealed midden within a relatively thin stratigraphic unit. This midden contains horizontally discrete clusters of artifacts that represent unique disposal processes. Given the dynamic geomorphic setting of the east-central coast, in the direct path of major storms that make landfall on Puerto Rico, a thin, sealed deposit with good internal spatial patterning is a most meaningful archaeological datum. Indeed, it is precisely this context/analytical scale that will allow us to address behaviorally important social institutions, like households, and archaeologically important processes like stylistic shifts.

The presence of other contemporaneous sites in the area in similar settings suggests that a well-developed adaptation at this time centered around the extraction and use of coastal estuarine resources. Despite the absence of faunal remains and features in Sites HU-6 and HU-7, it is hard to imagine a subsistence economy of these people that was not strongly oriented to the mangrove and coastal resources. These sites are situated within the largest remaining mangrove swamp on Puerto Rico. Based

on location, we can reasonably assume that the inhabitants of Sites HU-6 and HU-7 took advantage of the bountiful resources surrounding them.

Given the context of the post-Saladoid political landscape, these small household-based settlements were undoubtedly linked to larger networks of settlements, locally and regionally (Siegel 1991d). By Period IIIb, a site with a small ceremonial plaza was located in Sabana Arriba, approximately 22 km (13.75 mi.) to the northwest of Sites HU-6 and HU-7 (Rodríguez and Rivera 1983). Assuming that ball court/plaza sites served as political or administrative centers, then Sabana Arriba may have included the east-central coast within its jurisdiction during Period IIIb (Siegel 1999:Figure 6). Other undocumented Period IIIb ball court sites may be located closer to Sites HU-6 and HU-7 than Sabana Arriba. Corresponding to the development of site hierarchies and political/ceremonial centers was the institution of tributary relations within and across polities documented ethnohistorically (Alegría 1983; Las Casas 1967; Moscoso 1999; Redmond and Spencer 1994; Wilson 1990). Social and economic relations revolving around tribute may have been established by Period IIIa, associated with the earliest evidence for institutionalized social inequality on Puerto Rico. As such, small household-based camps dating to the post-Saladoid occupations on the island must be viewed as potential resource-extraction places in the primary production of tribute. This is difficult to substantiate without complete settlement data for a polity. The point, however, is that the social, political, and economic context must be considered when attempting to understand the function of any site dating to the post-Saladoid occupations on Puerto Rico.

SURVEY AND EXCAVATION STRATEGY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EASTERN PUERTO RICO

The playas and alluvial plains of the east coast are situated in the direct path of violent storms and the easterly trade winds, resulting in thick surface deposits of historic alluvium and recent sands. Archaeological sites located in this region thus may be sealed beneath thick deposits of historic or recent alluvium.

Suggestions may be offered for future Phase I Identification Surveys and excavations of sites located along the east coast of Puerto Rico. Identifying sites in these contexts may require a systematic sampling program, employing a combination of backhoe trenches and selected 1-x-1-m and/or 50-x-50-cm test pits. Relying exclusively on shovel test pit excavations is liable to miss deeply buried significant resources. A qualified soil scientist should be included in such surveys to identify the potential for buried surfaces that may contain intact archaeological deposits.

Prehistoric sites located on the coastal plain, in sandy sediments, are likely to have been subjected to extreme leaching and the loss of organic residues. Although the organic content of cultural features may be gone in this setting, we recommend that judicious stripping of historic alluvial sediments may be productive in identifying and recovering artifact deposits associated with middens, pits, hearths, etc. In Sites HU-6 and HU-7, the artifact deposits were consistently buried beneath approximately 50-60 cm of historic alluvium and positioned within the Bw-, BC-, and/or 2Ab-horizons.

It is recommended that Phase II Evaluation Surveys or Phase III Data Recoveries of prehistoric sites located in the Playas and Alluvial Plains physiographic region of Puerto Rico be conducted in stages to confidently identify the stratigraphic positioning of the significant resource, taking into consideration topographic and horizontal variability in the archaeological deposits. To this end, backhoe trenches and 1-x-1-m test units should be excavated across the site within the area of potential effect to carefully evaluate the stratigraphic associations of the archaeological deposit. As in the context of Phase I Surveys, this work should be performed in conjunction with a soil scientist.

Household middens associated with such sites are frequently small and spatially discrete. Close-interval probing using a narrow-gauge metal rod may be a reliable and quick method for identifying the presence and areal extent of buried middens within sandy deposits. Areas within a site that are resistant to the probe may be mapped and evaluated using shovel tests and/or 1-x-1-m test units. In this manner, small and large buried midden deposits may be quickly identified, mapped, evaluated and distinguished from natural subsurface anomalies.

If the significant resource is found to be consistently buried beneath a thick layer of historic or recent alluvium, then the next stage of fieldwork may be to carefully strip the historic alluvium using heavy equipment. It is recommended too that in the context of these sandy sediments heavy equipment be directed to avoid driving over the area of stripping because of the extreme stress-loads that would otherwise impact the archaeological deposit. A trackhoe with a telescoping arm may be the machine to use depending on the size of the area to be stripped. It is further recommended that the bucket used to remove the overburden be fitted with a smooth plate, thus providing maximum visibility of sediments and archaeological materials. Following stripping of the overburden, hand excavations may proceed using an agreed-upon sampling design. Employing a staged approach to Phase II Evaluations and Phase III Data Recoveries should maximize the information-return for a given amount of field time.

CONCLUSIONS

Phase III data recoveries conducted at Sites HU-6 and HU-7 documented small occupations located along the east coast of Puerto Rico dating primarily to the transition between the Monserrate and Santa Elena periods. Based on current understanding of these time periods the sites were occupied at approximately AD 900, although this may need to be revised to AD 1000, especially given the calibrated age range of the dated wood sample collected from a soil horizon underlying the cultural deposits in Site HU-7. Other contemporaneous sites in the vicinity of Sites HU-6 and HU-7 suggest that a well-developed coastal adaptation was established in the Humacao-Naguabo area by this time (Period IIIb). Except for Site HU-1, very few faunal or botanical remains have been recovered from any of these sites. However, their locations reveal a distinct preference for coastal mangroves and estuaries. Site HU-1, located on Cayo Santiago, produced fish and manatee bones and marine gastropods and bivalves (Rouse 1952b:552).

Ball courts and ceremonial plazas were well-established on Puerto Rico by Period IIIb, and had begun expanding geographically from the south coastal region to the interior mountains and the northeast. A small ceremonial plaza was located in the Sabana Arriba site, approximately 22 km to the northwest of Sites HU-6 and HU-7. It is conceivable that Sites HU-6 and HU-7 were within the jurisdiction of the Sabana Arriba politico-ceremonial center.

The ceramic assemblages recovered from Sites HU-6 and HU-7 indicate small household-based occupations were present for perhaps 10-20 years. It may be that small household compounds, like those represented in Sites HU-6 and HU-7, were important in the primary production/extraction of resources or tribute in the emerging polities documented for the island at this time. This observation can only be substantiated with systematically collected settlement data for a specific polity.

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APPENDIX I
SCOPES OF WORK

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SCOPES OF WORK

SCOPE OF WORK

PROFESSIONAL SERVICES FOR
ARCHEOLOGICAL DATA RECOVERY AT SITES HU-6 AND HU-7,
RIO ANTON RUIZ FLOOD CONTROL PROJECT,
MUNICIPIO DE HUMACAO, PUERTO RICO

1. GENERAL STATEMENT OF SERVICES: The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (Corps), Jacksonville District, proposes to construct a flood control project on the Rio Anton Ruiz, in the Municipio of Humacao, Puerto Rico. Archeological sites HU-6 and HU-7, historic properties eligible for inclusion on the National Register of Historic Places, will be affected by the proposed construction project. These historic properties are of value for their potential contribution to archeological research, and such value will be substantially preserved through the conduct of archeological data recovery under this contract effort.

This work shall be conducted in compliance with the National Historic Preservation Act of 1966 (PL 89-665) as amended and the Archeological and Historic Preservation Act of 1979 (PL 93-291) as amended, and shall be performed by a professional archeologist meeting the qualifications established in the Secretary of the Interior's Standards and Guidelines.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA: The Rio Anton Ruiz Flood Control project is located on the eastern coast of Puerto Rico in an area known as Playa de Humacao (Figure 1). Sites HU-6 and HU-7 are located near the southern bank of Rio Anton Ruiz, approximately 100 meters from PR Highway 3 (Figure 2).

3. PROJECT BACKGROUND AND PREVIOUS WORK. A cultural resources investigation was conducted on portions of the flood control project area in 1990 (Buchner and Childress 1991). The flood control project was subsequently redesigned. Site HU-6 was identified by Corps archeologists within the new project feature lands. Comprehensive cultural resources survey was conducted on the new project feature lands in 1995 (Cinquino et. al. 1997), resulting in the discovery of site HU-7. Cinquino also conducted phase II archeological site testing at sites HU-6 and HU-7. Based on the results of that archeological testing, the Corps determined that sites HU-6 and HU-7 meet the criteria of eligibility for inclusion on the National Register of Historic Places.

4. DESCRIPTION OF SERVICES: The Contractor shall supply the necessary personnel, facilities, supplies, materials, and other equipment required to conduct archeological data recovery at sites HU-6 and HU-7, providing the following specific services:

4.1. Background and Archival Data Examination and Development of a Research Design. The Contractor shall examine all historic background data collected by previous investigators and shall build upon that data to further construct and refine a background history of the project area. Pertinent environmental data which could aid in the interpretation of the sites shall also be collected. Informant interviews with individuals knowledgeable about cultural resources in the area shall be incorporated into the background research. The background research shall culminate in the construction of a written research design that identifies specific research questions that may be addressed through archeological data recovery at the site. The research design should specify what field and analytical techniques will be employed to gather information to address research questions.

4.2. Archeological Excavation. Archeological data recovery excavations shall be carried out at sites HU-6 and HU-7. All work will be conducted using standard archeological methods and fully documented with photographs and drawings. The Contractor shall maintain overall vertical and horizontal control throughout the work. Decisions on the placement of all excavation units shall be made by the Contractor in consultation with the Corps. All excavations units shall be located within the footprint of the flood control project, and shall be placed to maximize the production of archeological data and provide a representative sample of data from the site. Excavation units shall include machine-excavated trenches, hand-excavated 1 by 1 meter squares, and large-scale excavation blocks in which archeological features are identified and hand excavated. Each excavation unit type is discussed below.

4.2.1. Machine-excavated trenches. At each site, the Contractor shall first machine excavate a series of trenches, oriented east and west, and spaced evenly across the portion of the site that will be impacted by construction. Each trench will be approximately 20 meters long, 1 meter wide, and 1 meter deep. In a 2-3 meter long segment of each trench, the Contractor shall extend the depth of the trench to approximately 2 meters. One wall and the floor of each trench shall be cleaned and documented with photographs and drawings. The stratigraphy observed in the trench walls will be documented and used to vertically control additional excavations. A column sample will be taken from each trench wall. Soils excavated from the trenches will not be screened, but will be carefully examined during the excavation, and a representative sample of artifact from each trench will be collected.

4.2.2. Hand-excavated unit squares. These unit will measure 1 by 1 meter square, and shall be excavated to culturally sterile soil.

Vertical control will be maintained by the site's stratigraphy. Standard archeological excavation methods will be employed during these excavations. All features will be excavated separately.

4.2.3. Large-scale block excavation units. Guided by the stratigraphy observed in the trenches, the Contractor shall determine the depth below surface of the plow zone or surface-disturbed soil layer within a large-scale block excavation unit. Cinguino estimated this layer to extend approximately 30 cm below surface in site HU-6. The Contractor shall mechanically remove this plow zone, shovel clean the block excavation unit floor, map all archeological features observed in the floor, and excavate all features using standard archeological methods.

4.2.4. Number of excavation units at site HU-6.

- a. Machine Excavated Trenches: 4
- b. Hand-excavated 1 by 1 meter square units: 15
- c. Large-scale block units: 1 block measuring 20 m by 20 meters

4.2.5. Number of excavation units at site HU-7.

- a. Machine Excavated Trenches: 2
- b. Hand-excavated 1 by 1 meter square units: 10
- c. Large-scale block units: 1 block measuring 10 m by 15 meters

4.3. Executive Summary. Upon completion of the field work, the Contractor shall prepare and submit to the Government an Executive Summary. The summary shall include a general inventory of materials collected during the archival research and field investigation. It shall also assess the applicability of the research design, and make modifications to the research design if appropriate. And it will include a detailed plan and schedule for the data analysis and report preparation phases of the study.

4.5. Data Analysis and Report Preparation. All data will be processed, described, and analyzed using currently acceptable scientific methodology. All cultural materials recovered during the field investigation will be inventoried and cataloged.

The draft report shall contain a narrative of pertinent previous investigations, a description of the project area's culture history and environment, and a description of methods and techniques used in archival research, informant interview, field investigations, and laboratory analysis. This information shall

be integrated with the research design, fieldwork data, results and data analysis to produce a graphically illustrated, scientifically acceptable draft report which conforms to the Secretary of the Interior's Standards and Guidelines.

The report shall be typed or printed with a letter quality printer (dot-matrix printing will not be accepted) on fully white, offset book paper, 12 substance, (government weight, 1000 sheets, 25 x 38), or equal. Page size shall be 8-1/2 by 11 inches, with 1-1/2 inch binder margins and 1 inch side margins. All pages must be consecutively numbered. Drawings and plates will normally not have an image larger than 10 by 16 inches with sufficient margin for binding on the left side.

A complete References Cited section will list all sources and references consulted. The reference format of American Antiquity shall be followed. Spelling shall be in accordance with the U.S. Government Printing Office Style Manual dated March 1984.

The title page must bear an inscription indicating the contract number and the source of funds used to conduct the study. If the report has been authored by someone other than the contract Principal Investigator, the Principal Investigator shall: (1) have the cover and title pages of the report bear the inscription Prepared Under the Supervision of (Name), Principal Investigator; (2) prepare a foreword describing the overall research context of the report, the significance of the work, and any other related background circumstances relating to the manner in which the work was undertaken. The original copy of the final report shall be signed by the Principal Investigator.

An abstract suitable for publication in an abstract journal must be prepared. This shall consist of a brief, quotable summary useful for informing the technically oriented professional public of what the author considers to be the contributions of the investigation to knowledge.

5. SCHEDULE:

- 5.1. Commence work upon receipt of Notice to Proceed.
- 5.2. Field work shall be completed within 45 days after Notice to Proceed.
- 5.3. Five copies of the Executive Summary shall be submitted to the Government within 30 calendar days after completion of field work.

5.4. Five copies of the draft report shall be delivered to the Jacksonville District within 120 calendar days after completion of field work.

5.5. Government reviews of the draft report will be provided to the Contractor within 60 days after receipt of the draft report. Subsequent drafts may be required based on the comments of reviewers at no additional cost to the Government.

5.6. Within 14 days after acceptance of the draft report by Government, the Contractor shall deliver to Jacksonville District:

- One (1) camera ready copy of the final report
- One (1) copy of the report in Microsoft Word.
- Fifty (50) copies of the final report, perfect bound

F. The Contractor shall deliver to the Corps:

- All cultural materials recovered during the investigation
- Originals of records, data, photographs, negatives, and other documents resulting from work conducted under this contract.

6. REFERENCES:

Buchner, Andrew C. and Mitchell R. Childress.

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Contour Interval: 10 Meters

Figure 12: Project Study Areas A and B

Scale 1:20000

4

— = Area Shovel Tested at 20 Meter Intervals

FROM CINQUINO et al 1997

FIGURE 1

Figure 5: Archaeological Site Locations Hu-6 and Hu-7

FROM CINQUINO et. al. 1997

———— = Study Area Boundary

SUPPLEMENTAL SCOPE OF WORK
TO AMEND CONTRACT DACW17-98-D-0021
DELIVERY ORDER NO. 0002

PROFESSIONAL SERVICES FOR
ARCHEOLOGICAL DATA RECOVERY AT SITE HU-7,
RIO ANTON RUIZ FLOOD CONTROL PROJECT,
MUNICIPIO DE HUMACAO, PUERTO RICO

1. DESCRIPTION OF SERVICES: The Contractor shall supply the necessary personnel, facilities, supplies, materials, and other equipment required to conduct additional archeological data recovery at site HU-7. The additional work will be conducted between construction stations 3+00 and 4+00 on the levee corridor of the flood control project, as shown on the enclosed map (Encl. 1). An additional 20 square meters will be hand-excavated in 1 by 1-meter squares. The Contractor in consultation with the Corps shall make decisions on the placement of all excavation units. All work will be conducted using standard archeological methods and fully documented with photographs and drawings. The Contractor shall maintain overall vertical and horizontal control throughout the work. All excavations units shall be located within the footprint of the flood control project. All cultural materials collected during this excavation will be incorporated into the original data recovery collection and will be inventoried, cataloged, processed, described and analyzed following the procedures found in the original Delivery Order No. 2 Scope of Work. The final report will address the entire collection as a single site assemblage.

2. SCHEDULE:

2.1. Commence fieldwork on or before March 20, 2000 and complete fieldwork before March 31, 2000.

2.2. Five copies of the Executive Summary shall be submitted to the Government within 30 calendar days after completion of fieldwork.

2.3. Five copies of the draft report shall be delivered to the Jacksonville District within 180 calendar days after completion of fieldwork. This is an addition of 60 calendar days over the original delivery order schedule.

2.4. Government reviews of the draft report will be provided to the Contractor within 60 days after receipt of the draft report. Subsequent drafts may be required based on the comments of reviewers at no additional cost to the Government.

APPENDIX II
CHARACTERISTICS OF SOILS
OCCURRING AT HU-6 AND
HU-7 IN EASTERN
PUERTO RICO

CHARACTERISTICS OF SOILS OCCURRING AT HU-6 AND HU-7 IN EASTERN PUERTO
RICO

By
John E. Foss
Soils International, Inc.
Knoxville, TN 37933

January 2001

INTRODUCTION

A soils investigation was conducted at two archaeological sites in eastern Puerto Rico near the Rio Anton Ruiz. The soils investigation consisted of describing a number of backhoe trenches and archaeological excavations at the two study sites. Eight soil profiles were described at HU-6 and four at HU-7. As a result of the high water table at the sites, it was difficult to examine profiles below 1 meter, although attempts were made to describe some of the soils to depths below 1 meter during excavation with the backhoe. The water table ranged from 52 to 100 cm at the two sites during January 2000.

Soils at the sites were very sandy and according to the general geologic maps the sediments were derived from beach and dune deposits and alluvium. The topography was nearly level with some low ridges running parallel to the beach line; these could be reworked alluvium or dune deposits. Soils were previously mapped with the Aguadilla series; these soils are deep, excessively well drained, and with rapid permeability (Boccheciamp, 1977).

The objectives of the soils investigation were to (1) describe the major soils at the two sites and (2) develop the Holocene history of the site based on pedologic characteristics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 provides the profile descriptions of the soils described at archeological sites HU-6 and HU-7 near the Rio Anton Ruiz. As noted in the descriptions, most of the soils at HU-6 were sand or loamy sand in texture and had minimal pedologic development, i.e. little profile development except an A horizon and a weakly developed Bw with some iron coatings on sand grains and a BC or transitional horizon. Figures 1-3 show some typical soil profiles from the two sites. As noted in the figures, the darker-colored surface horizon is readily visible, but the Bw horizons can be detected by the slightly reddish color associated with some iron translocation into the subsoil. Because of the coarse-textured nature of the soils and lack of development, the B horizons did not qualify as cambic

The C horizon or relatively unweathered parent material occurred at 50 to 86 cm depending on elevation and depth of the water table. The upper portion of the C horizon was generally dark grayish brown to brown color (10YR 4/2, 5/3), but at greater depths the color changed to gray and light brownish gray (2.5Y 6/1-6/2) and the sands were calcareous. Figure 3 shows the lighter-colored, calcareous sands at >50 cm. Thus, it appears that the upper 50 to 80 cm of sands have been leached of their carbonates during the weathering process of many of the soils. The depth of leaching of carbonates is related to elevation and depth of water table; for example, carbonates were leached to >130 cm in Trench 5 which had a higher elevation than the surrounding soil landscape.

Although the soils were mapped with the Aguadilla series, most of the soils described would not fit into the central concept of this series. The soils were not well drained for the most part and calcareous sands were encountered at <100 cm. The soil in the study area was somewhat poorly drained, had calcareous sands within 100 cm, and had a very weakly developed Bw horizon (some translocation of Fe). In depth to carbonates, the soils of the two study areas are similar to the Espinal series, but the poor drainage characteristics of the soils on the sites are not compatible with the Espinal series.

The common characteristic of all soils described at HU-6 was the mottling or redoximorphic pattern resulting from the high water table and fluctuation of the zone of saturation throughout the year. The mottling occurred at very shallow depths in these soils, generally within 20 to 40 cm from the surface. This indicates water levels occur at this depth during parts of the year. The Cg or gleyed colors indicate water levels at this zone during long periods of the year, perhaps 6 months or more.

The soils at site HU-7 were similar to HU-6, except for a pronounced poorly drained area in the southeastern corner of HU-7. Trench 1 at HU-7 was described in this poorly drained area; the C horizon was stratified in this profile. At approximately 130 cm, several pieces of wood were noted in the profile. Trench 4 also contained wood at approximately the same depth. Trench 3B, with numerous artifacts, had a buried surface (2Ab) at the 63-70 cm depth. The lack of a weathered subsoil below the buried surface indicates a short period of stability to form the A horizon or accumulation of organic matter. This may represent only a few hundred years of stability before additional sediment covered the surface. This also indicates that occupation of the site occurred shortly after this brief period of stability. Thus, the sequence of events may be interpreted as follows (based on pedology):

- Landscape emergence from the sea---may be the result of both deposition of sediments and uplift
- Stabilization of landscape with vegetation becoming established
- Occupation of site
- Deposition of additional sediments
- Stabilization of surface and soil weathering processes takes place, i.e. organic matter accumulation, leaching of carbonates, translocation of iron

Pedologic development has been impeded at these sites because of the high water table and the recent age of sediments. Soil development, however, has included the following processes:

1. Organic matter accumulation in the surface forming an A or Ap horizon
2. Leaching of carbonates in surface horizons
3. Translocation of iron from surface horizons to Bw horizon
4. Some minimal development of platy or blocky soil structure
5. Development of drainage mottling (or redoximorphic features) resulting from seasonal water table fluctuations or gley (graying) from complete water saturation for long periods of time (6 months or more)

Table 1 Profile descriptions of soils occurring at archaeological sites Hu-6 and Hu-7 in Puerto Rico

Horizon	Depth Cm	Color	Mottles	Texture	Structure	Consistence	Boundary
Site HU-6							
Trench 1							
Ap	0-30	10YR 3/3	None	ls	1 mpl	vfr	as
Bw	30-47	10YR 4/3,4/2	None	ls	1 mpl	vfr	gs
BC	47-64	10YR 5/3-5/2	m2d 10YR 5/8	s	1 mpl,0sg	vfr	gs
Cg1	64-90	10YR 5/2-5/3	m2d 10YR 5/8	s	0sg	lo	-
Cg2	90-120	10YR 5/2-5/3	m2d 10YR 5/8	calc. s	0sg	lo	-
Cg3	120-150	2.5Y 5/1, 5Y 4/1		calc. s	0sg	lo	-
Notes: Described on N end of trench; many roots in upper 50 cm, few below; whole shell retrieved at 120-150 cm; poorly drained; water table at 60 cm; described on 1/13/00							
Trench 2							
Ap	0-28	10YR 3/3	None	s	1 mpl, 1 mabk	vfr	cs
Bw	28-47	10YR 4/2	f1d 10YR 5/6	s	1 mpl	vfr	gs
BC	47-65	10YR 4/2,4/3	c1f 10YR 4/6	s	0sg	lo	gs
Cg	65-100	10YR 5/2-5/3	c2d 10YR 5/6	s	0sg	lo	-
Notes: Poorly drained; water table 53 cm; leached sands; described on 1/13/00							
Trench 3							
Ap	0-18	10YR 3/3	None	s	1 mpl	vfr	as
Bw	18-40	10YR 5/3,4/3	None	s	0sg	lo	cs
BC	40-51	10YR 5/3	m2d 7.5YR 5/8	s	0sg	lo	cs
Cg1	51-92	2.5Y 6/2	m2d 10YR 5/8	calc. s	0sg	lo	-
Cg2	92-150	2.5Y 6/1,6/2	None	calc. s	0sg	lo	-
Notes: Poorly drained; water table at 80 cm (south end) and 56 cm on north end; few Fe coatings on sand grains in Bw; some 2mpr in BC horizon; described on 1/13/00							
Trench 4 (South face)							
Ap	0-33	10YR 3/3	None	ls	1 mpl	vfr	as
C1	33-42	10YR 5/3, 3/3	m2d 10YR 5/8	ls	1 mpl	vfr	as
2Ab	42-52	10YR 4/3	m2d 10YR 3/6	ls	1 mpl	vfr	as
2Bwb	52-80	10YR 5/3	m2d 10YR 5/8	ls	0sg	lo	gs
2Cg	80-94	2.5Y 6/1,6/2	None	calc. s	0sg	lo	-
Notes: South end of trench (2 m from south end); adjacent to unit 3, N124, E30; poorly drained; water table at 72 cm; 70 to 80 cm grading into calcareous sands; described on 1/14/00							

Trench 4 (East face)

Ap	0-29	10YR 3/3	None	ls	1msbk	vfr	cs
AB	29-44	10YR 4/3,3/3	flf 10YR 5/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	cs
Bw	44-66	10YR 5/3,5/4	m2d 10YR 5/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	gs
C	66-80	10YR 5/2	m2d 10YR 5/6	s	0sg	lo	gs
Cg	80-95	2.5Y 5/2	f2d 10YR 5/6	calc. s	0sg	lo	-

Notes: This profile is more typical for trench 4, poorly drained; water table at 66 cm; many roots in Ap, common in AB, few below Bw, none below; described on 1/14/00

EU3

A	0-10	10YR 3/3	None	ls	1mpl	vfr	cs
BA	10-24	10YR 4/2,4/3	m2d 10YR 5/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	as
Bw	24-36	10YR 4/2	m1d 7.5YR 4/8	ls	1msbk	vfr	cs
BC	36-52	10YR 4/2,5/2	m1d 7.5YR 4/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	gs
C	52-65	10YR 4/2,5/2	m1d 7.5YR 4/8	calc. s	0sg	lo	gs
Cg	65-80	10YR 4/2	-	calc. s	0sg	lo	-

Notes: Poorly drained; water table at 50 cm; some dark material at 65-80 cm; increasing coarse sands at 10-24 cm; nearly sandy loam from 24-52 cm; described on 1/14/00

Trench 5 (small trench)

Ap	0-29	10YR 3/3	None	s	1mpl	vfr	cs
AB	29-42	10YR 3/3,4/4	c1d 10YR 4/6	s	0sg	lo	cs
Bw	42-65	10YR 4/4,4/3	c1d 10YR 4/6	s	0sg	lo	gs
BC	65-86	10YR 4/4	m2d 10YR 5/8	s	0sg	lo	gs
C	86-130	10YR 5/3	m2d 10YR 5/8	s	0sg	lo	-

Notes: Leached sands, described on a micro high at the site; west wall described; somewhat poorly drained; water table at 110 cm; medium sands dominate in upper 65 cm, medium to coarse at 65-86, and dominantly coarse sands at 86-130 cm; described on 1/13/00

Test Unit 1, N20, E23

Ap	0-20	10YR 3/2	None	ls	1mpl	vfr	as
Bw1	20-37	10YR 5/4	m1d 10YR 5/8	s	0sg	lo	as
2Bw2	37-50	10YR 4/3,5/3	m1d 10YR 4/6	s	0sg	lo	cs
2C	50-93	10YR 5/3	m2d 10YR 4/6	calc. s	0sg	lo	gs
2Cg	93-105	10YR 6/1-6/2	m2d 10YR 4/6	calc. s	0sg	lo	-

Notes: Many shell fragments in Ap; possible surface at 37-50 cm, but now in position of Bw horizon; just of the crest of a small hill, dune; poorly drained; water table at 84 cm; described 1/14/00

Site HU7

Trench 1

Ap	0-17	10YR 3/2	None	sl	1mpl	vfr	cs
Bw	17-41	10YR 4/3,4/2	m2d 10YR 4/6	ls	1mabk	vfr	cs
Cg1	41-85	10YR 5/1,5/2	m2d	calc. ls	1mpr	vfr	gs
Cg2	85-93	10YR 4/2	-	calc. s	0sg	lo	-

Notes: Wood was retrieved at 130 cm, but no evidence of buried A horizon at this site; stratification noted in C horizon <41 cm, fine stratification with 1 cm thickness; described at south end of trench, south face; some disturbance of surface horizon noted throughout the site; poorly drained; water table at 52 cm; described on 1/14/00

Trench 2

Ap	0-22	10YR 3/3,4/3	None	sl	1mpl	vfr	cs
Bw	22-42	10YR 5/3,5/4 4/3	c2d 10YR 5/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	cs
BC	42-54	10YR 5/3,5/4	m1d 10YR 5/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	cs
C1	54-72	10YR 6/2-6/3	m2d 10YR 4/6	ls	0sg	lo	cs
C2	72-87	10YR 5/3-5/4	m1d 10YR 5/8	ls	0sg	lo	cs
Cg	87-110	10YR 6/2	m3d 10YR 5/8	calc. s	0sg	lo	-

Notes: Trench was on small ridge, linear feature-dune; north face described, 7 m from west end; somewhat poorly drained soil; water table at 100 cm; some cementation of soil in shell layer (87-110 cm); described 1/14/00

Trench 3B

Ap	0-7	10YR 3/2,3/3	None	ls	1mpl, 0sg	vfr	cs
BA	7-22	10YR 5/4,4/4	f2d 10YR 4/8	s	0sg	lo	cs
Bw	22-63	10YR 5/4,4/4	m2d 10YR 5/8	ls	0sg	lo	as
2Ab	63-70	10YR 4/3	m1d 10YR 5/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	cs
		Dark coatings	10YR 3/2				
2C1	70-90	10YR 5/3,5/4	m2d 10YR 5/8	ls	1cpl	vfr	cs
2C2g	90-103	2.5Y 5/1	c2d 10YR 4/4	calc. s	0sg	lo	-

Notes: Northeast face described, 1.4 m from north end of trench; somewhat poorly drained; water table at 98 cm; upland flat on small ridge; described on 1/14/00

Trench 4

Ap	0-21	10YR 3/3	None	ls	1mpl	vfr	as
AB	21-31	10YR 4/3	f1f 10YR 5/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	cs
		Some 10YR 3/2 spots					
Bw	31-53	10YR 5/4	m1d 10YR 5/8	ls	1mabk	vfr	gs
BC	53-76	10YR 5/3,5/4	m2d 10YR 4/8	ls	1mpl	vfr	cs
C1	76-86	10YR 4/3	m2d 10YR 5/8	ls	0sg	lo	cs
C2g	86-108	2.5Y 5/2,6/2	f1d 10YR 4/8	calc. s	0sg	lo	-
2Ab	125-130	10YR 3/1	m1d 2.5Y 5/1	calc. s	Described from spoil material		

Notes: Wood recovered at 130 cm, with buried surface at 125-130 cm (depths are approximate); northeast face described, 1 m from north end of trench; somewhat poorly drained; water table at 98 cm; described 1/13/00

Figure 1 HU6 Trench
3

Figure 2 HU7 Trench
3B

Figure 3 HU6 EU3

LITERATURE CITED

Boccheciamp, R.A. 1977. Soil survey of the Humacao area of eastern Puerto Rico. USDA, Soil Conservation Service, Pub. by U.S. Government Printing, Washington, D.C.

----- Original Message -----

Subject: Re: East coast Puerto Rico sites

Date: Mon, 11 Feb 2002 20:19:52 EST

From: Fossjohne@aol.com

To: psiegel@johnmilnerassociates.com

Had a good trip to AZ. In looking over the notes for HU7, it definitely appears that the buried surface horizons at 3B and 4 are separate horizons and represent different time periods. The buried wood in Trench 1 is probably related to the deeply buried wood and surface in Trench 4. As mentioned in my notes, we did not see a buried surface in Trench 1, except for the wood. These surfaces are thin and can easily be eroded away by water movement, or perhaps even wind if they dry out.

Hope this answers the questions.

John

STANDARD ABBREVIATIONS

MOTTLES:

Abundance

f - few
c - common
m - many

Size

1 - fine
2 - medium
3 - large

Contrast

f - faint
d - distinct
p - prominent

TEXTURES:

s - sand
ls - loamy sand
sl - sandy loam

l - loam
sil - silt loam
si - silt

scl - sandy clay loam
cl - clay loam
sicl - silty clay loam

sc - sandy clay
sic - silty clay
c - clay

Textural Modifiers:

vf - very fine
f - fine
c - coarse

g - gravel and gravelly

STRUCTURE:

Grade

1 - weak
2 - moderate
3 - strong

Size

vf - very fine
f - fine
m - medium
c - coarse
vc - very coarse

Form or Type

pl - platy
pr - prismatic
bk - blocky
abk - angular blocky

sbk - subangular blocky
sg - single grain
gr - granular
m - massive

CONSISTENCE:

Moist

lo - loose
vfr - very friable
fr - friable

fi - firm
vfi - very firm
efi - extremely firm

Wet

so - nonsticky
ss - slightly sticky
s - sticky
vs - very sticky

po - nonplastic
ps - slightly plastic
p - plastic

PERMEABILITY:

Rapid: Coarse textured soils such as sands and loamy sands with no impervious layers, pans, or cemented layers.

Moderate: Medium textured soils such as sandy loams, loams, silt loams and silts. Sandy clay loams, clay loams and silty loams may also be in this category, as long as they are not found in dense compacted layers. Also no impervious layers, pans, or cemented layers.

Slow: Fine textured soils such as sandy clay, silt clay, and clay. Impervious layers, pans, or cemented layers would constitute a slow permeability.

APPENDIX IIIA
PROVENIENCE LOG
SITE HU-6

**SITE HU-6
PROVENIENCE LOG
INTRODUCTION**

Owing to the large number of data fields, the artifact inventories from Sites HU-6 and HU-7 were each divided into two appendices (IIIa/IIIb and IIIc/III d, respectively). Appendices IIIa (Site HU-6) and IIIc (Site HU-7), called the Provenience Logs, present provenience information for the artifact lots (Bag Numbers). Each lot is associated with a unique set of up to five locational parameters: provenience type, provenience number, level number, north/south coordinate, and east/west coordinate. Each parameter represents a field in the database. A sixth data field is reserved for the bag number (or lot).

Appendices IIIb (Site HU-6) and III d (Site HU-7), the Artifact Inventories, contain nine data fields: bag no., artifact weight (g), artifact count, artifact category, ceramic surface treatment, temper, ceramic secondary shape features, vessel lip shape, and notes. The Provenience Log and Artifact Inventory for each site are linked together by the Bag No. field.

Provenience Log
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
1	Surface	1		0	0
2	Shovel Test	1		10	15
3	Unit	1	1	20	23
4	Unit	1	2	20	23
5	Unit	1	3	20	23
6	Unit	1	4	20	23
7	Unit	1	5	20	23
8	Unit	1	6	20	23
9	Unit	2	1	10	2
10	Unit	2	2	10	2
11	Unit	2	3	10	2
12	Unit	2	5	10	2
13	Trench	1		0	0
14	Trench	1		0	0
15	Trench	1		0	0
16	Trench	1		0	0
17	Trench	3	A	0	0
18	Trench	4		0	0
19	Trench	4		0	0
20	Trench	4	A	0	0
21	Trench	4	B	0	0
22	Surface	2		0	0
23	Unit	3	1	124	30
24	Unit	3	2	124	30
25	Unit	3	3	124	30
26	Unit	3	4	124	30
27	Unit	3	5	124	30
28	Unit	3	6	124	30
29	Surface	3		0	0
30	Surface	4		0	0
31	Unit	4	1	192	29
32	Unit	4	2	192	29
33	Unit	4	1	192	29
38	Unit	5	1	139	41
39	Unit	5	2	139	41
40	Unit	5	3	139	41
41	Unit	5	4	139	41
42	Unit	5	5	139	41
43	Unit	6	1	162	50
44	Unit	6	2	162	50
45	Unit	4	3	192	29
46	Unit	4	4	192	29
47	Unit	6	3	162	50
48	Unit	6	4	162	50
49	Unit	6	5	162	50

Provenience Log
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
50	Surface	5		190	30
51	Unit	9	1	157	29
52	Unit	10	1	102	20
53	Unit	10	2	102	20
54	Unit	10	3	102	20
55	Unit	8	1	159	16
56	Unit	8	2	159	16
57	Unit	8	3	159	16
58	Unit	7	1	187	49
59	Surface	6		0	0
60	Unit	10	5	102	20
61	Unit	11	1	180	15
62	Unit	11	2	180	15
63	Unit	12	2	142	8
64	Unit	12	3	142	8
65	Unit	12	4	142	8
66	Unit	13	1	152	0
67	Unit	13	2	152	0
68	Unit	13	3	152	0
69	Unit	13	4	152	0
70	Unit	14	1	145	60
71	Unit	14	2	145	60
72	Unit	14	2	145	60
73	Unit	14	4	145	60
74	Unit	16	1	98	3
75	Unit	16	3	98	3
76	Unit	16	5	98	3
77	Unit	16	6	98	3
78	Shovel Test	15	1	130	25
79	Unit	15	2	130	25
80	Unit	15	3	130	25
81	Unit	15	4	130	25
82	Unit	15	4	130	25
83	Unit	15	5	130	25
84	Unit	15	6	130	25
85	Unit	15	7	130	25
86	Unit	15	8	130	25
87	Unit	17	1	124	12
88	Unit	17	2	124	12
89	Unit	17	3	124	12
90	Unit	17	4	124	12
91	Unit	17	5	124	12
92	Unit	17	6	124	12
93	Unit	17	7	124	12
94	Unit	17	8	124	12

Provenience Log
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
150	Unit	1	7	20	23
151	Unit	16	2	98	3
152	Surface	7		0	0
197	Unit	19	1	130	18
198	Unit	19	2	130	18
199	Unit	19	3	130	18
200	Unit	19	4	130	18
201	Unit	18	1	139	28
202	Unit	18	2	139	28
203	Unit	18	3	139	28
204	Unit	18	4	139	28
205	Unit	18	5	139	28
206	Unit	18	6	139	28
207	Unit	19	5	130	18
208	Unit	18	6	130	18
209	Unit	19	7	130	18
210	Unit	19	8	130	18
1043	Surface	GENERAL		0	0

APPENDIX III B
ARTIFACT INVENTORY
SITE HU-6

**SITE HU-6
ARTIFACT INVENTORY
INTRODUCTION**

Owing to the large number of data fields, the artifact inventories from Sites HU-6 and HU-7 were each divided into two appendices (IIIa/IIIb and IIIc/III d, respectively). Appendices IIIa (Site HU-6) and IIIc (Site HU-7), called the Provenience Logs, present provenience information for the artifact lots (Bag Numbers). Each lot is associated with a unique set of up to five locational parameters: provenience type, provenience number, level number, north/south coordinate, and east/west coordinate. Each parameter represents a field in the database. A sixth data field is reserved for the bag number (or lot).

Appendices IIIb (Site HU-6) and III d (Site HU-7), the Artifact Inventories, contain nine data fields: bag no., artifact weight (g), artifact count, artifact category, ceramic surface treatment, temper, ceramic secondary shape features, vessel lip shape, and notes. The Provenience Log and Artifact Inventory for each site are linked together by the Bag No. field.

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
1	0.9	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			possible waster
1	27.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
2	14.3	44	Shell fragments					
3	0	1	Cobalt Blue Bottle Glass					
3	0	1	Local Slipped Redware					
3	0	1	Plain Cream Colored (C.C.) Ware					
3	21.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
3	31.9	32	Coral fragments					
3	57.3	150	Shell fragments					
4	0.7	4	Shell fragments					
4	3.6	3	Coral fragments					
4	3.7	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
5	9.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
6	1.2	1	Coral fragments					
6	2.4	21	Shell fragments					
6	30.8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			residue inside.
7	4.1	2	Coral fragments					
7	11.9	58	Shell fragments					
8	0.7	2	Coral fragments					
8	32.9	120	Shell fragments					
8	39.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
9	0	1	Aqua Bottle Glass					
9	0	1	Modern Mortar					
9	0	1	Olive Green Spirit Bottle Glass					
9	0	1	Plain White Granite					
9	4.2	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
9	5	2	Shell fragments					
9	38	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible buren (thick:18.3mm)
9	38.4	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
10	28.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
10	53	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
11	0.5	1	Shell fragments					
12	6.2	4	Shell fragments					
13	31.9	1	Buren	Plain unslipped	Sand			
14	6.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			possible coil break
14	31.7	1	Buren	Plain unslipped	Sand			
14	105.8	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
15	8.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
16	1.1	1	Plain Cream Colored (C.C.) Ware					
16	1.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
17	9.7	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
18	3.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
18	6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
18	14.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag.,	indeterminate	
18	16.8	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
18	18.5	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
18	32.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
18	110.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag.,	indeterminate	
18	404.2	22	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			3 possible coil breaks
19	8.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
19	8.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
19	14	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Handle frag.,	indeterminate	
19	29.6	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	exterior lip flange.
19	29.8	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
19	37.6	4	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			lip:round(1),square(2),incised(1).
19	117.9	9	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
19	404	25	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
20	5.3	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
20	28.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
20	91.8	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
21	4.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
21	11	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
22	45.5	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
23	4.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	weathered,incised line parallel to rim.
23	39.9	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
24	4.5	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
24	8.3	1	Shell fragments					
24	8.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
24	56.4	19	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
25	3.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
25	9	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
25	47.5	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
26	4.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
26	7.7	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
26	86.6	16	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
27	5.8	12	Shell fragments					
27	13.7	6	Coral fragments					
27	59.4	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
28	0.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
28	1.1	3	Shell fragments					
28	22.2	3	Coral fragments					
28	30.7	14	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			(1) coil break
29	0	1	Blue Floral					
29	0	1	Local Slipped Redware					gravely paste
29	0	1	Scalloped Rim Impressed Curved Edgeware					
29	0	1	Unidentified Domestic Stoneware					
29	0	1	Unscaloped Impressed Rim Edgeware					
29	0	2	Olive Green Spirit Bottle Glass					
29	0	2	Plain Clear Glazed Redware					
29	0	2	Polychrome Painted (Red, Black, Lt Blue, Lt Green					
29	0	2	Spattered Ware on White Body					
29	0	3	Blue and Simpled Banded Dipped Ware					
29	0	10	Plain White Granite					
29	6	1	Shell fragments					
29	72.3	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible buren.
30	0	1	Unidentified Porcelain					
30	0	4	Plain Cream Colored (C.C.) Ware					
30	8.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Handle frag., indeterminate		
30	15	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
30	39	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
30	39.4	2	Buren	Plain unslipped	quartz			
30	51.6	1	Shell fragments					
31	0	1	Unidentified Delft					plain light gray glaze.
31	0	1	Unidentified Metal Object					UID metal.
31	0.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
31	5.3	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
31	6.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vestigial handle fragment.
31	7.5	1	Body sherds	Incised	Sand	Handle frag., indeterminate		Sta. Elena.
31	15.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
31	25.2	1	Shell fragments					
32	2.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
32	6.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			painted interior.
32	7.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
33	0	1	Charcoal					charcoal sample.
38	0	1	Unidentified Nail					
38	0	7	Charcoal					
38	0.3	1	Shell fragments					
38	0.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
38	2.3	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	weathered.
38	6.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			2 subparallel lines of incision on interior.
38	10	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
39	0	10	Charcoal					
39	1.4	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
39	4.4	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
39	8.2	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 surface frag.
40	1.4	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	weathered.
40	2.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	possible restricted, weathered.
40	6.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
40	11.1	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
41	1.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
41	10.3	2	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	mends.
41	47.7	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
42	13.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
42	14.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
43	0	1	Unidentifiable Non Iron/Steel					
43	7.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unidentified	round	
43	11	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	decoration more punctate and drag.
44	4.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
45	1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
46	3.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
47	74.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
48	10.2	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
49	0.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
49	21.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
49	31	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			4 sherdlets
50	223.7	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
51	0	1	Unidentifiable Non Iron/Steel					
52	50.8	1	Shell fragments					

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
53	6.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
54	5	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
55	0	1	0.8 to 0.89 mm Flat Glass					
55	0	1	1.8 to 1.89 mm Flat Glass					
55	0	1	Brown Line Wares (over or underglaze)					
55	0	1	Dipped Ware Tan, Rust, Brown, Olive, Ocher, Gray					
55	0	1	Molded Tumbler					
55	0	1	North Devon Gravel Tempered					
55	0	1	Plain Clear Glaze Slipware					mottled hematite glaze.
55	0	1	Unglazed Redware					
55	0	1	Unidentified Clay Bowl Pipe Bowl					
55	0	1	Unidentified Domestic Stoneware					neck piece.
55	0	2	Aqua Bottle Glass					
55	0	2	Blue and Simplified Banded Dipped Ware					
55	0	2	Clear Bottle Glass					
55	0	2	Opaque Blue Machine Made Bottle Glass					
55	0	2	Spike					
55	0	2	Sponged Ware on White Body					sponged blue on white.
55	0	3	1.4 to 1.49 mm Flat Glass					
55	0	3	Scalloped Rim Impressed Curved Edgeware					
55	0	3	Unidentified Nail					
55	0	4	Plain Clear Glazed Redware					
55	0	5	Olive Green Spirit Bottle Glass					
55	0	17	Unidentifiable/Corroded Iron/Steel					
55	0	19	Plain White Granite					1 handle.
55	0.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			poss. slip interior (polished, thin layer)
55	2.2	2	Shatter					UID chert.
55	3.4	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Unidentified		weathered sherdlets.
55	5.7	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
55	12.1	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
55	21	17	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
55	94.6	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
55	125.9	1	Hammerstone					quartzite.
56	8.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
57	32.1	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
58	0	1	Bottle Glass, Embossed Letters					A
58	0	2	Unidentifiable Non Iron/Steel					

Artifact Inventory
Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
Humacao, Puerto Rico
Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
59	0	1	Clear Bottle Glass					
59	0	1	Clear Glaze Buff Bodied Refined Earthenware					gravely paste.
59	0	1	Scalloped Rim Impressed Curved Edgeware					
59	0	2	Plain Clear Glazed Redware					
59	0	2	Plain White Granite					
59	0	4	Blue Floral					
59	0	4	Unglazed Redware					
59	0	5	Olive Green Spirit Bottle Glass					
59	3.2	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
59	4.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
59	68.9	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
60	5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
61	0	1	Flow Painted (Blue, Purple)					
61	0	1	Plain White Granite					
61	0	2	Handmade Brick					
61	10.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
61	50.7	1	Coral fragments					
62	6.3	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
63	0	1	Clear Glaze Buff Bodied Refined Earthenware					
63	3.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
64	0	1	Aqua Bottle Glass					
64	0	1	Scalloped Rim Impressed Curved Edgeware					
64	0	1	Unidentifiable Non Iron/Steel					
64	1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
65	8.5	8	Charcoal					
66	3.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
67	2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
67	11.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
68	15.2	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
68	15.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
68	23.3	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	internally thickened rim.
70	3.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
70	7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
70	7.4	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
70	15.4	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 possible smudging exterior.
70	28.6	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
73	1.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			

Artifact Inventory
Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
Humacao, Puerto Rico
Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
73	3.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
74	0	1	Plain White Granite					
75	6.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
76	3.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
77	15.4	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
78	0	1	Unidentifiable Non Iron/Steel					
79	0	1	Molded Stemware					
79	0	1	Coral fragments					
79	0.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
79	10.3	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
79	14	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
80	13	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
81	1.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			soot on interior.
81	1.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
81	7.7	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
81	16.6	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
81	148.8	28	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
82	0	1	Charcoal					charcoal sample south 1/2.
83	1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
83	6.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina		
83	7.8	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
83	35.9	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
83	49.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
83	150.8	16	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
84	2.9	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
84	12.3	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
84	14.6	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
84	30.8	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
85	15.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
85	25.3	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
86	7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
87	1.2	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
87	5.4	4	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
87	15.1	2	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
87	20.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
87	27.9	13	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
88	5.5	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
88	5.5	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
88	6.7	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
88	8.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
88	9.9	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
89	0	2	Charcoal					
89	0.3	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	small.
89	0.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible rim sherd
89	2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			punctate
89	3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
89	5.1	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
89	6	4	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand			
89	17.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	2' shape tabular handle.
89	18.6	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	w/exterior lip flange (2' shape feature)
89	20.5	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
89	20.9	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
89	153.5	20	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
89	171.7	50	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			2 possible coil breaks
90	1.9	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
90	3.6	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	w/ punctate.
90	10	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Handle frag.,	indeterminate	
90	12.7	4	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
90	19.6	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina	round	exterior lip flange.
90	25.8	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
90	65.1	9	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
90	203.2	29	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
91	17	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
91	24	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
91	96.7	14	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
91	195.3	26	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			1 possible coil break
92	35	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
92	47.6	12	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
93	1.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
93	21.5	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
93	24.5	3	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
93	36.6	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
94	2.3	1	Body sherds	Incised	Sand			
94	6.6	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
150	4.1	4	Coral fragments					
150	40.4	82	Shell fragments					
151	0	1	Charcoal					
151	3.1	12	Body sherds					under fired pottery, wasters.
152	21.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
152	40.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
197	6.5	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
197	18.4	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
198	4.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
198	8.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag.,	indeterminate	
198	40.9	12	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
199	0.5	2	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
199	1.6	2	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
199	7.7	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unspecified	round	exterior lip flange.
199	8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
199	11.6	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
199	87.5	2	Shell fragments					
199	273.2	46	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
199	292.5	34	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
200	19.3	3	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
200	71	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
200	186.7	30	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
201	0	1	Aqua Bottle Glass					
201	0	1	Light Blue Machine Made Bottle Glass					
201	0	1	Olive Green Spirit Bottle Glass					
201	0	2	Green Bottle Glass					
201	34.8	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
202	7.3	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
202	21.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
203	0	11	Charcoal					
203	4.7	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
203	5.2	2	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
203	6.9	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
203	13.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
203	89.7	13	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
204	12.5	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
205	107.9	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-6, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Features	Lip Shape	Notes
206	3.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
207	3.2	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
207	40.8	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
208	44.7	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
209	6.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
210	8.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1043	41.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina	square	
1043	41.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina	square	
1043	50.6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	possible griddle.
1043	50.6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	thick lip-possible griddle

APPENDIX IIIc
PROVENIENCE LOG
SITE HU-6

**SITE HU-7
PROVENIENCE LOG
INTRODUCTION**

Owing to the large number of data fields, the artifact inventories from Sites HU-6 and HU-7 were each divided into two appendices (IIIa/IIIb and IIIc/IIIId, respectively). Appendices IIIa (Site HU-6) and IIIc (Site HU-7), called the Provenience Logs, present provenience information for the artifact lots (Bag Numbers). Each lot is associated with a unique set of up to five locational parameters: provenience type, provenience number, level number, north/south coordinate, and east/west coordinate. Each parameter represents a field in the database. A sixth data field is reserved for the bag number (or lot).

Appendices IIIb (Site HU-6) and IIIId (Site HU-7), the Artifact Inventories, contain nine data fields: bag no., artifact weight (g), artifact count, artifact category, ceramic surface treatment, temper, ceramic secondary shape features, vessel lip shape, and notes. The Provenience Log and Artifact Inventory for each site are linked together by the Bag No. field.

Provenience Log
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	Feature No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
34	Trench	3A			0	0
35	Trench	3B			0	0
36	Trench	4			0	0
37	Trench	1			0	0
95	Trench	3A			0	0
96	Trench	3B			0	0
97	Trench	3B			0	0
98	Trench	3A/3B			0	0
99	Trench	3A/3B			0	0
100	Trench	3A	1		0	0
101	Trench	3A	2		0	0
102	Trench	3A			0	0
103	Unit	1	1		72	-13
104	Unit	1	2		72	-13
105	Unit	1	3		72	-13
106	Unit	1	4		72	-13
107	Unit	1	5		72	-13
108	Unit	1	6		72	-13
109	Unit	1	7		72	-13
110	Unit	1	8		72	-13
111	Unit	1	9		72	-13
112	Unit	1	10		72	-13
113	Unit	1	11		72	-13
114	Unit	2	1		76	-17
115	Unit	2	2		76	-17
116	Unit	2	3		76	-17
117	Unit	2	4		76	-17
118	Unit	2	5		76	-17
119	Unit	3	1		82	0
120	Unit	3	2		82	0
121	Unit	3	3		82	0
122	Unit	3	4		82	0
123	Unit	3	5		82	0
124	Unit	3	6		82	0
125	Unit	3	7		82	0
126	Unit	3	3	7	82	0
127	Unit	4	1		62	-36
128	Unit	4	2		62	-36
129	Unit	4	3		62	-36
130	Unit	5	1		14	1
131	Unit	5	2		14	1
132	Unit	6	2		40	25
133	Unit	6	3		40	25
134	Unit	6	4		40	25
135	Unit	6	5		40	25
136	Unit	7	1		60	5

Provenience Log
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
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Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	Feature No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
137	Unit	7	3		60	5
138	Unit	7	4		60	5
139	Unit	7	5		60	5
140	Unit	7	6		60	5
141	Unit	8	1		70	12
142	Unit	8	2		70	12
143	Unit	8	3		70	12
144	Unit	8	4		70	12
145	Unit	8	5		70	12
146	Unit	9	1		36	5
147	Unit	10	1		49	12
148	Trench	3B		5	0	0
149	Trench	4			0	0
153	Unit	11	1		73	-13
154	Unit	11	2		73	-13
155	Unit	11	3		73	-13
156	Unit	11	4		73	-13
157	Unit	11	5		73	-13
158	Unit	11	6		73	-13
159	Unit	11	7		73	-13
160	Unit	11	8		73	-13
161	Unit	11	9		73	-13
162	Unit	12	1		81	0
163	Unit	12	2		81	0
164	Unit	12	3		81	0
165	Unit	12	5		81	0
166	Unit	12	6		81	0
167	Unit	12	7		81	0
168	Unit	13	1		73	-12
169	Unit	13	2		73	-12
170	Unit	13	3		73	-12
171	Unit	13	4		73	-12
172	Unit	13	6		73	-12
173	Unit	13	7		73	-12
174	Unit	13	8		73	-12
175	Unit	13	9		73	-12
176	Unit	12	4		81	0
177	Unit	16	1		98	-1
178	Unit	16	3-Feb		98	-1
179	Unit	16	4		98	-1
180	Unit	16	5		98	-1
181	Unit	14	1		72	-12
182	Unit	14	2		72	-12
183	Unit	14	4		72	-12
184	Unit	14	5		72	-12
185	Unit	14	6		72	-12

Provenience Log
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	Feature No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
186	Unit	14	8		72	-12
187	Unit	14	7		72	-12
188	Unit	14	9		72	-12
189	Unit	15	1		85	-20
190	Unit	15	2		85	-20
191	Unit	15	3		85	-20
192	Unit	15	4		85	-20
193	Unit	15	5		85	-20
194	Unit	15	6		85	-20
195	Unit	15	7		85	-20
196	Unit	15	8		85	-20
211	Unit	18	1		74	-12
212	Unit	18	2		74	-12
213	Unit	18	3		74	-12
214	Unit	18	4		74	-12
215	Unit	18	6		74	-12
216	Unit	18	6		74	-12
217	Unit	18	6		74	-12
218	Unit	18	7		74	-12
219	Unit	18	5		74	-12
220	Unit	20	1		73	-11
221	Unit	20	2		73	-11
222	Unit	20	4		73	-11
223	Unit	20	6		73	-11
224	Unit	20	7		73	-11
225	Unit	21	1		72	-11
226	Unit	21	5		72	-11
227	Unit	21	6		72	-11
228	Unit	21	7		72	-11
229	Unit	21	8		72	-11
230	Unit	17	1		74	-13
231	Unit	17	2		74	-13
232	Unit	17	3		74	-13
234	Unit	17	4		74	-13
235	Unit	17	5		74	-13
236	Unit	17	6		74	-13
237	Unit	17	7		74	-13
238	Unit	17	8		74	-13
239	Unit	17	9		74	-13
240	Unit	19	1		74	-11
241	Unit	19	6		74	-11
242	Unit	19	7		74	-11
243	Shovel Test	1	1		0	0
244	Shovel Test	3	1		0	0
245	Shovel Test	5	2		0	0
1000	Unit	29	1		83	18

Provenience Log
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	Feature No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
1001	Unit	29	2		83	-19
1002	Unit	29	3		83	-19
1003	Unit	29	4		83	-19
1004	Unit	28	1		83	-20
1005	Unit	28	2		83	-20
1006	Unit	28	3		83	-20
1007	Unit	28	4		83	-20
1008	Unit	28	5		83	-20
1009	Unit	26	1		82	-19
1010	Unit	26	2		82	-19
1011	Unit	26	2		82	-19
1012	Unit	26	3		82	-19
1013	Unit	22	2		76	-12
1014	Unit	22	3		76	-12
1015	Unit	23	2		76	-13
1016	Unit	24	2		77	-13
1017	Unit	27	1		82	-20
1018	Unit	27	2		82	-20
1019	Unit	27	3		82	-20
1020	Unit	31	1		76	19
1021	Unit	25	1		77	-12
1022	Unit	25	2		77	-12
1023	Unit	25	2		77	-12
1024	Unit	25	4		77	-12
1025	Unit	31	1		76	-20
1026	Unit	31	1		76	-20
1027	Unit	31	2		76	-20
1028	Unit	31	3		76	-20
1029	Unit	33	1		73	-21
1030	Unit	33	2		73	-21
1031	Unit	33	3		73	-21
1032	Unit	33	4		73	-21
1033	Unit	34	1		73	-22
1034	Unit	34	2		73	-22
1035	Unit	34	3		73	-22
1036	Unit	34	4		73	-22
1037	Unit	37	1		76	-14
1038	Unit	37	2		76	-14
1039	Unit	37	3		76	-14
1040	Unit	37	4		76	-14
1041	Unit	38	2		75.5	-13
1042	Unit	39	1		75.5	13
1044	Surface	GENERAL			0	0
1045	Unit	31	4		76	-20
1046	Unit	31	5		76	-20
1047	Unit	34	5		73	21

Provenience Log
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	Feature No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
1048	Unit	36	1		74	-21
1049	Unit	36	2		74	-21
1050	Unit	36	3		74	-21
1051	Unit	36	4		74	-21
1052	Unit	36	5		74	-21
1053	Unit	37	5		76	-14
1054	Unit	38	3		75.5	-13
1055	Unit	39	3		75.5	-14
1056	Unit	39	4		75.5	-14
1057	Unit	39	5		75.5	-14
1058	Unit	35	1		74	-22
1059	Unit	35	2		74	-22
1060	Unit	35	3		74	-22
1061	Unit	35	4		74	-22
1062	Unit	35	5		74	-22
1063	Unit	43	1		72	-22
1064	Unit	43	2		72	-22
1065	Unit	43	3		72	-22
1066	Unit	43	4		72	-22
1067	Unit	30	1		80	-5
1068	Unit	30	2		80	-5
1069	Unit	30	3		80	-5
1070	Unit	30	4		80	-5
1071	Unit	30	4		80	-5
1072	Unit	30	5		80	-5
1073	Unit	30	6		80	-5
1074	Unit	30	7		80	-5
1075	Unit	32	1		80	5
1076	Unit	43	5		72	-22
1077	Unit	32	2		80	-6
1078	Unit	32	4		80	-6
1079	Unit	32	5		80	-6
1080	Unit	32	6		80	-6
1081	Unit	32	7		80	-6
1082	Unit	32	8		80	-6
1083	Unit	42	1		72	-21
1084	Unit	42	2		72	-21
1085	Unit	42	3		72	-21
1086	Unit	42	4		72	-21
1087	Unit	42	5		72	-21
1088	Unit	41	1		81	-6
1089	Unit	41	3		81	-6
1090	Unit	41	6		81	-6
1091	Unit	41	6		81	-6
1092	Unit	41	6		81	-6
1093	Unit	41	7		81	-6

Provenience Log
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Provenience Type	Provenience No.	Level No.	Feature No.	North Coordinate	East Coordinate
1094	Unit	41	8		81	-6
1095	Unit	40	1		81	-5
1096	Unit	40	2		81	-5
1097	Unit	40	3		81	-5
1098	Unit	40	4		81	-5
1099	Unit	40	5		81	-5
1100	Unit	40	6		81	-5
1101	Unit	44	1		79	-5
1102	Unit	44	2		79	-5
1103	Unit	44	3		79	-5
1104	Unit	44	4		79	-5
1105	Unit	44	4		79	-5
1106	Unit	44	4		79	-5
1107	Unit	44	4		79	-5
1108	Unit	44	5		79	-5
1109	Unit	45	1		79	-6
1110	Unit	45	2		79	-6
1111	Unit	45	3		79	-6
1112	Unit	45	4		79	-6
1113	Unit	45	4		79	-6
1114	Unit	45	4		79	-6
1115	Unit	40	7		81	-5
1116	Unit	40	8		81	-5
1117	Unit	44	6		79	-5
1118	Unit	45	5		79	-6

APPENDIX III D
ARTIFACT INVENTORY
SITE HU-7

**SITE HU-7
ARTIFACT INVENTORY
INTRODUCTION**

Owing to the large number of data fields, the artifact inventories from Sites HU-6 and HU-7 were each divided into two appendices (IIIa/IIIb and IIIc/IIIId, respectively). Appendices IIIa (Site HU-6) and IIIc (Site HU-7), called the Provenience Logs, present provenience information for the artifact lots (Bag Numbers). Each lot is associated with a unique set of up to five locational parameters: provenience type, provenience number, level number, north/south coordinate, and east/west coordinate. Each parameter represents a field in the database. A sixth data field is reserved for the bag number (or lot).

Appendices IIIb (Site HU-6) and IIIId (Site HU-7), the Artifact Inventories, contain nine data fields: bag no., artifact weight (g), artifact count, artifact category, ceramic surface treatment, temper, ceramic secondary shape features, vessel lip shape, and notes. The Provenience Log and Artifact Inventory for each site are linked together by the Bag No. field.

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
34	78.8	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
35	0	3		Amber Bottle Glass				embossed "AMB" and "IRE"
35	9	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			SADDLE rim, thickens @ lip.
35	18.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
35	21.3	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	square	
35	22.3	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	internally thickened rim.
35	24	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			pattern painted-red on interior.
35	48.9	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
35	63.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
35	75.3	3	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
35	130.7	3	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
35	175.2	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	
35	176	20	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
35	350.9	11	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
95	79.1	4	Restricted and Convex Rim	unspecified	quartz			thicker lip;red paint along lip&ext
95	191.6	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
96	87.1	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
97	2.6	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
97	5.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
97	10.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
97	16.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
97	20.7	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			w/ exterior lip flange.
97	31.5	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
97	42	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
97	51.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
97	94.3	3	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vertically incised; strap handle.
97	290.4	26	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
98	0	1	Bottle Glass, Embossed Letters					"TEJA"
98	0	2	Amber Bottle Glass					
98	3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
98	4.2	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			small weathered piece.
98	5.3	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz			
98	6.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
98	7.3	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
98	7.8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
98	8.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			UID; 2' shape feature.
98	12.4	1	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz			pattern painted red exterior.
98	14.8	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	square	w/ internally thick rim.

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
 Jan-Feb 2001

Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
98	15.8	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vertically incised.
98	21.7	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
98	27.8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
98	48.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	round rim, ext lip fold, thicker lip
98	49.8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
98	52.4	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	
98	56.9	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina		2 soft, 1 sharp carina.
98	58.4	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	internal thickened rim.
98	70.9	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
98	84.9	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina		2 sharp, 1 soft carina.
98	114	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	square	
98	128.3	7	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
98	142.4	5	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			lip thickens @ rim; 3 diff. Vessels
98	1015	89	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
99	2.3	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
99	5.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
99	12.7	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
99	13.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			UID 2' shape .
99	29.5	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
99	35.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
99	40.4	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	thickens @ lip.
99	53.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
99	53.8	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
99	67.8	2	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz			pattern painted-1 brown, 1 red.
99	70.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		handle attachment
99	71.8	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	thickens @ lip.
99	135.3	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		poss.handle frag;(2)vertical incision.
99	804.9	92	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
100	8.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
101	0.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			sherdlet.
101	2.3	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
101	54.2	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
101	66.1	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	thickens @ lip.
101	83.1	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
102	61.9	2	Concave Rim	unspecified	quartz		round	paint upper body&rim internally thick
102	71.9	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
103	7.8	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz			
103	16.9	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	vestigial handle.

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
104	2.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Soft Carina		punctate.
104	40.6	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
105	0.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
105	1.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
106	6.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
108	11.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
108	51.1	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
109	0.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
109	18.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
110	5.3	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
110	9.9	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
110	19.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Handle frag., indeterminate		
110	50.2	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
110	151.2	24	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			2 possible coil breaks
111	2.3	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
111	3.9	9	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
111	6.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
111	27	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
111	30	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand	Sharp Carina	square	
111	36.8	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
111	83.6	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot on inside?
111	268.1	27	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 possible coil break
112	34.1	4	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	weathered
112	68.6	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			weathered, 2 possible coil breaks
113	43.8	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 possible coil break
113	124.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot on inside?
114	1.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
114	18.5	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
116	11.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
117	6.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
117	65.7	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	
117	76.7	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
118	31.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
118	44.4	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
119	2.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
119	4.5	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
119	20.5	1	Buren	Plain unslipped	quartz			
119	25.8	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
120	36.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
121	15.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
122	23.5	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
122	167.6	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
122	193.2	13	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
123	16.1	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	T-shaped rim; SADDLE rim.
123	36.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
123	41.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
123	108.5	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
124	47.3	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
124	66	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot inside?
125	110.8	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 possible coil break
127	0	1	Clear Bottle Glass					embossed "PINT"
127	3.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
127	13.1	2	Coral fragments					
127	18.7	1	Bone					
128	13.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
128	21.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
129	34.6	5	Coral fragments					
130	0	3	Unidentified Nail					
131	0	5	Unidentified Nail					
131	14.2	3	OliveGreen Spirit Bottle Glass					
132	0	1	Clear Bottle Glass					
132	0	4	Unidentified Nail					
133	0	2	Unidentified Nail					
133	12.3	15	Shell fragments					
133	14.9	2	Coral fragments					
134	0	24	Unidentified Nail					
134	1.5	1	Coral fragments					
134	2.3	3	Shell fragments					
135	0	2	Unidentified Nail					
135	6.8	15	Shell fragments					
135	28.9	5	Coral fragments					
136	0	2	Amber Bottle Glass					
136	0	2	Unidentified Brick					
136	0	2	Unidentified Brick					
136	0	3	Unidentified Nail					
136	0	4	Clear Bottle Glass					

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
136	2.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
136	8.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
136	89.1	7	Coral fragments					
137	5.2	5	Shell fragments					
137	5.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
138	14	22	Shell fragments					
139	4.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
139	20.2	8	Shell fragments					
140	11.2	20	Shell fragments					
141	15.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
142	0	5	Unidentified Nail					
142	19.7	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
143	24.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
144	23.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
146	0	1	Green Bottle Glass					
147	0	1	Metal Sheeting(roofing-etc)					
148	22.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
149	0	1						soil sample/ buried A & wood.
153	2.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
154	43.9	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
155	7.4	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
156	1.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
157	15.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			Mends w/ #111 body.
158	7.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
158	27.4	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Red Slip	quartz	Soft Carina	square	
158	29.3	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
158	36	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
158	48.4	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
158	120.9	17	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
158	153	2	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	red painted lip.
159	10.3	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
159	11.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
159	12.3	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
159	74.7	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
159	109.7	38	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			poss. coil breaks, poss. painted
160	1.8	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
160	44	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible coil breaks
161	71.3	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	Cuevas?

Artifact Inventory
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
162	8.2	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
162	15.4	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
162	38.3	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
163	43.1	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
164	13.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
164	17.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
164	32	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			red paint int. w/neg. space stripe.
165	6.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
165	162.2	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible coil break
166	0.9	1	Shell fragments					
166	1.5	13	Coral fragments					
166	5.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
167	20.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
167	26.5	35	Shell fragments					
167	31.5	5	Coral fragments					
168	61.4	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
169	8.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Unidentified		UID secondary feature.
169	9.9	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
170	2.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
170	9.2	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	CUEVAS?
170	10.4	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
172	6.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
172	28.4	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	internally thickened rim.
172	66.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
172	76.5	3	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	thickens @ lip.
172	212.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	STRAP handle; w/ vertical incisions.
172	264.6	22	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
173	3.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
173	4.1	1	Body sherds	Incised	Sand	Handle frag., indeterminate		handle w/ vertical incision.
173	6	1	Concave Rim	Red Slip	Sand		square	
173	11.1	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
173	14.7	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	thickens @ lip.
173	20.8	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
173	46.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
173	350	28	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
174	16.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
174	63.3	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	CUEVAS
175	6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
176	42	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
176	60.7	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
177	0	1	Unmeasured Flat Glass					
177	22.4	11	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
178	5.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
178	9.9	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
178	25.1	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
179	1.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
180	24.6	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
181	8.6	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
181	90.2	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
182	14.8	9	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible coil breaks
183	12.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
184	10.1	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
185	47.4	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
185	53.6	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	
185	77.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
185	105.2	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	square	vertical applique coils; SANTA ELENA.
185	395.2	41	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
186	10.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unidentified		2' shape, unidentified.
186	15.2	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
187	9.6	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
187	20.9	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Red Slip	quartz		round	thickens @ lip.
187	30.4	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
187	31.4	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	
187	38	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
187	42.8	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
187	61	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
187	142	4	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	flat lip, but rounded edges
187	210.1	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
187	322.4	57	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible coil break
188	4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
189	6.5	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
189	39.6	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
190	3.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
190	83.2	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
190	128.7	22	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
191	31.8	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
192	3.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
192	13.4	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Red Slip	Sand	Sharp Carina	square	
192	14.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
192	22.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Handle frag., indeterminate		
192	37.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
192	130	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
192	295.7	58	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			2 possible coil breaks
193	17.4	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	SADDLE rim.
193	39.4	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
193	40.2	105	Shell fragments					
193	73.3	4	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
193	100.9	3	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
193	114.1	22	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			2 possible coil breaks
193	215	34	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			possible coil break
194	0.6	1	Coral fragments					
194	7.4	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
194	18.6	24	Shell fragments					
194	19.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
194	94.2	14	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
195	15.3	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
195	23.3	20	Shell fragments					
195	34.5	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
196	9.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
196	21.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	lip coil.
196	26	7	Shell fragments					
211	4.8	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
212	2.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
213	12.5	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
214	1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
215	4.5	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
215	10.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
215	19.1	12	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
215	36.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
215	38.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	lip thickens @ rim.
215	64.6	3	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	lip thickens @ rim.
215	66.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
215	95.6	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
215	102.2	11	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		STRAP handle w/vertical incisions.

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
215	168.1	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vertical incisions.
215	428.8	5	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
215	435.3	33	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
216	38.7	4	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		STRAP handle w/ vertical incisions; all 216 mends.
216	121.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			all 216 mends.
216	137.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	vertical incision on STRAP handle area/all 216 mends.
216	155.8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			all of prov. 216 mends.
217	2.3	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
217	5.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
217	8	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
217	9.6	2	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	thickens @ lip, like folded.
217	16.4	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
217	22.6	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
217	24.9	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
217	31.4	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
217	31.5	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	thickens @ lip.
217	33.1	3	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
217	33.3	3	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
217	59	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Red Slip	quartz		round	thickens @ lip.
217	79.1	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	STRAP handle frag.
217	124.4	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
217	139.9	31	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			13 frag/sherdlets (<5mm).
217	145.2	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vertical incised STRAP handle.
218	8	2	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		square	
218	16.6	1	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz			red painted int. w/ neg. stripe; CUEVAS/MONTSERAT?
218	34.3	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
218	63.2	3	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
218	128	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
218	158.7	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
218	225.9	11	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
219	0.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
219	5.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
220	0	1	UID Non Iron/Steel					
221	9.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	
221	46.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
222	0.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			sherdlet.
223	4.9	3	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
223	5.2	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Red Slip	Sand	Sharp Carina	square	
223	10.1	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
223	16.7	3	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	folded interior rim.
223	24.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Button	round	soft carina.
223	52	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Soft Carina		
223	62.9	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			4 sherdlets.
223	71.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
223	89.2	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			some of body paste has disintegrated, partly hollowed out.
223	174.3	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	square	
224	1.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
224	2.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
224	4.5	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand	Sharp Carina		
224	9	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
225	0	2	Unidentified Metal Object					
225	1.8	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
225	3.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
226	3.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
227	3.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
227	4.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
227	18.7	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
227	19.1	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
228	2.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unidentified		rolled pieces.
228	5.8	19	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets/frags.
228	10.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
228	16.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
228	18	5	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vertical incisions on handle frag.
228	25.4	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
228	25.5	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	
228	30.7	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	
228	43.4	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
228	163.6	27	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
229	1.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 frag (<5mm)
230	6.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
231	12.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
231	12.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
231	13	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
232	0.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
234	0.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
235	3.4	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
236	1.6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
236	90.3	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	
236	103	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
236	143.7	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
237	1.9	1	Unidentified Rim	Red Slip	quartz		square	
237	4.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
237	20.3	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	pattern red paint along interior rim.
237	80.5	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			possible coil breaks
237	127.6	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
238	2.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
238	13	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
238	59.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			
239	0.3	2	Shell fragments					
239	1.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
239	6.3	3	Coral fragments					
240	25.6	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			fabric impressed.
241	2.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
241	15.6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	
241	17	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unidentified	round	
241	26.9	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unspecified	square	exterior lip flange.
241	54.9	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
241	59.7	2	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz			soot exterior.
241	250.3	28	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			13 frag/sherdlets.
242	1.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
242	13.5	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
242	32.5	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 frag/sherdlet.
243	0	5	UID Non Iron/Steel					
244	11.4	9	Charcoal					
245	28.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1000	3.2	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1000	3.6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1000	20.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
1000	39	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1000	151.2	20	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1001	15.2	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1001	16.4	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	
1001	22.1	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			coarse quartz
1001	159	16	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1002	15.4	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1003	27.5	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1004	3.9	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1004	4	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1004	6.7	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1004	10	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
1004	31	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1004	62.2	12	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1005	16.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1006	1.7	1	Deep and Convex Rim	unspecified	quartz		square	diagonal markings like cordmark.
1006	3.6	2	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		2 sherds mend.
1006	80.9	11	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1007	3	1	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz	Unidentified	round	diagonal parallel lines, like cordmarking.
1007	7.7	2	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	1 incised line, parallel cordmark diagonal lines.
1007	35.8	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1008	1.5	5	Shell fragments					
1008	5.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1009	54	16	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1010	19.1	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1010	28.1	28	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1010	45.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1012	58.6	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1013	0	4	Bone					
1013	11.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1013	65.7	13	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1014	1	2	Shell fragments					
1015	151.6	4	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 w/ soot
1015	189.2	14	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1016	1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1016	3.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1016	72.3	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1017	4.6	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1017	5.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1017	80.5	22	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1018	5.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1019	2.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1019	16.6	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1021	31.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1022	0.3	1	Charcoal					
1023	0.2	1	Charcoal					
1023	5	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1023	5.2	1	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vertical coils, Santa Elena.
1023	60.2	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1025	1	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	
1025	15.6	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1025	34	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1026	26.2	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1027	17.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1027	18.3	1	Body sherds	Incised	Sand			coil break
1027	43.6	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1028	31.4	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1028	108.9	13	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1029	5.5	1	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz			red painted exterior
1029	38.7	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1030	54.9	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1031	32.8	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	square round	
1031	37.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1031	61.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1031	67.2	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1031	67.2	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1032	25.9	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1033	91.9	20	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1034	6.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1034	12.7	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1034	13.5	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina	round	
1035	92.9	18	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			some with soot deposit
1036	6.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1036	68.4	13	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1037	17.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1037	32.6	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1038	28.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1038	399.8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1039	21.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1040	11.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
1040	14.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1040	40.3	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1041	2.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1041	620	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			glued together-part of pot bust
1042	0	1	Plain CreamColored(C.C.)Ware					
1042	0.5	1	Shell fragments					weight under 1 gram
1044	31.2	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1045	3.3	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz			coil break
1045	4.6	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1045	14.9	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1045	26.9	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1046	1.7	3	Shell fragments					
1046	9.2	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1047	15.7	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1048	3.6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1048	39	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 w/ soot deposit
1049	29.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1050	1.4	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1050	9.5	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	folded edge
1050	16.7	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1050	93.4	16	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1051	0	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1051	4.8	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1052	27.7	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1053	11	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1053	50.3	11	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1054	26.5	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	internally thick rim, red slip int&rim.
1054	44.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1055	52	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1056	2	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	most of rim gone
1056	5.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1056	5.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1057	32.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1058	6.1	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1058	19.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1058	94.5	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1059	1.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1059	27.5	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand	Carina	square	
1060	12.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1060	106.9	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1061	4.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1061	24.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1061	27.6	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand	Soft Carina	round	
1062	8.8	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1063	58.8	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1064	5	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1064	14.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			with soot
1064	63.9	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	square	
1064	68.3	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			some with soot
1065	12.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1065	72.1	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1066	0.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1066	2.3	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1066	12.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1067	92.3	22	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1068	1.1	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1068	12.6	5	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1069	0.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1070	42.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1071	2.7	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1071	643.8	39	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1072	1.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1072	13.5	27	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1072	26	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1072	36.8	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	2/3 of rim missing.
1072	46.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1072	46.7	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1072	165.2	5	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		rounded but flat, thickens @ lip.
1072	264.6	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sooty interior.
1072	866.3	85	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1073	20.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1074	8.6	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1075	1.3	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	

Artifact Inventory
Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1075	7.7	2	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1075	7.9	3	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1075	17.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	
1075	20.6	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
1075	20.8	3	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1075	99.4	18	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1076	11.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1077	0	1	Unidentified Metal Object					
1077	2.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina		
1078	1.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1078	29.3	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1079	3.6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	weathered.
1079	6.3	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	thickens @ lip, flattened lip.
1079	14.1	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1079	22.4	43	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1079	25.3	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1079	56	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	thickens @ lip.
1079	71.2	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1079	77.2	5	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1079	1054.8	78	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1080	9.7	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1080	16.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1080	17.9	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unidentified		
1080	23	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			weathered down lip.
1080	26	55	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1080	26.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	
1080	26.7	2	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1080	29.1	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1080	35.7	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			thickens @ lip, flattened lip.
1080	36	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
1080	107.4	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1080	215.2	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1080	397.7	48	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			47>5mm: 1<5mm.
1081	8.5	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1082	2	1	Shell fragments					
1082	8.7	1	Shallow and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1082	29.9	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1082	64.2	7	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1083	7	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1083	19.3	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1084	1.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1084	15.3	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	internally thickened rim.
1084	16.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot deposit, may be flat base
1084	27.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
1084	31.2	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1084	31.3	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	internally thickened rim.
1084	221.5	19	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1085	1.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1085	4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			weathered
1085	80.9	9	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1086	18.6	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1086	21	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1087	16.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1088	22.5	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1089	6.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1090	2.8	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
1090	5.7	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	Saddle rim.
1090	8.1	18	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1090	11.9	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			lip rounded edges, flattened top.
1090	22.6	3	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1090	27.3	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
1090	34.1	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1090	48.8	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1090	49.8	17	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		vertically incised, coiled (Santa Elena).
1090	50.8	3	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1090	69.9	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
1090	375.9	34	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1091	2.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1091	5.6	9	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1091	15.9	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		
1091	20	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1091	60.6	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1091	85.1	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	rim thickens at lip.
1091	152.4	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1091	153.7	20	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		7 incised/ broken coils (Santa Elena).
1091	217.9	12	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

Artifact Inventory
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1093	2.8	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1093	3.3	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1093	4.4	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1093	14.4	18	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1093	17.1	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1093	22	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1093	125.9	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1093	417	31	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1094	3.2	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1095	2.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina		possible carina or base?
1095	18.9	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1095	26.8	10	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1096	8.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina		
1096	80.7	8	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1097	35.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1098	3.4	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1098	9.4	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1098	15.1	4	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	Sand			
1098	35.2	9	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1099	0	1	Unidentified Metal Object					concretion?
1099	5.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1099	26.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	square	
1099	36.4	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
1099	81	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1099	399	33	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1100	18.8	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1100	32.4	1	Body sherds	Red Slip	quartz			
1100	39.8	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1100	65.2	14	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1101	4.3	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	small piece.
1101	6	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	internally thick, red paint along lip.
1101	7.1	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	square	
1101	10.8	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1101	38.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1101	72.3	13	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1102	69	6	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1103	5.4	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1103	17.8	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	

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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1103	35.7	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
1103	67.5	14	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1104	5.1	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
1104	57.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1104	414	15	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			2 w/ soot interior.
1105	8.2	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1105	19.6	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	
1105	39	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina	round	internally thickened rim.
1105	78	3	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	thickens @ lip, folded ext. lip.
1105	347.5	38	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1106	12.4	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1106	13.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			externally thickened rim.
1106	15.2	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			indeterminate lip shape, externally thick rim.
1106	25.4	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Unidentified		possible shoulder.
1106	28.7	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	externally thickened rim.
1106	47.3	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1106	531	29	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 has soot.
1107	21.5	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1107	40.7	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		
1107	56.6	2	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	externally thickened rim.
1107	74.2	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1107	451.4	25	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1108	14.8	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1108	17.2	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1108	64.1	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	round	thickens @ lip.
1108	264.2	21	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1109	9.3	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate	round	
1109	26	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	Sand		round	edge thins out at rim
1109	94.8	14	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1110	13.1	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1111	17.5	1	Deep and Convex Rim	unspecified	quartz		round	red paint on lip, externally thick rim.
1111	20.6	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1112	2.3	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1112	6.9	18	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			sherdlets.
1112	9.4	1	Unidentified Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1112	13.7	1	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1112	17.7	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina		

Artifact Inventory
 Site HU-7, Rio Anton Ruiz Data Recovery
 Humacao, Puerto Rico
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Bag No.	Weight (g)	Quantity	Artifact Category	Ceramic Surface Treatment	Temper	Secondary Feature	Lip Shape	Notes
1112	17.9	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Carina	square	
1112	21.9	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 flat, 1 dimpled base.
1112	51.2	2	Body sherds	Red Slip	quartz			
1112	52.5	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1112	69.7	5	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1112	512.4	56	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1113	7.3	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		
1113	8	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		round	
1113	8.9	1	Unidentified Rim	unspecified	quartz		round	Saddle rim, red painted lip, Monserrate
1113	10.3	2	Body sherds	unspecified	quartz			painted red ochre.
1113	20.6	2	Restricted and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz		square	
1113	30.2	3	Unidentified Rim	unspecified	quartz		round	painted red top lip.
1113	52.4	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1113	58.7	1	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
1113	64.7	1	Concave Rim	unspecified	quartz		round	painted red lip, internally thick rim.
1113	65.8	2	Base Sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			1 flat, 1 dimpled base.
1113	497.1	38	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1115	7.9	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1115	19.8	1	Concave Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Sharp Carina	round	
1115	34.4	1	Deep and Convex Rim	Plain unslipped	quartz	Soft Carina	square	
1116	11.9	2	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			
1117	29.6	1	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			soot interior.
1118	3.6	1	Body sherds	Incised	quartz	Handle frag., indeterminate		incised or has coils, Santa Elena.
1118	25.6	3	Body sherds	Plain unslipped	quartz			

APPENDIX IV

RESUMÉ OF PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

PETER E. SIEGEL

Principal Archeologist/Project Manager
John Milner Associates, Inc.
The Barclay
535 North Church Street
West Chester, PA 19380
(610) 436-9000 (phone)
(610) 436-8468 (fax)
psiegel@johnmilnerassociates.com

EDUCATION

Ph.D.	SUNY-Binghamton	Anthropology	1992
M.A.	SUNY-Binghamton	Anthropology	1982
B.A.	University of Delaware	Anthropology	1978
B.S.	University of Delaware	Entomology and Applied Ecology	1978

ADDITIONAL TRAINING

2000 Section 106 in the New Regulatory Environment: A Workshop for Consultants and their Clients. Course instructor: Dr. Lynne Sebastian. Sponsored by URS Greiner-Woodward Clyde, Florence, New Jersey.

1995 Section 106 Training: Introduction to Federal Projects and Historic Preservation Law. Sponsored by the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation and the General Services Administration. Course instructor: Dr. Thomas F. King. Philadelphia, Pennsylvania.

1988 On-site Museum Workshop in "Fundraising." Sponsored by the Smithsonian Institution and the Institute for Puerto Rican Culture. San Juan, Puerto Rico.

1988 On-site Museum Workshop in "Developing, Managing, and Maintaining Collections." Sponsored by the Smithsonian Institution and the Institute for Puerto Rican Culture. San Juan, Puerto Rico.

PROFESSIONAL CERTIFICATIONS

1999- Registered Professional Archaeologist
1999/2000 8-hour refresher training: Hazardous Waste Operator and Emergency Responder (HAZWOPER)
1998 40-hour HAZWOPER training

PROFESSIONAL AFFILIATIONS

American Anthropological Association
Society for American Archaeology
Society for Latin American Anthropology
New York Archaeological Council
Pennsylvania Archaeological Council
Asociación Puertorriqueña de Antropólogos y Arqueólogos
International Association for Caribbean Archaeology

PROFESSIONAL INTERESTS

Caribbean and Lowland South American archeology
Eastern North American archeology
Complex societies

Chiefdoms
Lithic microwear analysis
Spatial analysis
Quantitative methods
Ethnoarcheology

PROJECT EXPERIENCE (John Milner Associates, Inc.)

- 2001 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, John Milner Associates (JMA). Phase IA archeological reconnaissance and historic resources investigation, Route 23, Upper Merion Township, Pennsylvania. Boles Smyth, Upper Merion Township, and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 2000 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Harthman Tract, Estate Charlotte Amalie, St. Thomas, U. S. Virgin Islands. New South Associates.
- 2000 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey for the Kent County natural gas pipeline, Harrington and Milford Townships, Kent County, Delaware. Eastern Shore Natural Gas Pipeline Company, Dover, Delaware.
- 2000 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey and Phase II archeological evaluation for the Acorn Hills Development Project, New Hanover, Montgomery County, Pennsylvania. Sal Lapio, Inc.
- 2000 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase III data recoveries of Sites HU-6 and HU-7. Río Antón Ruíz flood control project, Punta Santiago, Humacao, Puerto Rico. New South Associates and U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Jacksonville District.
- 1999/2000 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Archeological testing, excavation, and laboratory analysis. Cuiabá Gas Pipeline, Departamento de Santa Cruz, Bolivia, South America. Dames & Moore.
- 1999 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey. Rainbow Elementary School Expansion, Chester County, Pennsylvania. Herbert, Rowland & Grubic, Inc.
- 1999 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey. City of Reading Sewerage Facilities, Berks County, Pennsylvania. BCM Engineers, Inc.
- 1999 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey. South Carolina pipeline, Aiken, Kershaw, and Marlboro Counties, South Carolina. New South Associates.
- 1999 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase IA archeological reconnaissance survey. Pocono International Raceway, Tunkhannock and Tobyhanna Townships, Monroe County, Pennsylvania. The Wilson T. Ballard Company.
- 1998 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey and Phase II archeological evaluations for the Athens Generating Project, Athens, Greene County, New York. U.S. Generating Company.
- 1997 Principal Investigator, sediment coring project. Maisabel wetland, Vega Baja, Puerto Rico. Sponsored by the Wenner-Gren Foundation for Anthropological Research and the Heinz Family Foundation.

- 1997 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Archeological reconnaissance survey. James River, Lynchburg, Virginia. Foster Wheeler Environmental Corporation.
- 1997 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey and Phase II archeological evaluation at Lake Gaston, Mecklenburg County, Virginia. New South Associates.
- 1997 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Route U.S. 206-Waterloo Road Intersection, Byram Township, Sussex County, New Jersey. New Jersey Department of Transportation.
- 1997 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the East Whiteland Ecology Park, East Whiteland Township, Chester County, Pennsylvania. DePallo Design & Planning.
- 1997 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey and geomorphological research for the Long Island Beach Reformulation Study, Suffolk County, New York. The Greeley-Polhemus Group and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, New York District.
- 1996/1997 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase III data recovery at Site 36CH128, Exton Mall Expansion, Chester County, Pennsylvania. The Rouse Company.
- 1996 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey and Phase II archeological evaluations of three sites. Route U.S. 1/Penns Neck Interchange, Mercer and Middlesex Counties, New Jersey. New Jersey Department of Transportation.
- 1996 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Geomorphological and archeological research for the Arthur Kill-Howland Hook Marine Terminal Channel, Richmond County, New York and Union County, New Jersey. The Greeley-Polhemus Group and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, New York District.
- 1996 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Red Lion Road Acme project, Philadelphia County, Pennsylvania. Environmental Resolutions, Inc. and American Stores Properties, Inc.
- 1996 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase IB archeological survey of the Mills at Rose Valley development project, Delaware County, Pennsylvania. Renaissance Properties, Inc.
- 1995-1996 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase III data recovery at the Fahs II Site, Northampton County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1995-1996 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase III data recovery at the Oberly Island Site, Northampton County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1995 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey for the Western Lehigh Relief Facilities project, Lehigh County, Pennsylvania. Roy F. Weston, Inc. and Lehigh County Authority.
- 1995 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of Route 21, Borough of Elmwood Park, Bergen County, New Jersey. New Jersey Department of Transportation.
- 1994 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of Route 1 and 9, Ridgfield Circle, Ridgfield Borough, Bergen County, New Jersey. New Jersey Department of Transportation.

- 1994 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of Route 46, Lodi Borough, Bergen County, New Jersey. New Jersey Department of Transportation.
- 1994 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of Interstate 78, Bedminster Township, Somerset County, New Jersey. New Jersey Department of Transportation.
- 1994 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase II archeological evaluation of nine sites in the Hunting Run Reservoir, Spotsylvania County, Virginia. Hayes, Seay, Mattern & Mattern, Inc. and Spotsylvania County Public Utilities.
- 1994 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Phase III data recovery at the Aud Site, St. Mary's County, Maryland. Maryland State Highway Administration.
- 1994 Principal Archeologist/Project Manager, JMA. Supplemental Phase I archeological survey of the Middletown bridge replacement. Middletown Township, Susquehanna County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1994 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological reconnaissance of Route 56, Bedford and Somerset Counties, Pennsylvania. The Wilson T. Ballard Company and the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1994 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase II archeological evaluation of the Evitts Creek I Site, Allegany County, Maryland. Maryland State Highway Administration.
- 1994 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase III archeological data recovery analysis of the Barking Road Site, Plum Borough, Allegheny County, Pennsylvania. NPW Consultants and CNG Transmission Corporation.
- 1993 Consultant to New South Associates. Directed fieldwork/wrote report for Phase III data recoveries of two sites in Vega Baja, Puerto Rico. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Jacksonville District.
- 1993 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of Route 26, Centre County, Pennsylvania. Boles, Smyth Associates. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1993 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase II archeological evaluation of the Biesecker Site, Gibson Township, Susquehanna County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1993 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase II archeological evaluation of the Heimbach Site, Snyder County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1993 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase II archeological evaluation of the Loretto Branch Site, Princess Anne, Somerset County, Maryland. Maryland State Highway Administration.
- 1992 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Rush Township bridge replacement, Susquehanna County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1992 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Railroad bridge replacement, Pittston Township, Luzerne County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1992 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Lakeside bridge replacement, New Milford Township, Susquehanna County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.

- 1992 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Hill Street realignment, Jessup Borough, Lackawanna County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1992 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Gibson bridge replacement, Susquehanna County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.
- 1992 Project Archeologist, JMA. Phase I archeological survey of the Middletown bridge replacement, Susquehanna County, Pennsylvania. Pennsylvania Department of Transportation.

PROJECT EXPERIENCE (Previous)

- 1999 Principal Investigator. University of Texas at Dallas. Indian Creek Archaeological Project, St. Paul, Antigua, West Indies.
- 1997 Principal Investigator. Sediment coring project. Maisabel wetland, Vega Baja, Puerto Rico. Sponsored by the Wenner-Gren Foundation for Anthropological Research and the Heinz Family Foundation for Latin American Archaeology.
- 1985-1992 Project Director. Centro de Investigaciones Indígenas de Puerto Rico (CIIPR). Maisabel Archaeological Project, Vega Baja, Puerto Rico.
- 1985 Ethnoarchaeological research. CIIPR. Shefariymo Village (Waiwai and Wapisiana Indians), Upper Essequibo River, southern Guyana.
- 1984-1985 Project Director. SUNY-Binghamton Lower Chenango Valley Survey. Developed and applied a probabilistic sampling design for the Lower Chenango Valley, New York.
- 1983 Project Director. Public Archaeology Facility (PAF), SUNY-Binghamton. Highway archaeological survey. Downsville, New York. State Education Department, New York State Museum and Science Service, Albany.
- 1983 Co-Project Director (with Dr. Judith A. Rasson). Wilkes College Archaeology Program, Wilkes College, Wilkes-Barre, Pennsylvania. Francis E. Walter Dam archaeological survey conducted for U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Philadelphia District.
- 1982 Laboratory Research Assistant, PAF, SUNY-Binghamton. Artifact analysis, Utquiagvik Archaeological Project, Pt. Barrow, Alaska.
- 1970 Crew Chief. PAF, SUNY-Binghamton. Various projects. Southern tier of New York State.
- 1981 Laboratory Research Assistant, PAF, SUNY-Binghamton. Artifact cataloguing, Rhode Island highway archaeological survey.
- 1981 Crew Chief. Rhode Island highway archaeological survey. PAF, SUNY-Binghamton.
- 1979-1980 Contract Archeology Program, Center for American Archeology, Kampsville, Illinois. Major excavation of Kuhlman Site (Late Woodland habitation site in Central Mississippi Valley).
- 1976 Field Research Assistant, Department of Anthropology, University of Delaware. Ethnoarchaeological research, Shipibo Indians, Ucayali River, Eastern Peru.
- 1975 Crew Member, Museum of Natural History and Department of Anthropology, University of Oregon. Survey and excavation, northwestern portion of Great Basin (Chewaukan Valley, southeastern Oregon, near town of Paisley). Supervised by Dr. C. Melvin Aikens.

1973 Volunteer, Hebrew University, excavation of Herodian-age building complex adjacent to the Western Wall, Old Jerusalem, Israel. Project Director: Dr. Benjamin Mazar.

CULTURAL RESOURCES REPORTS

- 2001 Phase I Archaeological Survey of the Harthman Tract, Estate Charlotte Amalie, St. Thomas, U. S. Virgin Islands. Submitted to the Harthman Family. New South Associates, Inc.
- 2000 Phase I Archeological Survey in Selected Portions of the Eastern Shore Natural Gas Pipeline, Harrington and Milford Townships, Kent County, Delaware. Submitted to Eastern Shore Natural Gas Company. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 2000 Phase I Archeological Survey and Phase II Archeological Evaluation in Conjunction with the Proposed Acorn Hills Development, New Hanover Township, Montgomery County, Pennsylvania. Submitted to Sal Lapio, Inc., Sellersville, Pennsylvania. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1999 A Phase I Archeological Survey of the Proposed 18th Ward Pumping Station Sewerage Facilities in the City of Reading, Berks County, Pennsylvania. Submitted to BCM Engineers, Plymouth Meeting, Pennsylvania. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1999 A Phase I Archeological Survey of the Proposed Rainbow Elementary School Expansion, Chester County, Pennsylvania. Submitted to Herbert, Rowland & Grubic, Inc. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1999 I-80 Point of Access Study, Pocono International Raceway, Monroe County, Pennsylvania: Reconnaissance Level Archeological and Historic Resources Investigation (co-author). Submitted to the Wilson T. Ballard Company, Shrewsbury, Pennsylvania and Pocono International Raceway, Long Pond, Pennsylvania. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1999 Archeological Data Recoveries at the Fahs II and Oberly Island Sites: Structure, Function, and Context in the Lower Lehigh Valley, Northampton County, Pennsylvania (co-author). Submitted to URS Greiner Woodward Clyde, King of Prussia, Pennsylvania and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation, Harrisburg. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1998 Background Research and Archeological Sensitivity Assessment for the Athens Transmission Line Project, Greene, Columbia, and Dutchess Counties, New York. Submitted to U.S. Generating Company. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1998 Phase I Archeological Survey and Phase II Archeological Evaluations for the Athens Generating Project, Greene County, New York (co-author). Submitted to U.S. Generating Company. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1998 Roanoke Rapids and Gaston Hydropower Relicensing Project: Cultural Resources Testing/Evaluation of Archaeological Site 44MC113, Mecklenburg County, Virginia. Technical Report 596. New South Associates, Stone Mountain, Georgia. Submitted to Foster Wheeler Environmental Corporation, Livingston, New Jersey. FERC No. 2009.
- 1998 Roanoke Rapids and Gaston Hydropower Relicensing Project: Cultural Resources Survey of High Probability Areas Parallel to the Shoreline: Brunswick and Mecklenburg Counties, Virginia. Technical Report 597. New South Associates, Stone Mountain, Georgia. Submitted to Foster Wheeler Environmental Corporation, Livingston, New Jersey. FERC No. 2009.

- 1998 Cultural Resources Study, Fire Island Inlet to Montauk Point, Suffolk County, New York, Reformulation Study (co-author). Submitted to The Greeley-Polhemus Group and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, New York District. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1997 Addendum, Phase I Archeological Survey and Architectural Resources Investigation, Route U.S. 206-Waterloo Road Intersection Improvements, Byram Township, Sussex County, New Jersey (co-author). Submitted to New Jersey Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1997 Phase I Archeological Survey in Conjunction with the Proposed East Whiteland Ecology Park, East Whiteland Township, Chester County, Pennsylvania. Submitted to DePallo Design & Planning. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 A Geomorphological and Archeological Analysis of the Arthur Kill-Howland Hook Marine Terminal Channel, Richmond County, New York and Union County, New Jersey (co-author). Submitted to The Greeley-Polhemus Group and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, New York District. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 A Phase I Archeological Survey of the Proposed Red Lion Road Acme Store in Philadelphia County, Pennsylvania. Submitted to Environmental Resolutions, Inc. and American Stores Properties, Inc. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 Luzerne County, S.R. 1018, Section 370, Dallas Township Bridge Replacement, Phase I Archeological Survey and Historic Resources Investigation (co-author). Submitted to Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 Preliminary Cultural Resources Review Form, Proposed S.R. 0029, Section M01 Road Widening, from S.R. 0113 Intersection in Rahns to S.R. 0073 Intersection South of the Borough of Schwenksville, Perkiomen Township, Montgomery County, Pennsylvania (co-author). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 Phase I Archeological Survey, Route 21 Freeway Wetland Mitigation Site, Borough of Elmwood Park, Bergen County, New Jersey. Pennsylvania. Submitted to the New Jersey Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 A Phase IB Archeological Survey of the The Mills at Rose Valley Development Project, Delaware County, Pennsylvania. Submitted to Renaissance Properties, Inc. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 Phase III Data Recovery at the Aud Site (Site 18ST634), St. Mary's County, Maryland (co-author). Maryland State Highway Administration Archeological Report No. 111. Submitted to the Maryland State Highway Administration. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1996 Phase III Data Recovery at the Heimbach Site (Site 36SN223), Monroe Township, Snyder County, Pennsylvania, Penns Creek Bridge Replacement, S.R. 1014, Section 001 (co-author). Submitted to Greiner Engineering Sciences, Inc. and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1995 Phase II Archeological Evaluation of the Motts Run Site (44SP254), for the Proposed Motts Run Water Filtration Plant, Spotsylvania County, Virginia (co-author). Submitted to Hayes, Seay, Mattern & Mattern. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1995 Cambria, Westmoreland and Indiana Counties, S.R. 56 West End Traffic Study, Johnstown to U.S. 22, Cultural Resources Investigation (co-author). Submitted to the Wilson T. Ballard Company and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.

- 1995 Lehigh County, Western Lehigh Relief Interceptor, Phase I Archeological Survey. Submitted to Roy F. Weston, Inc. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1995 Wyoming County, S.R. 0292, Section 770, Bowman's Creek Bridge Replacement, Phase I Archeological Survey (co-author). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1995 S.R. 56 Planning Study, Windber to Bedford, Somerset and Bedford Counties, Reconnaissance Level Archeological and Historic Resources Investigations (co-author). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1995 Phase II Archeological Evaluation of Nine Sites in the Proposed Hunting Run Reservoir Area, Spotsylvania County, Virginia (co-author). Submitted to Hayes, Seay, Mattern & Mattern. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1995 Susquehanna County, S.R. 0547, Section 570, Gibson Bridge Replacement, Phase I Archeological Survey and Phase II Archeological Evaluation (co-author). Submitted to Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1994 The Barking Road Site: A Multicomponent Prehistoric Occupation in Plum Borough, Allegheny County, Pennsylvania (co-author). Prepared for CNG Transmission Corporation, Clarksburg, West Virginia. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1994 Susquehanna County, S.R. 0858, Section 572, Middletown Township Bridge Replacement, Supplemental Phase I Archeological Survey (co-author). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1994 Phase II Archeological Evaluation of the Evitts Creek I Site (Site 18AG186), Allegany County, Maryland, U.S. 220 Relocated, Contract No. A 555-000-670, (co-author). Maryland State Highway Administration Archeological Report No. 90. Submitted to the Maryland State Highway Administration. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1994 Phase I Archeological Survey, Interstate 78, Section 3G, Truck Rest Area, Bedminster Township, Somerset County, New Jersey (co-author). Submitted to the New Jersey Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1994 Centre County, S.R. 26, Section C04, Phase I Archeological Survey. Submitted to Boles, Smyth Associates. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1994 A Phase I Archeological Survey and Architectural Resources Investigation, Route 46 Drainage Improvements Project, Lodi Borough, Bergen County, New Jersey (co-author). Submitted to the New Jersey Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1994 A Phase I Archeological Survey and Architectural Resources Investigation, Route 1 and 9 Ridgefield Circle Improvements Project, Ridgefield Borough, Bergen County, New Jersey (co-author). Submitted to the New Jersey Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Susquehanna County, S.R. 0858, Section 572, Middletown Township Bridge Replacement, Phase I Archeological Survey and Historic Resources Investigation (co-author). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Susquehanna County, S.R. 0547, Section 570, Gibson Bridge Replacement, Phase II Archeological Evaluation Management Summary. Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Susquehanna County, S.R. 0492, Section 570, Lakeside Bridge Replacement, New Milford Township, Phase I Archeological Survey and Historic Resources Investigation (co-

- author). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Snyder County, S.R. 1014, Section 001, Penns Creek Bridge, Supplemental Phase II Archeological Evaluation Management Summary (co-author). Submitted to Greiner Engineering Sciences. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Phase II Archeological Testing of the Loretto Branch Site (18SO147), University of Maryland Eastern Shore Access Road, Alternate 6/6A Modified, Contract Number S 365-101-171 (co-author). Maryland State Highway Administration Archeological Report No. 85. Submitted to the Maryland State Highway Administration. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Archeological Data Recovery of the Mayview Site (36AL134), Mayview Wetlands Replacement Area, Upper St. Clair Township, Allegheny County, Pennsylvania (editor). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Archeological Data Recovery at El Palmar de las Animas (VB-27) and the Concrete Well (VB-32) Sites, Río Cibuco Flood Control Project, Municipio de Vega Baja, Puerto Rico (co-author). Technical Report 206. New South Associates, Stone Mountain, Georgia. Submitted to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Jacksonville, Florida.
- 1993 Susquehanna County, S.R. 0267, Section 571, Rush Township Bridge Replacement, Phase I Archeological Survey. Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Luzerne County, S.R. 2035, Section 370, Railroad Bridge Replacement, Phase I Archeological Survey. Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1993 Lackawanna County, S.R. 1014 at S.R. 0247, Hill Street Realignment, Phase I Archeological Survey and Historic Resources Investigation (co-author). Submitted to the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. John Milner Associates, Inc.
- 1983 Cultural Resources Management Survey for PIN 9014.13, Routes 206 and 30, Hamlet of Downsville, Colchester, New York. Department of Anthropology, State University of New York at Binghamton, Public Archaeology Facility. Submitted to the New York State Museum and Science Service, Albany.
- 1983 A Cultural Resources Report on Selected Areas in the Vicinity of the Proposed Modification at F.E. Walter Dam (co-author). Wilkes College Archaeology Program, Department of Sociology-Anthropology, Wilkes College, Wilkes-Barre, Pennsylvania. Submitted to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Philadelphia District.

PUBLICATIONS

- 2000 Review of *Excavations at the Indian Creek Site, Antigua, West Indies* by Irving Rouse and Birgit Faber Morse (Yale University Publications in Anthropology, No. 82). *Journal of Anthropological Research* 56:418-420.
- 1999 Contested Places and Places of Contest: The Evolution of Social Power and Ceremonial Space in Prehistoric Puerto Rico. *Latin American Antiquity* 10:209-238.
- 1999 Putting the Indian Creek Site Excavation into Context. *Museum of Antigua and Barbuda Historical and Archaeological Newsletter* 66:9.
- 1998 Review of *The Indigenous People of the Caribbean*, edited by Samuel M. Wilson (University Press of Florida, Gainesville). *Latin American Antiquity* 9:180-182.

- 1997 Ancestor Worship and Cosmology among the Taíno. In *Taíno: Pre-Columbian Art and Culture from the Caribbean*, edited by Fatima Bercht, Estrellita Brodsky, John Alan Farmer, and Dicey Taylor, pp. 106-111. The Monacelli Press and El Museo del Barrio, New York.
- 1996 An Interview with Irving Rouse. *Current Anthropology* 37:671-689.
- 1996 Ideology and Culture Change in Prehistoric Puerto Rico: A View from the Community. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 23:313-333.
- 1995 The Archaeology of Community Organization in the Tropical Lowlands: A Case Study from Puerto Rico. In *Archaeology in the American Tropics: Current Analytical Methods and Applications*, edited by Peter W. Stahl, pp. 42-65. Cambridge University Press, New York.
- 1995 Review of *The Archaeology of Pacific Nicaragua*, by Frederick W. Lange, Payson D. Sheets, Anibal Martinez, and Suzanne Abel-Vidor (University of New Mexico Press, Albuquerque). *The Latin American Anthropology Review* (Spring 1993) 5(1):45-46.
- 1993 The First Documented Prehistoric Gold-Copper Alloy Artefact from the West Indies (with Kenneth P. Severin). *Journal of Archaeological Science* 20:67-79.
- 1993 Saladoid Survival Strategies: Evidence from Site Locations. *Proceedings of the International Congress for Caribbean Archaeology* 14:315-337. Barbados.
- 1992 *Ideology, Power, and Social Complexity in Prehistoric Puerto Rico*. Ph.D. dissertation, SUNY-Binghamton. University Microfilms, Ann Arbor.
- 1991 The Maisabel Archaeological Project: A Long Term Multi-Disciplinary Investigation (with Peter G. Roe). *Proceedings of the International Congress for Caribbean Archaeology* 12:109-115. Martinique.
- 1991 Sampling for Site Structure and Spatial Organization in the Saladoid: A Case Study (with David J. Bernstein). *Proceedings of the International Congress for Caribbean Archaeology* 12:87-107. Martinique.
- 1991 Political Evolution in the Caribbean. *Proceedings of the International Congress for Caribbean Archaeology* 13:232-250. Curaçao, Netherlands Antilles.
- 1991 On the Antillean Connection for the Introduction of Cultigens into Eastern North America. *Current Anthropology* 32:332-334.
- 1991 Occupational History of the Maisabel Site: A Progress Report. Special Publication No. 7, "Topics in Caribbean Anthropology," edited by James Cusick and Kathleen Barnes. *Florida Journal of Anthropology* 16:65-79.
- 1991 Migration Research in Saladoid Archaeology: A Review. *The Florida Anthropologist* 44(1):79-91.
- 1990 Proyecto arqueológico de Maisabel. *Patrimonio: Boletín de la Oficina Estatal de Preservación Histórica* 1(7):7-10.
- 1990 Ethnoarchaeological Study of a Waiwai Village in the Tropical Forest of Southern Guyana. *Proceedings of the International Congress for Caribbean Archaeology* 11:400-417. San Juan, Puerto Rico.
- 1990 Demographic and Architectural Retrodiction: An Ethnoarchaeological Case Study in the South American Tropical Lowlands. *Latin American Antiquity* 1:319-346.

- 1989 Site Structure, Demography, and Social Complexity in the Early Ceramic Age of the Caribbean. In *Early Ceramic Population Lifeways and Adaptive Strategies in the Caribbean*, edited by Peter E. Siegel, pp. 193-245. B.A.R. International Series No. 506. British Archaeological Reports, Oxford.
- 1989 *Early Ceramic Population Lifeways and Adaptive Strategies in the Caribbean* (editor). B.A.R. International Series No. 506. British Archaeological Reports, Oxford.
- 1986 The Maisabel Project Excavation. *Arqueología* 2(1):20-21.
- 1986 Shipibo Archaeo-Ethnography: Site Formation Processes and Archaeological Interpretation (with Peter G. Roe). *World Archaeology* 18:96-115.
- 1986 More on Functional Variability within an Assemblage of Endscrapers: A Reply to Hayden and Bamforth. *Lithic Technology* 15:71-78.
- 1985 Edge Angle as a Functional Indicator: A Test. *Lithic Technology* 14:90-94.
- 1984 Prehistoric Behavioral/Locational Organization in the Lower Chenango River Valley, New York. Ms. on file, Department of Anthropology, State University of New York, Binghamton.
- 1984 Functional Variability within an Assemblage of Endscrapers. *Lithic Technology* 13:35-51.
- 1982 The Life History of a Shipibo Compound: Ethnoarchaeology in the Peruvian Montaña (junior author). *Journal of Archaeology and Anthropology* 5(2):94-118.
- 1982 *A Feature Analysis of a Late Woodland Bluff-Top Encampment Located in the Central Mississippi Valley*. M.A. thesis, SUNY-Binghamton.
- 1981 A Functional Analysis of an Assemblage of Inupiat Eskimo End Scrapers. In *The 1981 Excavations at the Utquiagvik Archaeological Site, Barrow, Alaska*, edited by Albert A. Dekin, Jr., chapter 13, Department of Anthropology, State University of New York at Binghamton, Public Archaeology Facility. Submitted to the Bureau of Indian Affairs and the National Park Service, 540 West 5th Avenue, Anchorage, Alaska 99501.
- 1977 The Making of a Midden: Ethnoarchaeology in the Tropical Rain Forest of Peru. Ms. on file, Department of Anthropology, University of Delaware, Newark.

LECTURES AND PAPERS PRESENTED AT PROFESSIONAL MEETINGS

"Oberly Island: Trend and Tradition in the Lower Lehigh Valley, Pennsylvania." Paper presented (with Robert G. Kingsley and Tod L. Benedict) at 65th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, Philadelphia, 2000.

"The Oberly Island Site: Prehistoric Late Archaic/Late Woodland Adaptations in the Lower Lehigh Valley. Paper presented in "Byways to the Past: The First Annual Conference on Historic and Archaeological Investigations in Pennsylvania Transportation Projects." Sponsored by the Federal Highway Administration, the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation, and Indiana University of Pennsylvania. Indiana, Pennsylvania, 2000.

"Compliance on Route 33: Major Excavation of the Oberly Island Site." Lecture presented to the Forks of the Delaware Chapter 14, Pennsylvania Archaeological Society, Easton. 1999.

"Culture and Environment in Prehistoric Puerto Rico." Paper presented in the symposium, "Culture and Environment in the Lowland Neotropics" (with John G. Jones, Deborah M. Pearsall, and Daniel P. Wagner). Organized and chaired by Peter E. Siegel, 64th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, Chicago. 1999.

"Waiwai Ethnography, Lowland South American Cosmology, and Caribbean Ceramic-Age Archaeology: Some Unifying Threads." Lecture presented to the Department of Social and Cultural Anthropology, Oxford University, Oxford, England. 1998.

"Community Organization and Cosmology in the Lowland Neotropics." Lecture presented to the Department of Anthropology, Florida Atlantic University, Boca Raton. 1998.

"Prehistory of the Caribbean and Lowland South America." Lecture presented to the students enrolled in Anthropology 285 (Prehistoric Peoples of the Americas). Department of Anthropology, State University of New York, Stony Brook. 1997.

"Ideology, Space, and Status: The Evolution of Taíno Chiefdoms." Paper presented in the symposium, "Alternative Models for Social Complexity in Latin America." Organized by John W. Hoopes and Anna C. Roosevelt, 61st Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology. New Orleans. 1996.

"Woodland Period Activity Organization and Habitat Selection in Southern Maryland: A View from the Aud Site" (with Stuart A. Reeve). Paper presented at the 62nd Annual Meeting of the Eastern States Archeological Federation, Wilmington, Delaware. 1995.

"The Heimbach Site: Technological, Spatial, and Chemical Analysis of Quarry Site Artifacts" (with Robert G. Kingsley and Tod L. Benedict). Paper presented at the 62nd Annual Meeting of the Eastern States Archeological Federation, Wilmington, Delaware. 1995.

"Prehistory of the Caribbean and Lowland South America." Lecture presented to the students enrolled in Anthropology 285 (Prehistoric Peoples of the Americas). Department of Anthropology, State University of New York, Stony Brook. 1995.

"Ideology and Culture Change: A View from the Community." Paper presented in the symposium, "It's a Small World After All: The Study of Communities and Their Organization." Organized by Peter E. Siegel and Michael J. Kolb, 59th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology. Anaheim, California. 1994.

"Lowland Cosmology as an Interpretive Framework for Prehistoric Community Organization: The Maisabel Site, Puerto Rico." Paper presented at the 57th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, Pittsburgh. 1992.

"Art, World View, and Culture of the Tainos and their Ancestors: An Ethnohistoric and Archaeological Perspective." Lecture presented in the series "The Year 1492 at Home and Abroad." Sponsored by the Department of Humanities and Communications, Drexel University, Philadelphia. 1992.

"Current Research in Caribbean Saladoid Archaeology and the Maisabel Excavation." Lecture presented to the Foundation for Field Research and Florida Museum of Natural History staff. Pearls, St. Andrews, Grenada. 1990.

"Thermoluminescence (TL) Dating and Archaeological Interpretation at Maisabel." Paper presented at the III Encuentro de Investigadores de la Asociación Puertorriqueña de Antropólogos y Arqueólogos, Universidad del Sagrado Corazón, San Juan, Puerto Rico. 1989.

"Baskets to Bones: Ethnography and Archaeology in the Caribbean." Lecture presented to the Department of Geology, University of Puerto Rico, Mayagüez. 1989.

"Demographic and Architectural Organization Among Early Ceramic Groups in the Caribbean." Paper presented in the symposium, "Early Ceramic Population Lifeways and Adaptive Strategies in the Caribbean." Organized by Peter E. Siegel, 53rd Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology. Phoenix. 1988.

"Small Village Demographic and Architectural Organization: An Example from the Tropical Lowlands." Paper presented in the symposium, "Site Structure and Spatial Organization of Sedentary Communities." Organized by Philip J. Arnold III and Michael P. Smyth, 52nd Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology. Toronto. 1987.

"Ethnographic Tyranny in Northwest Alaska: A Case Study of an Archaeological Rebellion." Paper presented in the symposium, "Lithic Experiments in Archaeology: Case Studies in Replication and Usewear Research." Organized by William F. Andrefsky and Paula Bienenfeld, 49th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology. Portland, Oregon. 1984.

"An Archaeo-Ethnographic Spatial Analysis of Two Shipibo House Compounds: Implications for Site Formation Processes and Interpreting the Archaeological Record." Paper presented in the symposium, "Ethnoarchaeology of Refuse Disposal" (with Peter G. Roe). Organized by Edward Staski and Livingston D. Sutro, 49th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology. Portland, Oregon. 1984.

"A Quantitative Method for Describing and Analyzing Feature Morphology." Paper presented at the 48th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology. Pittsburgh. 1983.

"A Functional Analysis of an Assemblage of Inupiat Eskimo Endscrapers: Morphological, Edge Angle, and Ethnographic Implications." Paper presented at the 23rd Annual Meeting of the Northeastern Anthropological Association. Syracuse, New York. 1983.

"A Lithic Microwear and Spatial Analysis of a Late Woodland Blufftop site" (with Richard B. Hughes). Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the Eastern States Archaeological Federation. Albany, New York. 1980.

SYMPOSIA

Organizer and chairperson of symposium for 64th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, March 24 - March 28, 1999, Chicago, Illinois. "Culture and Environment in the Lowland Neotropics."

Discussant for "Recent Directions in Caribbean Prehistory: Beyond Migration," held at the 62nd Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, April 2-April 6, 1997, Nashville, Tennessee. Organized by Mary Jane Berman and L. Antonio Curet.

Co-organizer and chairperson of symposium for 59th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, April 20-April 24, 1994, Anaheim, California. "It's a Small World After All: The Study of Communities and Their Organization."

Discussant for "The Late Ceramic Age in the Northeast Caribbean," held at the 57th Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, April 8-April 12, 1992, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania. Organized by David R. Watters.

Organizer and chairperson of symposium for 53rd Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, April 27-May 1, 1988, Phoenix, Arizona. "Early Ceramic Population Lifeways and Adaptive Strategies in the Caribbean."

SOLICITED REVIEWS PROVIDED FOR:

Journal of Field Archaeology (1)

American Antiquity (1)

Latin American Antiquity (6)

Journal of Caribbean Archaeology (1)

National Science Foundation (10)

Wenner-Gren Foundation for Anthropological Research (9)

GRANTS AND SUPPORT

- 1997 Wenner-Gren Foundation for Anthropological Research. Regular Grant Program (Grant No. 6167). *Horticultural and Environmental Reconstruction in Prehistoric Puerto Rico.*
- 1997 H. John Heinz III Charitable Fund of the Heinz Family Foundation. Latin American Archaeological Field Research Grant Program. *Horticultural and Environmental Reconstruction in Prehistoric Puerto Rico.* Co-Principal Investigator with Deborah M. Pearsall.

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

- 1999 Instructor, University of Texas at Dallas, Summer Archaeology Field School. Indian Creek Site, Antigua, West Indies.
- 1992 Instructor, Department of Anthropology, University of Delaware. Introduction to Prehistoric Archaeology.
- 1984 Instructor, SUNY-Binghamton, Summer Archaeology Field School. Chenango Valley, New York.

SCHOLARSHIPS, ACADEMIC AWARDS, OTHER ACADEMIC-RELATED ACHIEVEMENTS

- 1989 National Science Foundation. Doctoral Dissertation Research Grant (BNS88-22317). *Occupational History of an Early Ceramic Age Settlement on the North Coast of Puerto Rico.*
- 1984 SUNY-Binghamton Research Foundation Seed Grant. *Prehistoric Behavioral/Locational Organization in the Lower Chenango River Valley, New York.*
- 1976 University of Delaware Research Foundation Grants-in-Aid. *Ethnoarchaeological Study of Two Shipibo House Compounds.*

EMPLOYMENT HISTORY

- 1994- Principal Archeologist/Project Manager
John Milner Associates, Inc.
West Chester, Pennsylvania
- 1992-1994 Project Archeologist
John Milner Associates, Inc.
West Chester, Pennsylvania
- 1993 Consulting Archeologist
New South Associates
Stone Mountain, Georgia
- 1992 Instructor
Department of Anthropology
University of Delaware, Newark
- 1985-1992 Research Associate
Centro de Investigaciones Indígenas de Puerto Rico
San Juan, Puerto Rico
- 1984-1985 Project Director
Lower Chenango Valley Archaeological Survey
SUNY-Binghamton

- 1984 Instructor
Summer Archaeology Field School
SUNY-Binghamton
- 1983 Project Director
Public Archaeology Facility
SUNY-Binghamton Highway Archaeological Survey
Downsville, New York
- 1983 Co-Project Director
Wilkes College Archaeology Program
Wilkes-Barre, Pennsylvania
- 1982 Laboratory Research Assistant
Public Archaeology Facility
SUNY-Binghamton
Utquiagvik Archaeological Project
- 1981-1982 Crew Chief
Various Projects
Public Archaeology Facility
SUNY-Binghamton
- 1981 Laboratory Research Assistant
Public Archaeology Facility
SUNY-Binghamton
Rhode Island Archaeological Survey
- 1979-1980 Contract Archeology Program
Center for American Archeology
Kampsville, Illinois
- 1975 Crew Member
Museum of Natural History and Department of Anthropology
University of Oregon